

SIGNATURES OF SECULAR EVOLUTION IN DISK GALAXIES

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In loving memory of my uncle César

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Abstract

In this thesis we shed light on the formation and evolution of disk galaxies, which often host a stellar bar (about 2/3 of cases). In particular, we address the bar-driven secular evolution, that is, the steady redistribution of stellar and gaseous material through the disk induced by the bar torques and resonances. We characterize the mass distribution of the disks in the Spitzer Survey of Stellar Structure in Galaxies (S⁴G, Sheth et al. 2010) and study the properties of the different stellar structure components and the interplay between them.

We use 3.6 μm photometry for ~ 1300 face-on and moderately inclined disk galaxies to analyze the frequency, dimensions, orientations and shapes of stellar bars, spiral arms, rings, (ring)lenses, and barlenses (i.e. lens-like structures embedded in the bars). We calculate the strength of the bars in the S⁴G via ellipse fitting, Fourier decomposition of the galaxy images, and from the gravitational tangential-to-radial forces. We also estimate the stellar contribution to the circular velocity, allowing us to analyze the coupling between non-baryonic and stellar matter within the optical disk. We average stellar density profiles (1D), the disk(+bulge) component of the rotation curve, and stellar bars (2D) as a function of fundamental galaxy parameters.

We complement the study with integral-field unit kinematic data from Seidel et al. (2015b) for a subsample of 16 S⁴G barred galaxies. We quantify the bar-induced perturbation strengths in the stellar and gaseous disk from the kinematics, and show that they agree with the estimates obtained from the images. We also use H_α Fabry-Perot observations from Erroz-Ferrer et al. (2015) for 29 S⁴G disk galaxies to study the inner slope of the rotation curves.

We provide possible observational evidence for the growth of bars in a Hubble time. We demonstrate the role of bars causing the spreading of the disk and the enhancement of the central stellar concentration. Our observations support the idea that Boxy/Peanut bulges in face-on perspective manifest as barlenses, that are often identified in early-type galaxies hosting strong bars, and some of them also as inner lenses. We find that the amount of dark matter within the optical disk scales with the total stellar mass, as expected in the Λ CDM models. We also confirm that the observed inner velocity gradient is correlated with the central surface brightness, showing a strong connection between the inner shape of the

potential well and the central stellar density.

We show that disks and bars in early-type ($T < 5 \equiv \text{Sc}$) and late-type ($T \geq 5$) disk galaxies, or alternatively in galaxies having total stellar masses greater or smaller than $10^{10} M_{\odot}$, are characterized by very distinct properties. Late-type disks are less centrally concentrated (many galaxies are bulge-less) and present a larger halo-to-stellar mass ratio, what probably affects the disk stability properties. The detection of bars in late-type galaxies is strongly dependent on the identification criteria. On average, bars in early-type spirals ($T = 0 - 2$) are longer (both in physical units and relative to the disk) and have larger density amplitudes than the intermediate-type spirals ($T \approx 5$), and the bar lengths among the latest-types in the S⁴G are also larger. In comparison to earlier types, the bars in late-type systems show larger tangential-to-radial force ratios. This result holds even when the estimated dark halo effect is included.

Key words: galaxies: structure - galaxies: statistics - galaxies: evolution - galaxies: barred - galaxies: dark matter

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LIST OF ORIGINAL PAPERS

The present thesis incorporates an introductory part and the following papers, referred in the text by their Roman numerals:

- I. **Díaz-García, S.**, Salo, H., Laurikainen, E., and Herrera-Endoqui, M., *Characterization of galactic bars from S^4G imaging*, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*. 587, A160 (2016).
- II. Herrera-Endoqui, M., **Díaz-García, S.**, Laurikainen, E., and Salo, H., *Catalogue of the morphological features in the Spitzer Survey of Stellar Structure in Galaxies (S^4G)*, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*. 582, A86 (2015).
- III. Seidel, M. K., Falcón-Barroso, J., Martínez-Valpuesta, I., **Díaz-García, S.**, Laurikainen, E., Salo, H., and Knapen, J. H., *The BaLRoG project - I. Quantifying the influence of bars on the kinematics of nearby galaxies*, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*. 451, 936 (2015).
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- V. **Díaz-García, S.**, Salo, H., and Laurikainen, E., *Stellar mass distribution of S^4G disk galaxies and signatures of bar-induced secular evolution*, *Astronomy & Astrophysics* (2016) (Accepted, in press).

Author contributions

All the papers included in this thesis are results of teamwork. The author of the thesis was the corresponding author of Paper I and Paper V, where he led the research and manuscript production. In Paper II, he participated in the measurement of the sizes and position angles of stellar bars with different methodologies, and in the quality flag assessment. He also performed ellipse fitting for a subsample of galaxies. In Paper III, he carried out all the bar length and strength measurements based on photometry, and he derived gravitational torques from a set of N-body simulations. He also carried out tests to determine the optimal way to measure the bar-induced perturbation strength from kinematics, and he collaborated in the writing of some sections of the manuscript. In Paper IV, he calculated the disk component of the circular velocity using $3.6 \mu\text{m}$ photometry and contaminant-free mass maps. He performed several tests to study the uncertainty related to the thickness of the disk and the mass-to-light ratio, and he obtained all the bar parameters.

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2. Sánchez-Menguiano, L., Pérez, I., Zurita, A., Martínez-Valpuesta, I., Aguerri, J. A. L., Sánchez, S. F., Comerón, S., and **Díaz-García, S.**, *On the morphology of dust lanes in galactic bars*, Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society. 450, 2670 (2015).
3. Erroz-Ferrer, S., Knapen, J. H., Leaman, R., Cisternas, M., Font, J., Beckman, J. E., Sheth, K., Muñoz-Mateos, J. C., **Díaz-García, S.**, Bosma, A., Athanassoula, E., Elmegreen, B. G., Ho, L. C., Kim, T., Laurikainen, E., Martínez-Valpuesta, I., Meidt, S. E., and Salo, H., *H_α kinematics of S^4G spiral galaxies - II. Data description and non-circular motions*, Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society. 451, 1004 (2015).
4. **Díaz-García, S.**, Salo, H., and Laurikainen, E., *The stellar mass distribution of S^4G disk galaxies*, IAU 321 proceedings. (2016).
5. **Díaz-García, S.**, Salo, H., and Laurikainen, E., *The halo-to-stellar mass ratio in the S^4G* , IAU 321 proceedings. (2016).

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Chapter 1

Introduction

In this chapter we review the most important theoretical and observational work that has been done in the field of galaxies, which are the objects of study in this thesis. We mainly focus on disk galaxies, with particular emphasis on stellar bars. Fundamental progress has been achieved in the past years in the understanding of how disk galaxies formed and evolved, but many questions remain.

1.1 Galaxies: A general overview.

Galaxies are the basic building blocks of the Universe. They are gravitationally coupled collections of stars, interstellar medium of gas and dust, and quite possibly dark (i.e. non-visible) matter. The number of stars within a galaxy varies from a few millions (dwarf galaxies), or even less, to $\sim 10^{14}$ (giant galaxies). Disk galaxies are formed by a flat rotating disk and, theoretically, a massive dark halo. In many cases, they also contain a protuberant central stellar component, commonly known as a bulge, which has older stars than the disk.

The light emitted by galaxies can be observed in almost all wavelengths of the electromagnetic spectrum, including X-rays, ultraviolet, visible, infrared and radio. In the optical spectrum, the colors of stars vary from bluish-white through to red, indicating their effective temperature. The most massive, youngest and hottest stars tend to emit in the bluer parts of the spectrum.

The Milky Way (MW hereafter)¹ is the disk galaxy where the sun resides, orbiting the galactic center at a distance of ~ 8.0 – 8.5 kiloparsecs (e.g. Gillessen et al. 2009). In 1750, Thomas Wright proposed that the MW could be a flattened disk of stars (Wright 1750), and that some of the nebulae visible on a starry night in the sky could be independent MWs. In 1755, Immanuel Kant coined the term *island Universe* to refer to these distant nebulae (Kant 1755). The Persian astronomer Al-Sufi had already discovered our neighbor galaxy Andromeda (M 31) in the tenth century and described it as a *cloud*.

¹Occasionally, we will refer to the Milky Way as the Galaxy, with capital G.

Figure 1.1: The Hubble tuning fork. Credit: Courtesy NASA, ESA, and The Hubble Heritage Team (STScI/AURA).

The total mass of the MW is around $1\text{--}5 \cdot 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ (e.g. Phelps et al. 2013; Kafle et al. 2014), where M_{\odot} refers to the mass of the sun. Stars account for roughly $5 \cdot 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ (e.g. McMillan 2011). The stars in the MW extend up to ~ 100000 light-years (~ 30 kpc) in diameter (e.g. Rix & Bovy 2013). The mass of the interstellar gas ($\sim 90\%$ hydrogen and $\sim 10\%$ helium) in the MW is $\sim 10 - 15\%$ that of the stars, while dust comprises $\sim 1\%$ of the gas mass (e.g. Sparke & Gallagher 2000). Roughly one half of the gas inside the sun orbit is in the form of clouds of molecular hydrogen, that only occupy $\sim 1\%$ of the interstellar medium.

Most disk galaxies are characterized by a thin and a thick disks (e.g. Yoachim & Dalcanton 2006; Comerón et al. 2011), which is the case also with the MW (Gilmore & Reid 1983). The thick disk tends to have stars substantially older (more than ~ 8 billion years) than those of the thin disk. Extending beyond the disk, many disk galaxies also present a faint and roughly spherical halo (e.g. Gilmore et al. 1989) composed of very old stars (more than ~ 10 Gyr). Some of these stars are gravitationally bounded forming globular clusters. Unlike the disk, the stellar halo is dominated by random motions.

1.1.1 Morphological classification

The first galaxy classification system is the so-called *Hubble Tuning Fork* (see Fig. 1.1), used by the American astronomer Edwin Hubble after he discovered the true nature of galaxies and how far outside the MW they really were (Hubble

Figure 1.2: The barred spiral galaxy NGC 1300, imaged with the *Hubble Space Telescope (HST)*. Credit: Courtesy NASA, ESA, and The Hubble Heritage Team (STScI/AURA).

1926, 1936). The most detailed and updated galaxy classification, used in this thesis, has been published by Buta et al. (2015).

Primarily, galaxies can be divided into ellipticals and spirals. The former are characterized by a smoothly declining luminosity gradient with very little or no presence of a disk component. Subclasses of ellipticals (E0-7) are defined as a function of the apparent ellipticity. Spiral galaxies are a type of disk galaxies in which a spiral pattern is observed in their morphology, typically with two spiral arms starting in the central parts. Based on the mass of the bulge and on the opening angle of the arms, spiral galaxies are classified as Sa-Sc. Sa galaxies are the spirals hosting the most prominent bulges and the most tightly wrapped arms. The galaxies in the left sector of the Tuning Fork (E/Sa) are often referred as early-types, while the galaxies on the right sector are named late-types, based on the evolution of galaxies envisaged by Hubble. Nowadays, we know that such an evolution is unrealistic. There is also a transition type between spirals and ellipticals, the lenticular galaxies or S0s, added to the scheme by Hubble's student Allan Sandage (e.g. Sandage 1975). S0s are disk galaxies without any spiral pattern. Both S0s and ellipticals are known to be poor in neutral atomic hydrogen (H I). The French astronomer Gérard de Vaucouleurs expanded the classification system and included the class Sd (de Vaucouleurs 1959). Another category of late-type disk galaxies added afterwards are the irregulars. These are chaotic systems in appearance with neither a bulge nor any well-defined spiral structure. They are rich in H I gas in general. The MW is a Sbc galaxy.

Barred spiral galaxies are characterized by the presence of an elongated or oval-shaped stellar structure in the central regions (see the image of NGC 1300 in Fig. 1.2), known as a bar. Bars were first noticed by Curtis (1918). The presence of a bar is a fundamental criterion that established two branches of disk galaxies in the Hubble Tuning Fork. When observed in the visible spectrum, roughly

T	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1
de Vaucouleurs class	cE	E	E ⁺	S0 ⁻	S0 ⁰	S0 ⁺

Table 1.1: Morphological classification of elliptical and lenticular galaxies using the system by de Vaucouleurs (1959).

T	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
de Vaucouleurs class	S0/a	Sa	Sab	Sb	Sbc	Sc	Scd	Sd	Sdm	Sm	Im

Table 1.2: As in Table 1.1, but for spiral and irregular galaxies.

two-thirds of the spiral galaxies in the local Universe (i.e. no further than approximately a billion light years from Earth) have a bar (e.g. de Vaucouleurs et al. 1991; Knapen et al. 2002). Bars in spiral galaxies stand out more clearly in the near-infrared wavelengths (e.g. Hackwell & Schweizer 1983), where the old stellar populations that probe the underlying mass distribution are better traced (e.g. Eskridge et al. 2000). The MW is known to have a bar (e.g. de Vaucouleurs 1964; Binney et al. 1991).

In the updated classification scheme by de Vaucouleurs, numerical values (Hubble stage T) were assigned to the galaxies (see Table 1.1 and Table 1.2)². Negative numbers covered early-type galaxies, namely ellipticals (subdivided in compact, normal and late-type ellipticals) and lenticulars (also partitioned into early-, intermediate- and late-type S0s). Positive values were assigned to spirals and irregulars.

Many disk galaxies show other stellar substructures like inner and/or outer rings, which generally contain gas (e.g. Buta & Crocker 1991). In intermediate morphological types, rings contain stars younger than those in the bar, and similar to those in the disk (e.g. Buta & Combes 1996). Also, galaxies can host nuclear rings (e.g. Morgan 1958) and nuclear bars (e.g. de Vaucouleurs 1975). Early-type disk galaxies can also present lenses (e.g. Kormendy 1981), characterized by a gradually decreasing surface brightness and a sharp edge.

1.1.2 Stellar bars and the evolution of galaxies

Bars are generally considered to be density enhancements resulting from rotating density waves in spiral galaxies that reshape the orbits of the inner stars. Early work by Ostriker & Peebles (1973) suggested that a stellar system would form a bar if the energy contained in the rotational motions exceeds $\sim 40\%$ of the energy contained in random motions.

The morphology and mass distribution of the galaxies that we observe today

²In this thesis we will often study separately S0s ($-3 \leq T < 0$), early-type spirals ($0 \leq T < 3$), intermediate-type spirals ($3 \leq T < 5$), late-type spirals ($5 \leq T \leq 7$) and irregular galaxies and Magellanics ($7 < T \leq 10$). Occasionally, we also study early- ($T < 5$) and late-type ($T \geq 5$) systems separately.

are the fossil records of a long multiphase transformation out of the virialized density fluctuations of cold dark matter (DM) (e.g. Kormendy & Kennicutt 2004). During its early life a galaxy evolution is dominated by rapid processes (i.e. taking place in a free-fall dynamical timescale) such as protogalactic collapse (Eggen et al. 1962), mergers with other galaxies (Toomre 1977a), or RAM pressure stripping exerted by the hot (X-ray emitting) gas present inside a cluster of galaxies (e.g. Grebel et al. 2003). A subsequent phase, that takes place at a much slower pace on assembled disks, is the *secular evolution* (Kormendy 1979). This steady evolution can have an external origin, like the accretion of intergalactic gas (e.g. Sancisi et al. 2008), or episodes of galaxy harassment in clusters (e.g. Moore et al. 1996). The latter is caused by fly-bys of nearby galaxies that disturb the progenitor's morphology (e.g., by forming bars, tails and warps) and induce star formation bursts, and also by the gravitational interactions with the global cluster potential (e.g. Moore et al. 1998).

The secular evolution of a disk galaxy can have an internal origin, a process in which stellar non-axisymmetries are the main engines causing a long-term rearrangement of material through the disk. This internal secular evolution is the main subject of this thesis. Stellar bars are known to play a role in the secular evolution of disk galaxies. They redistribute angular momentum (e.g. Weinberg 1985; Athanassoula & Misiriotis 2002), and the stellar material in the galaxies (e.g. Hohl 1971; Athanassoula & Misiriotis 2002; Minchev et al. 2011). Bars exert torques that drive gas towards the nuclear regions of galaxies (e.g. Shlosman et al. 1989; Athanassoula 1992a; Wada & Habe 1992). They are also believed to contribute to the formation of spiral density waves (Toomre 1969) and stellar rings (e.g. Buta 1986).

1.2 Cosmological framework

According to the *Big Bang*, which is the commonly accepted cosmological model, the Universe is estimated to be $\sim 13.8 \cdot 10^9$ years old and to have formed from a highly dense and hot singularity in the spacetime. Structure formation theories predict that about 10^{-35} seconds after the Big Bang the early Universe experienced an accelerated, exponential expansion, known as the cosmological inflation. The cosmological inflation amplified to macroscopic scales the primordial quantum density fluctuations, that is, short-lived appearances of energetic particles out of the vacuum allowed by the Heisenberg's uncertainty principle (Heisenberg 1930). This set up the build-up of the large-size structure and explains the homogeneity and isotropy of the cosmos that we observe today: the Universe looks the same in all directions and from any location (this is known as the *cosmological principle*).

After the inflation, the Universe continued growing over the ensuing billions of years at a slower pace and assembled structure in a hierarchical way: first, smaller structures like quasars and the first generation of stars formed from the light ele-

Figure 1.3: Representation of the evolution of the Universe over the last $\sim 13.8 \cdot 10^9$ years. Credit: NASA / WMAP Science Team.

ments created in the Big Bang nucleosynthesis (primordial hydrogen, lithium and helium); then, bigger volumes of matter collapsed to form metal-rich stars and galaxies; followed by groups and clusters of galaxies. Clusters clump in some regions of space to form filaments and superclusters, while creating voids in others.

In 1922, the Russian physicist and mathematician Alexander Friedmann applied the theory of general relativity (Einstein 1916) to obtain a set of equations that described the expanding Universe (Friedmann 1922). In 1927, the same result was independently reached by the Belgian astronomer Georges Lemaître (Lemaître 1927), who was the first person proposing a Universe arising from a *primeval atom*. Lemaître was a pioneer providing observational evidence for such expansion. Using observations of distant galaxies (further than 10 megaparsecs from the Earth), he demonstrated that the rate at which galaxies recede from the Earth (V) is linearly proportional to their distance (D): $v = H_0 D$, where H_0 is known as the *Hubble constant*. This relation is known as the *Hubble's Law* because it was published later in 1929, and set as a landmark with detriment to Lemaître, by Edwin Hubble after he independently reached an identical conclusion from the same measurements (Hubble 1929). The latest estimate of H_0 by the Planck Mission (Planck Collaboration et al. 2014) is ~ 68 km/s/Mpc. By studying distant type Ia supernovae (*standard candles*), it has been recently shown by

FIGURE 1
Velocity-Distance Relation among Extra-Galactic Nebulae.

Figure 1.4: The relation between the distance (in parsecs) and the radial velocity (in km/s, labeled in the wrong units in the figure) of galaxies presented by Hubble. Credit: Fig. 1 from Hubble (1929).

the Supernova Cosmology Project and High-Z Supernova Search Team that such expansion is actually accelerated (Schmidt et al. 1998; Perlmutter et al. 1999). Because of the Universe expansion and the *Doppler effect*, the wavelength of the electromagnetic radiation emitted by distant objects has increased when it reaches the Earth. This is called *cosmological redshift* (z).

The lambda cold dark matter (Λ CDM) model is the modern parametrization of the Big Bang theory under the assumption that the general relativity is the valid theory of gravity at a cosmological level. It postulates the existence of cold dark matter and dark energy. The former refers to hypothesized form of a slowly-moving (relative to the speed of light) particle that does not emit any electromagnetic radiation but interacts with the baryonic (or visible) matter through gravity and possibly the weak force. The dark energy is the *cosmological constant* (Λ), the energy density of the vacuum that triggers the aforementioned acceleration on the expansion of the Universe. The Λ CDM model also explains the cosmic abundances of hydrogen, helium and lithium, and the large-scale structure in the distribution of galaxies. Besides, it accounts for the existence of the cosmic microwave background (CMB) radiation, that is, the afterglow of the Big Bang (more specifically from the *recombination* epoch ~ 378000 years later, when electrons and protons became bound to form neutral hydrogen atoms) prognosticated by Ralph Alpher and Robert Herman in 1948 (Alpher & Herman 1948) and discovered 20 years later by Arno Penzias and Robert Wilson (Penzias & Wilson 1965).

Modern cosmological simulations allow to model *ab initio* the large scale distribution of the dark matter component in the Universe since the recombina-

tion epoch until the present day by using dissipationless N -body codes³. One of the largest and ground-breaking examples (see the upper panel of Fig. 1.5) is the *Millennium Run* (Lemson & Virgo Consortium 2006), carried out using a modified version of the code GADGET-2 (Springel 2005) and using 10^{10} particles inside a cubic region of size $500 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$ and resolution $5 h^{-1}\text{kpc}$, where $h = \left(\frac{H_0}{100\text{km s}^{-1}\text{Mpc}^{-1}}\right)$. To date, the *Bolshoi* (Klypin et al. 2011) and *MultiDark* (Prada et al. 2012) simulations are the most powerful cosmological runs of the large-scale structure of the Universe, reaching almost an order of magnitude better resolution.

In a ΛCDM cosmological framework, dark matter halos grow by means of gravitational instabilities, and they acquire angular momentum from cosmological torques. Disk galaxies are thought to form when the gas within those halos cools down and condenses (White & Rees 1978; Fall & Efstathiou 1980). The formation of galaxies in cosmological simulations can be tracked by treating the baryons with hydrodynamic codes (e.g. Katz et al. 1996; Springel & Hernquist 2003) or semi-analytic methods (e.g. Kauffmann et al. 1999; Springel et al. 2001), in which the halo gas accretion, the star formation (SF) efficiency and feedback (i.e. SF suppression) due to supernovae (SN), active galactic nuclei (AGN) or even the CMB (e.g. Verbeke et al. 2015) need to be fine-tuned. The aforementioned high-resolution N -body simulations have shown that halos can harbor subhalos orbiting within the main halo potential that might eventually give birth to satellite galaxies.

The earliest notion of galaxy formation in a cosmological context was presented in the work by Eggen et al. (1962), who hypothesized that spheroidal galaxies form from an early collapse of a non-rotating star-forming cloud of gas, while disk galaxies originate from clouds with large angular momentum and inefficient star formation. Major morphological features are believed to be determined by the spin of the host dark matter halo and the accretion history of the galaxy (e.g. Mo et al. 1998). In this scenario, disk galaxies form in halos with large spins and quiescent assembly histories (e.g. Navarro & Steinmetz 1997; Steinmetz & Navarro 1999), whereas spheroids result from merger events (e.g. Toomre 1977a; Cole et al. 2000). Recent models of galaxy formation in a cosmological framework by Sales et al. (2012), using DM halo masses similar to that of the MW, showed that the final morphology of a galaxy is dependent on the combined effect of hot and cold gas accretion and the alignment of the spin of the angular momentum of the different galaxy components. However, the halo spin and the merger history did not play a major role in the disk/bulge assembly in these simulations. Specifically, substantial misalignments of the accreted gas with respect to that of the assembled baryons favored the formation of spheroids. On the contrary, when the angular momentum spin of the early-accreted material was coincident with the newly accreted gas, pure discs were formed. Also, the disks in these simulations

³In astronomy, an N -body code simulates a dynamical system in which the equations of motion of N particles (e.g. stars) governed by their mutual gravitational forces are integrated numerically. They can be used to study galaxy dynamics or the large-scale formation of galaxy filaments and dark matter halos.

formed preferentially from a corona of hot gas, whereas slowly rotating spheroids typically formed from filamentary accretion of cold gas.

1.2.1 The stellar-to-halo mass ratio

In the Λ CDM scenario fundamental galaxy parameters, such as the total stellar mass, are expected to be linked to properties of the host halo masses. For subhalos, that link should not be very strong, as the stellar mass of the satellite galaxy would be dependent on the halo mass before the accretion took place at high redshift, i.e. prior to any halo tidal stripping episode.

Recent statistical methods based on cosmological simulations to address the halo-galaxy interdependence are the *halo occupation distribution* (HOD; e.g. Peacock & Smith 2000; Zheng et al. 2007; Leauthaud et al. 2012) and the *conditional luminosity function* (CLF; e.g. van den Bosch et al. 2003; Yang et al. 2003, 2012). HOD and CLF use large galaxy surveys to calculate the probability distribution of a given halo to host certain number of galaxies of particular properties (e.g. total luminosity). Galaxy clustering statistics are the main constraint on these methods (this makes them being typically used at low redshifts). A more suitable method to estimate the stellar-to-halo mass ratio at all redshifts is the *abundance matching* (e.g. Vale & Ostriker 2004, 2006; Behroozi et al. 2010; Guo et al. 2010; Moster et al. 2010). This method links the abundances of halos (and subhalos) to those of galaxies under the assumption of a monotonic relation between the dark matter and the stellar mass. It uses constraints based on the luminosity function, that is, the space density of galaxies per luminosity interval, or also by clustering (e.g. Wang & Jing 2010). The dark matter content of a galaxy can also be measured directly based on lensing analysis (e.g. Mandelbaum et al. 2006; Gavazzi et al. 2007), that is, by the bending of the path of light passing near a massive object like a galaxy (e.g. Einstein 1916; Newton 1931), predicted by the English natural philosopher Isaac Newton in 1704 in his book *Opticks*. The halo-to-stellar mass ratio can also be measured from the dynamics of satellite galaxies (e.g. Klypin et al. 2011). Also, coupling between the stellar and the dynamical mass has been investigated by finding galaxy groups in large galaxy surveys, for instance using the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS; Gunn et al. 2006) photometry (Yang et al. 2007, 2009), SDSS spectroscopy (Hansen et al. 2009), or X-ray cluster catalogs and the Two Micron All Sky Survey (2MASS)⁴ *K*-band data (Lin & Mohr 2004).

From the above techniques, some of the resulting trends for the halo-to-stellar mass ratio as a function of halo mass (SHM function hereafter) are shown in the lower panel of Fig. 1.5, taken from Behroozi et al. (2010). In general, the SHM function has a maximum near $10^{12} M_{\odot}$, where the star formation efficiency is highest, drops sharply towards lower-mass halos, and less steeply towards larger

⁴2MASS is a joint project of the University of Massachusetts and the Infrared Processing and Analysis Center/California Institute of Technology, funded by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration and the National Science Foundation.

Figure 1.5: *Upper panel:* Dark matter distribution in the Universe at the present time (left) as seen in the Millennium simulation (Lemson & Virgo Consortium 2006), and zoom in on a cluster of galaxies (resolution increasing towards the right in steps of two). Credit: Springel (2005). *Lower panel:* Best-fit model of the stellar-to-halo mass ratio at $z=0.1$ as a function of the halo mass from Behroozi et al. (2010) (black solid line). The dark gray shaded area corresponds to the statistical and sample variance errors, while the light gray shading indicates systematic errors. The red line indicates the results averaged over stellar mass instead of halo mass. The rest of the lines correspond to the other published results for the halo-to-stellar mass ratio (see the text and the legend), applying abundance matching (AM), also with clustering constraints (AM+CC), halo occupation distribution modeling (HOD), weak (WL) and strong lensing (SL), satellite dynamics (SD) and direct measurements from clusters (CL). These results were *a posteriori* adjusted to a common Chabrier (2003) initial mass function (IMF; that describes the number of stars within a mass range and volume) for the sake of comparison. Credit: Fig. 11 from Behroozi et al. (2010).

masses. As discussed in Moster et al. (2010), this trend results from the combined effect of supernova feedback, which is more efficient at reheating and dislodging the gas in low-mass halos, and AGN feedback, which is more effective in high mass halos (e.g. Shankar et al. 2006; Croton et al. 2006; Bower et al. 2006; Somerville et al. 2008).

1.2.2 Drawbacks of Λ CDM

One of the biggest flaws of the Λ CDM numerical simulations is the overproduction of bulges, and their excessive concentrations (e.g. Steinmetz & Navarro 1999; Navarro & Steinmetz 2000). In part, this is a consequence of the so-called overcooling problem, which is the rapid condensation of baryons in the centers of halos. However, from the observations of local galaxies it is known that many disk galaxies are practically bulge-less (e.g. Salo et al. 2015). This challenges the picture of galaxy formation in the hierarchical Λ CDM model, unless star formation is suppressed via strong feedback (e.g. Brook et al. 2012).

By improving the treatment of the physics of the baryons (SF and AGN feedback), more realistic galaxies have been produced in cosmological simulations in the past years. State-of-the-art hydrodynamical simulations by the Virgo Consortium's EAGLE project (Schaye et al. 2015) are much closer to observed properties and frequencies of galaxies. Bulge-less dwarf disk galaxies have been obtained in the simulations by Governato et al. (2010) and Teyssier et al. (2013); as well as low mass disk-like bulges (Okamoto 2013). Recently, Christensen et al. (2014) simulated galaxies whose bulges matched observed scaling relations. Nevertheless, as discussed in Brooks & Christensen (2016), no realistic bulge has been produced in a cosmological simulation in combination with a realistic star formation history. In addition, depending on the strength of SN feedback, galaxies can be blown apart (Agertz et al. 2013), the resulting disks can become too thick (Roškar et al. 2014) or experience too much outer growth (Aumer et al. 2014).

In addition, non-hierarchical trends in the Universe have been detected, what is not predicted in Λ CDM. It has been observed that massive galaxies had an early star formation (early assembly) and ceased star formation at high z , whereas fainter galaxies continued an active star formation to later epochs (known as *downsizing*; Cowie et al. 1996). Another important failure of the Λ CDM is the prediction of galaxies at $z \approx 0$ whose dark matter density profiles are cuspy, that is, very centrally concentrated. However, observations of the dynamics of nearby galaxies favor cored profiles (e.g. de Blok et al. 2008). An additional issue is the creation of excessively small galaxies compared to real ones (e.g. Navarro & Steinmetz 2000), due to acquisition of angular momentum by dark matter halos in detriment to the baryonic component. Furthermore, Λ CDM predicts an amount of dwarf galaxies (e.g. ~ 500 MW satellites) which is about an order of magnitude higher than observed (e.g. Moore et al. 1999; Klypin et al. 1999; Diemand et al. 2008). Besides, low-mass MW satellites are less DM dominated than estimated from halo

abundance matching (Boylan-Kolchin et al. 2011).

There are alternatives to the Λ CDM model, not contemplated in this thesis, that do not invoke dark matter. This is the case of the modified Newtonian dynamics (MOND; Milgrom 1983), a successful theory at explaining the dynamics of galaxies and systems of galaxies, that to date lacks a robust cosmological model constructed around it.

MW sized dark matter halos in Λ CDM cosmological simulations can extend further than $\sim 200 - 250$ kpc (e.g. Macciò et al. 2010), while galaxies of the size of the MW have optical radii of $\sim 20 - 30$ kpc (e.g. van Dokkum et al. 2013). Because of the dynamical friction between DM halos, mergers are fairly common in Λ CDM cosmological simulations, inducing the formation of spheroids. Interestingly, in a MONDian cosmology, the lack of halos would reduce substantially the rate of mergers (Tiret & Combes 2008). For example, at a distance of ~ 100 kpc, two galaxies of similar masses would not merge in a Hubble-Lemaître time (Combes 2016). This implies that in MOND the frequency of merger-built bulges is substantially reduced, in agreement with observations showing a large frequency of bulge-less galaxies (e.g. Weinzirl et al. 2009).

1.3 Insights into galactic disks

1.3.1 Light distribution of disk galaxies

Since the early observational work by Freeman (1970), it has become evident that the azimuthally averaged surface brightness profiles of disk galaxies is characterized by an exponential radial decay (see Fig. 1.6). Exponential luminosity profiles (Σ) are described as follows:

$$\Sigma(r) = \Sigma_0 \cdot e^{-r/h_R}, \quad (1.1)$$

or expressed in magnitudes:

$$\mu(r) = \mu_0 + 1.086 \cdot r/h_R, \quad (1.2)$$

where μ_0 and Σ_0 correspond the central surface brightness and h_R is the scalelength of the exponential disk, estimated by obtaining the best fit to the luminosity profile of a galaxy (e.g. van der Kruit 1987). There is a large dispersion of h_R values between galaxies (e.g. Fathi et al. 2010). Because often disk galaxies have central bulges, these can also be fitted (e.g. de Jong & van der Kruit 1994), allowing to obtain bulge/disk decompositions. The light distribution of a galaxy can also be decomposed in two dimensions with multiple structure components (e.g. Laurikainen et al. 2005; Gadotti 2009; Weinzirl et al. 2009; Salo et al. 2015), and the modeling of bars and lens-like structures is fundamental to recover trustworthy structural parameters of bulges and disks (e.g. Laurikainen et al. 2005, 2010, 2014).

Figure 1.6: The radial luminosity distribution of NGC 4459 and M 83. Credit: Fig. 1 from Freeman (1970).

Surveys in optical and near-IR wavelengths allowed to reach larger depths and revealed that many galaxies present breaks in the outer parts of the luminosity profiles. For instance, Erwin et al. (2005) found that the luminosity profiles of many early-type galaxies become shallower after a certain radius ($\sim 3 - 5 \cdot h_R$), that they termed *anti-truncations*. Studies of the surface brightness profiles of ~ 90 face-on late-type galaxies by Pohlen & Trujillo (2006) revealed that only $\sim 10\%$ of the galaxies had purely exponential profiles, while 60% presented a downbending sector after a break, and the remaining 30% showed upbending sections. Downbending breaks, or *truncations*, were already discussed in the pioneering work by Freeman (1970). Also, van der Kruit (1979) showed a sharp drop in the outer parts of the luminosity profiles of edge-on galaxies. Later studies of face-on galaxies at different redshifts ($z < 1$) showed that many galaxies present smooth truncated double-exponential profiles (e.g. Naeslund & Joersaeter 1997; Pohlen et al. 2002; de Grijs et al. 2001; Pérez 2004). Erwin et al. (2008) put the pieces together and established a new taxonomy for the luminosity profiles of disk galaxies: Type I profiles present a continuous exponential slope, while Types II and III turn steeper or shallower after the break, respectively.

Muñoz-Mateos et al. (2013) associated the loci of breaks to the presence of bars and the dynamical coupling between the bar and the spiral pattern. Type II breaks were linked to morphological features such as rings, lenses, and spirals in the study by Laine et al. (2014), based on $3.6 \mu\text{m}$ photometry. Besides, Laine

et al. (2014) estimated the tidal interaction strength of galaxies by computing the Dahari parameter (Dahari 1984), which is determined based on the number and relative mass of companion galaxies and their deprojected distance (e.g. Verley et al. 2007). Laine et al. (2014) showed that galaxies with a higher tidal interaction strength present more often Type III profiles, implying that nearby galaxy encounters might be one of the reasons for this type of truncations. This was also suggested by simulations and observations of M 51-type interacting pairs (Laurikainen & Salo 2000; Salo & Laurikainen 2000).

Despite the almost ubiquitous exponential backbone of observed disk galaxies, their formation process remains unclear (e.g. Fall & Efstathiou 1980; Lin & Pringle 1987; Pfenniger & Friedli 1991). In fact, producing exponential stellar disks in cosmological simulations became a difficult challenge (e.g. van den Bosch 2001). However, models by Abadi et al. (2003) or Robertson et al. (2004) were successful at creating them. More recently, exponential or quasi-exponential stellar disks were obtained in the simulations in a Λ CDM context by Dutton (2009) of the accretion, cooling and ejection of baryonic mass inside DM halos.

1.3.2 Dynamics of disk galaxies

Unlike elliptical galaxies or globular clusters, which are supported by random motions and evolve by outward energy transport (e.g. Lynden-Bell & Wood 1968; Binney & Tremaine 1987), galactic disks are supported by rotation, and their evolution is driven by angular momentum transport (e.g. Lynden-Bell & Kalnajs 1972; Lynden-Bell & Pringle 1974).

The mass distribution of a galaxy can be traced from its rotation curve. The rotation curve of a galaxy is defined as the change in the orbital circular velocity of stars or gas clouds as a function of galactocentric radius (see Fig. 1.7). The rotation curve of a galaxy having an exponential disk would in principle rise up to a maximum, reached in the central parts of the galaxy ($\sim 2.2h_R$), and then decrease asymptotically with the square root of the radius (e.g. Freeman 1970). This Keplerian fall-off characterizes the dynamics of the Solar System (Newton 1687). Nevertheless, Bosma (1978, 1981) and Rubin et al. (1980) discovered that the rotation of disk galaxies, traced from the kinematics of neutral hydrogen, does not always decline at large radii. This was interpreted as clear evidence for the existence of dark matter. The discovery of missing matter in the Coma cluster by the Swiss astrophysicist Fritz Zwicky (Zwicky 1933) also supported the existence of non-baryonic mass. The Australian astronomer Ken Freeman had speculated that some disk galaxies must have unobserved mass (of the same order as the observed) when he analyzed the rotation curve of NGC 300 (Freeman 1970). The existence of dark matter had been discussed by the Dutch astronomers Jacobus Kapteyn and Jan Oort. Kapteyn (1922) found that the stellar populations and interstellar gas were sufficient to account for the vertical oscillations of stars around the MW plane in the solar vicinity. On the contrary, Oort (1932) claimed

(wrongly) that in the solar neighborhood the amount of invisible matter should be roughly equal to that of visible matter.

Figure 1.7: Rotation curves of 7 spiral galaxies as a function of galactocentric radius. Credit: Fig. 3 from Rubin et al. (1978).

Decomposition of rotation curves into contributions from stars, gas and dark matter as a function of radius has been historically used to separate dark matter and baryons in galaxies (e.g. Bosma 1978; Carignan & Freeman 1985; van Albada et al. 1985) and remains a controversial issue. The relationship between the fundamental optical properties of the galaxies and the shapes of their rotation curves has been debated (e.g. Rubin et al. 1985; Persic & Salucci 1991). From the study of the rotation curves using more than a thousand spiral galaxies, Persic et al. (1996) concluded that the shape and amplitude of a rotation curve can be described by the total luminosity of a galaxy. Rubin et al. (1980) had already claimed the existence of the so-called universal rotation curve (URC). However, counterexamples to the URC were a posteriori found by Verheijen (1997).

In the *maximum-disk* hypothesis (van Albada & Sancisi 1986), the stellar contribution of the disk to the circular velocity (V_{disk}) accounts for the observed rotation curve (V_{total}) to a great extent. The criterion by Sackett (1997) establishes that a disk is maximal if $V_{\text{disk}}/V_{\text{total}}(2.2h_{\text{R}}) > 0.85$. Otherwise, they are called submaximal. Lately, Martinsson et al. (2013) tested the maximum-disk hypothesis by decomposing rotation curves of 30 spiral galaxies from the DiskMass Survey (Bershady et al. 2010). They found that all galaxies in their sample were submaximal, consistent with the results in Bershady et al. (2011). Specifically, they measured the baryonic (V_{baryons}) to total rotational velocities at $2.2h_{\text{R}}$ and obtained a mean $V_{\text{baryons}}/V_{\text{total}}(2.2h_{\text{R}}) = 0.57 \pm 0.07$. Zavala et al. (2003) found that the ratio of disk

maximum velocity to total maximum velocity depends mainly on the central disk surface brightness. Martinsson et al. (2013) also showed that $V_{\text{baryons}}/V_{\text{total}}(2.2h_{\text{R}})$ correlates with the central surface brightness of the disk. Based on the analysis of a compilation of rotation curves, Courteau & Dutton (2015) recently confirmed that low-mass galaxies tend to be more dark matter dominated within the optical disk than their brighter counterparts.

1.3.3 Galactic disks at high redshift

Using images of galaxies at high redshift from the *Hubble Space Telescope* (HST) Ultra Deep Field (UDF; Beckwith et al. 2006), Elmegreen & Elmegreen (2005) and Elmegreen et al. (2007b) showed that an important fraction of their baryonic mass is comprised in blue star-forming clumps. Simulations by Ceverino et al. (2012) showed that the nature of these clumps is very turbulent. Elmegreen et al. (2005) also found that those clumps appear distributed in an exponential profile. Models by Bournaud et al. (2007) suggested that these clumps, formed from gas via gravitational instabilities, interacted and exchanged angular momentum, and eventually dissolved into the exponential disks observed in the local Universe.

In the models by Bournaud et al. (2007) and Elmegreen et al. (2008), clumpy galaxies have typical values of V/σ below 0.5, meaning that they are pressure supported systems (e.g. Kormendy & Illingworth 1982). However, dynamically speaking, galaxies of all types have been observed at high redshifts, ranging from rotation-supported to dispersion-dominated systems to very chaotic systems (e.g. Yang et al. 2008; Genzel et al. 2008; Buitrago et al. 2014). In particular, evidence for ordered circular orbital motions in luminous star-forming galaxies at $z \sim 1.3$ was provided by Wisnioski et al. (2011). The gravitational collapse of a $10^9 M_{\odot}$ giant clump at $z \sim 2$ was observed by Zanella et al. (2015): the clump was identifiable in the O II, O III and H β emission without presenting any stellar component.

It is possible that thick disk in galaxies formed at high redshift from the highly turbulent interstellar medium, in a period of chaotic hierarchical clustering with frequent gas-rich mergers, as shown by the cosmological simulations by Brook et al. (2004, 2005). Also, Bournaud et al. (2009) proposed that thick disks arose at high z from gravitational instabilities in clumpy disks, while the thin disk formed later via gas accretion, with a lower velocity dispersion. Alternatively, thick disks could have had an external origin and formed through satellite accretion (e.g. Abadi et al. 2003). Likewise, they could have formed from dynamical heating caused by satellite galaxies (e.g. Quinn et al. 1993). In a different model, thick disks are proposed to form secularly through vertical heating and radial migration of stars (e.g. Villumsen 1985; Schönrich & Binney 2009). Nevertheless, this is not supported by a number of studies showing that radial migration does not thicken the disk (Minchev et al. 2012; Vera-Ciro et al. 2014; Martig et al. 2014; Grand et al. 2016). Recent work by Comerón et al. (2014a) favors the early-formation of the thick disks, which is in a qualitative agreement with the picture for the MW

(see Gonzalez & Gadotti 2016).

Galaxies at $z \sim 2$ tend to have turbulent disks (Newman et al. 2013). At that redshift, red, massive and very compact galaxies have been observed (e.g. Franx et al. 2003; Daddi et al. 2005). Extremely compact galaxies (based on a Sérsic fit of their luminosity profile; Sérsic 1963) were also found by Trujillo et al. (2006a) at $z \sim 1.4$. Trujillo et al. (2006b) studied the luminosity-size and stellar mass-size relation of massive galaxies during the last ~ 11 Gyr. For the galaxies with low light concentration (like the MW), their sizes were ~ 3 times smaller at $z \sim 2.5$ than today, given a certain luminosity interval. For a fixed stellar mass galaxy sizes evolved less (factor ~ 2) in that period. Because the mass-to-light ratios were lower at high- z , the evolution of the luminosity-size and the stellar mass-size relations in galaxies are different (e.g. Trujillo et al. 2004). Trujillo et al. (2007) studied the evolution of very massive galaxies since $z \approx 2$, finding that at that epoch galaxies were much smaller than present day massive systems regardless of their compactness. They also realized that the concentrated galaxies that they find at $z = 1.5 - 2$ are not observed in the local Universe, meaning that those systems probably merged to form the present-day massive galaxies. Other studies have shown a lack of strong evolution in the stellar mass-size relation in disk galaxies since $z \sim 1$ (e.g. Lilly et al. 1998; Simard et al. 1999; Barden et al. 2005). Altogether, these results are consistent with an *inside-out growth* of the massive disk galaxies, that is, they increase in size as they grow more massive.

Based on u - and g -band imaging from SDSS, 3D-HST (Brammer et al. 2012) and CANDELS (Koekemoer et al. 2011), van Dokkum et al. (2013) studied the median stellar mass density profiles of the MW-ancestors at different redshifts. At a given z , these progenitors were chosen based on the cumulative co-moving number density of galaxies, calibrated at $z = 0$, where $M_*(MW) \approx 5 \cdot 10^{10} M_\odot$. They found that $\sim 90\%$ of the stellar mass of MW-type galaxies was built between $z = 2.5$ and $z = 1$. They reported a concurrent growth of stellar mass at all radii, discarding *inside-out* or *outside-in* growth scenarios for the MW progenitors, that could be explained via star formation without invoking mergers. They showed that in the last 8 Gyr the disk continued the buildup, but the central parts grew more slowly. According to van Dokkum et al. (2010), in systems with present-day stellar masses $M_* \approx 3 \cdot 10^{11} M_\odot$, the central regions formed earlier than $z = 2$, followed by an inside-out growth and an overall factor ~ 3 increase in the total stellar mass between $z = 3$ and $z = 0$. The mass assembly of these galaxies could not be explained only by the star formation activity. Sachdeva et al. (2015) demonstrated that disk galaxies grew peripherally since $z \sim 1$, based on measurements of the Petrosian radius (Petrosian 1976), which is obtained from the ratio of the surface brightness at a given galactocentric radius divided by that averaged inside that radius.

1.3.4 Coupling between baryonic and dark matter

The most fundamental scaling relation in disk galaxies is the relationship between the width of the H I 21 cm line (i.e. the galaxy angular velocity) and the total optical luminosity (see the left panel in Fig. 1.8), published by R. Brent Tully and J. Richard Fisher in 1977 (Tully & Fisher 1977) and known as the *Tully-Fisher (TF) relation*. This calibration is a very important tool to estimate galactic distances, becoming a very important step in the *cosmic distance ladder*, because the luminosity of a galaxy (L) is proportional to its distance (D) and apparent brightness (B): $L = 4\pi D^2 B$.

The TF relation was extended to near-IR wavelengths, less affected by extinction, in subsequent work (e.g. Peletier & Willner 1993; Tully et al. 1996). McGaugh et al. (2000) found a break in the Tully-Fisher relation for velocities lower than 90 km/s. They found an even tighter linear relationship when the galaxy rotation velocity mass was studied as a function of the total baryonic mass, so-called *baryonic Tully-Fisher relation*. Verheijen (2001) studied the TF relation for a sample of spiral galaxies in the nearby Ursa Major Cluster with available H I velocity fields and photometry at optical and near-infrared wavelengths. Three kinematic measurements were obtained, namely the corrected H I line widths, the maximum of the H I rotation curves, and the amplitudes of the flat part of the rotation curve (V_{flat}). The latter measurement reduced significantly the scatter in the correlation between the dark matter halo mass and the rotation velocity. It was found that the total baryonic mass is proportional to V_{flat}^4 . The slope of the baryonic TF relation reported by McGaugh et al. (2000) was also 4. Later, Zaritsky et al. (2014) reassessed the baryonic TF relation using 3.6 μm photometry from the Spitzer Survey of Stellar Structure in Galaxies (S⁴G; Sheth et al. 2010; Muñoz-Mateos et al. 2013), and H I line widths from the Cosmic Flows project (Courtois et al. 2009, 2011), that comprises observations done at Green Bank in the USA and at Parkes in Australia. They measured a baryonic TF slope of 3.5 ± 0.2 .

The TF relation is an elementary observational constraint for simulation models in a cosmological framework to be tested against (e.g. Governato et al. 2007). Contrary to Newtonian physics, that establish that the force exerted by one body into another at a distance r is proportional to $1/r^2$, MOND hypothesizes that in the weak field regime ($a \ll a_0 = 2 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m/s}^2$) accelerations behave as $a^2/a_0 = GM/r^2$. In other words, accelerations are proportional to $1/r$. This implies that $v^4 = GMa_0$, meaning that the slope of the Tully-Fisher relation in a MONDian framework should be exactly 4 (consistent with the calibration by e.g. McGaugh et al. 2000; Verheijen 2001). From theoretical calculations, White (1997) determined that the slope of the Tully-Fisher relation in a ΛCDM cosmology is ~ 3 . Based on halo abundance matching techniques, Desmond (2012) argued that such a slope, in the context of ΛCDM , should be larger, in agreement with the observations locating it in the range of 3.5 – 4 (e.g. Torres-Flores et al. 2011).

Figure 1.8: *Left panel:* The correlation between the H I profile width and the galaxy absolute magnitude for a sample of nearby galaxies, presented by R. Brent Tully and J. Richard Fisher. Credit: Fig. 1 from Tully & Fisher (1977). *Right panel:* The dependence of the central velocity gradient on the central surface brightness in disk galaxies. The shaded area corresponds to a model with no dark matter in the central regions (within roughly one half of the disk scalelength). Credit: Fig. 1 from Lelli (2014).

The intimate coupling between the baryonic and dynamical mass in rotation supported systems (S0s, spirals and irregulars) has become established in the past years, based on the analysis of rotation curves and luminosity profiles (e.g. Kent 1987; Casertano & van Gorkom 1991). Studies of the inner parts of spiral galaxies led Sancisi (2004) to conclude that for any feature in the galaxy surface brightness profile there is a corresponding feature in the rotation curve, and vice versa. Along the same line, Swaters et al. (2012) found that rotation curves can be fitted by scaling-up the co-added contribution of the stellar and gaseous (H I) components. Based on a compilation of high-quality H I rotation curves, Lelli et al. (2013) recently presented a new scaling relation for disk galaxies: they found a linear correlation between the inner slope of the rotation curve (inner shape of the potential well) and the galaxy central surface brightness. The correlation holds for high- and low-surface brightness systems, which are typically characterized by steeply- and slowly-rising rotation curves, respectively (Tully & Verheijen 1997; Verheijen 1997). In follow-up work by Lelli (2014), this scaling relation is found to be consistent with a model for spirals and irregulars with no dark matter within the inner regions (radius $r < 0.5h_R$). Previous work by Swaters et al. (2009) had already suggested that the baryonic mass dominates the gravitational potential in the central regions, even among low surface brightness dwarf galaxies. Recent work by Lelli et al. (2016) reassessed the dependence between the central surface density of stars and the central dynamical mass. The authors found that high-

surface brightness galaxies are completely baryon dominated in the inner parts, while among low-surface brightness the contribution of dark matter gradually increases but remains tightly coupled to the stellar one.

The coupling between dark and baryonic matter manifests also in pressure supported systems (e.g. ellipticals and dwarf spheroidals). Faber & Jackson (1976) found a linear dependence of the mean velocity dispersion (σ) of lenticulars and ellipticals (ETGs) on the total luminosity of the system. This is known as the *Faber-Jackson* relation. Also, the central stellar velocity dispersion (proxy of the inner gravitational potential) has been observed to scale with the circular velocity at large radius (e.g. Whitmore et al. 1979; Ferrarese 2002; Ho 2007). This was recently reassessed using a sample of 16 nearby ETGs from the ATLAS^{3D} sample (Cappellari et al. 2011) by Serra et al. (2016), who found an even tighter correlation between the H I circular velocity at $6h_R$ and σ measured within one effective radius (enclosing half the light of the galaxy).

1.3.5 Galactic resonances

Prior to and after the advent of N -body simulations, studies of particle motions on (quasi-)steady-state potentials set up the basis of orbital structure analysis. Simulation models of the gas flowing in a rigidly-rotating bar potential were found to be crucial for understanding the dynamics in barred galaxies and the formation of stellar and gaseous substructures in the resonances of the bar (e.g. Sanders & Huntley 1976; Sanders & Tubbs 1980; Athanassoula 1992a).

In an epicyclic approximation, the angular speed (Ω), the radial epicyclic frequency (κ) and the pattern speed of the bar (Ω_b) define the resonances of a rotating barred disk (e.g. Sellwood & Wilkinson 1993). Ω_b is the rotation speed of the bar, and κ quantifies the frequency of radial motions, defined as

$$\kappa^2 = \frac{2\Omega}{R} \frac{d}{dR}(R^2\Omega), \quad (1.3)$$

where R is the radial coordinate. The main resonances are the inner Lindblad resonance (ILR), where $\Omega_b = \Omega - \kappa/2$, the outer Lindblad resonance (OLR), where $\Omega_b = \Omega + \kappa/2$, and the corotation resonance (CR), where $\Omega = \Omega_b$. Other important resonances are the 1/4 ultraharmonic resonance (UHR), where $\Omega_b = \Omega - \kappa/4$, and the outer 4/1 resonance (O4R), where $\Omega_b = \Omega + \kappa/4$. Depending on Ω_b , the ILRs may or may not exist. The bar always lies somewhat before corotation (Contopoulos 1980). The ILRs, if any, are located well inside the bar, while the OLR appears typically at a radius of twice the size of the bar (e.g. Athanassoula 2013). The resonances are the sites of the formation of the resonance rings (see Sect. 1.5.2).

To better illustrate the location of resonances, in Fig. 1.9 we show the result of a simple numerical model of the behavior of gas and stars in a barred galaxy, where a spiral pattern formed. More specifically, we calculated the response of the

Figure 1.9: *Left panel:* Snapshot of the gas response simulation to a rigidly rotating bar potential (Toomre disk + weak bar perturbation, following Wada 1994) at the end of one orbital period. The inner Lindblad resonance, corotation and the outer Lindblad resonance are over-plotted in blue, red and green, respectively. *Right panel:* The angular speed (Ω , in red), $\Omega - \kappa/2$ (blue) and $\Omega + \kappa/2$ (green), as a function of galactocentric radius (red). Resonance locations are highlighted with a vertical line. The horizontal line corresponds to the pattern speed of the bar (Ω_b).

non-self-gravitating particles in a rigidly rotating potential with a weak bar-like distortion using 10^5 particles, following the mathematical recipes in Wada (1994). On the right panel we show the rotation speed as a function of galactocentric radius, and also the $\Omega - \kappa/2$ and $\Omega + \kappa/2$ curves, highlighting the position of the resonances.

1.4 Insights into galactic bars

With the advent of the N -body simulations in the 1960s to approach the theory of stellar dynamics (von Hoerner 1960; Aarseth 1963), a new window to study the structure of galaxies on theoretical grounds was opened. To date, much light has been shed on the formation and evolution of stellar bars in particular based on N -body codes. In this section we present some of the most relevant historical results on the formation and evolution of disks, with a more thorough discussion on stellar bars, obtained with the aid of N -body codes. We also provide a brief summary of the observational and analytical work supporting some of these theoretical findings.

1.4.1 Formation and frequency of bars

Early N-body simulations showed spontaneous formation of bars in massive and cold galactic disks (e.g. Miller et al. 1970; Hohl 1971; Toomre 1977b; Efstathiou et al. 1982; Sellwood 1980, 1981; Toomre 1981; Athanassoula 1984; Athanassoula & Sellwood 1986; Sellwood & Wilkinson 1993), known as *bar instability* (see Fig. 1.10). This instability is believed to be the mechanism for the formation of the bar of the MW at $z \approx 1$ from a cold massive precursor (e.g. Shen & Li 2016).

Using a few hundreds of particles, Ostriker & Peebles (1973) showed that spherical halos can stabilize disks against bar formation. To the present day, the role of halos inhibiting the bar instability has been confirmed in several other simulations (e.g. Hohl 1976; Mihos et al. 1997). Stellar disks are unstable under MONDian physics (Brada & Milgrom 1999), given the lack of DM halos.

The stability of a fluid (e.g. collisional gas) disk was studied in the pioneering work by Safronov (1960). Toomre (1964) derived a model for the stability of stellar discs and defined the nowadays so-called *Toomre parameter*:

$$Q = \frac{\sigma_R \kappa}{3.36 G \Sigma}, \quad (1.4)$$

where σ_R refers to the radial velocity dispersion, κ is the local epicyclic frequency, G is the Newton's gravitational constant and Σ is the disk surface density. Toomre (1964) set the axisymmetric stability criterion of an infinitesimally thin rotating stellar disk against collapse as $Q > 1$. Analytical work by Toomre (1981) also showed the effect of massive halos (relative to the stellar disk) slowing down the bar growth, which was also confirmed by Athanassoula & Sellwood (1986) using 2D simulations. Moreover, Athanassoula & Sellwood (1986) showed that the growth rate of the bar instability is slower in hotter disks, that is, the bar instability can be suppressed by increasing the velocity dispersions. Larger velocity dispersions delayed the formation of bars in the more sophisticated simulations by Athanassoula (2003). Low surface brightness discs are believed to be stable against bar formation because of their low self-gravity and typically large halo-to-stellar mass ratio, according to the simulations with an inert, rigid halo by Mayer & Wadsley (2004). In the simulations by Athanassoula (2002) and Villa-Vargas et al. (2009) bars take longer to form in systems with massive live halos (i.e. self-consistently treated halos that may absorb angular momentum), due to their substantial contribution to the total gravitational force, but in the long term they produce stronger bars (see discussion in Sect. 1.4.2). Athanassoula (2002) challenged the classic view of dark matter halos inhibiting bar formation by studying the evolution of an initially symmetric disk in the presence of halos of equal masses, with and without a capacity to absorb angular momentum, finding that the long-term halo stabilizing effect happens only with unrealistic rigid halos (only a weak oval is formed).

Figure 1.10: Non-axisymmetric evolution of a disk of 100000 stars. Time is given in units of the rotational period of the cold balanced disk. Credit: Fig. 1 from Hohl (1971).

Nonetheless, the formation of bars via bar-instability, once the disk has grown axisymmetrically and fully assembled, does not look convincing. In fact, as reviewed in Sect. 1.3.3, galaxies at high redshift are known to be clumpy, thick and rich in gas, and present high velocity dispersions and star formation rates (e.g. Genzel et al. 2006; Bournaud et al. 2007; Dekel et al. 2009; Förster Schreiber et al. 2011; Newman et al. 2013). This is quite far from the initial conditions employed in the most common simulation models. This was discussed by Sellwood (2000) and Kormendy (2013), who claimed that the substantial central mass concentrations observed in many present-day galaxies could stabilize the disk against bar formation due to the presence of a strong ILR (e.g. Toomre 1981). Alternatives to the *bar instability* are the bar formation and growth through slow orbit alignment (Lynden-Bell 1979) or via the episodic trapping of disk particles by an initially weak seeded bar (Sellwood 1981).

From an observational point of view, the best approach to test the conditions that favor the formation of bars is to study the bar fraction as a function of fundamental galaxy parameters. This can be a complicated task at high redshift, where the resolution can become an issue for the detection of bars. In the local Universe, nearly two thirds of the galaxies are barred (e.g. Sandage & Tammann 1981; Knapen et al. 2000; Whyte et al. 2002; Laurikainen et al. 2004a; Menéndez-Delmestre et al. 2007; Aguerri et al. 2009), and roughly one half of them are strongly barred (e.g. de Vaucouleurs 1963; Sellwood & Wilkinson 1993; Buta 2013).

The earliest studies of the cosmic bar fraction (Abraham et al. 1996, 1999) reported a significant decline on the frequency of bars with z , but the weak statistics and the image resolution were an issue in the analysis (e.g. Sheth et al. 2003). On the contrary, studies by Jogee et al. (2004) found a constant fraction of strong bars over the last 8 Gyr, indicating that cold gravitationally unstable disks are already in place at $z \sim 1$. The long lifetime of bars was also confirmed by Elmegreen et al. (2004), who suggested that bars in clumpy galaxies could have formed from instabilities of the gaseous disk and star formation rather than instabilities in the stellar disk. However, more recent work by Sheth et al. (2008) and Nair & Abraham (2010) showed that the global bar fraction increases with time ($\sim 20\%$ at $z \approx 0.84$). These studies also showed that the bar fraction depends on the colour, stellar mass, and bulge prominence of the host galaxy. More specifically, Sheth et al. (2008) found that only in the most massive systems was the bar fraction constant, with the long-standing bars formed at $z \approx 0.83$. However, in bluer and fainter systems the bar fraction declined before $z \sim 0.3$. Studies of the bar fraction at high z by Méndez-Abreu et al. (2010b) also indicated that the bar fraction is lower for the faintest systems. This is most likely related to the lower bar fraction observed in dynamically hot systems (Sheth et al. 2012), in agreement with the simulations by Athanassoula (2003). Nair & Abraham (2010) found a bimodal dependence of the bar fraction on the central concentration and the total stellar mass, with a minimum at $M_* \approx 10^{10.2} M_\odot$, which is consistent with the studies in Barazza et al. (2008). Because this was the mass at which a bimodality in the fundamental properties of galaxies and stellar populations was detected (e.g. Shen et al. 2003; Kauffmann et al. 2003; Baldry et al. 2004), the authors speculated that this might imply that the creation of the red and blue sequences are linked to the origin and evolution of bars. Interestingly, recent work by Simmons et al. (2014) based on the Galaxy Zoo project (Lintott et al. 2008; Masters et al. 2011, 2012), found the same low ($\sim 10\%$) bar fraction among the massive disks in the redshift range $0.5 < z < 2$. Galaxy Zoo is a citizen science project in which people across the world, irrespective of their academic background, classify the morphology of galaxies, and thus the presence of bars. Only galaxies with a reliable classification, based on the quality flags assigned by the participants, are used for the statistical analysis in Galaxy Zoo. This can induce a bias because faint galaxies tend to be excluded. Visual classification from Galaxy Zoo were used by Melvin et al. (2014) to study the evolution of the bar fraction with redshift in the Cosmic Evolution Survey (COSMOS; Scoville et al. 2007). They found a factor of ~ 2 decline in the bar fraction from $z = 0.4$ to $z = 1$, consistent with previous studies.

Recent simulations with live stellar discs and dark matter halos in a cosmological framework by DeBuhr et al. (2012) favor the stabilizing effect of dark matter halos. Possible observational evidence for this was recently provided by Cervantes Sodi et al. (2015), who reported a positive dependence between the bar fraction and the stellar-to-halo mass ratio using SDSS DR7 imaging and the galaxy group catalog by Yang et al. (2007).

One of the first self-consistent simulations of disk galaxies modeling the gas component was presented by Berentzen et al. (1998). Using a stellar and gaseous disk and a live halo, the authors showed that the amplitude of the dynamical instabilities is reduced if the cold gas component is taken into account. In this simulation the gas flowed towards the inner parts of the disk, enhancing the central mass concentration. The important role of the cooling of the disk via gas accretion for the formation of a bar was shown by Sellwood & Carlberg (1984) by adding stars in circular orbits to a self-gravitating disk. The accreted cold gas counterbalanced the kinematic heating caused by the recurrent spirals, favouring the formation of bars. However, different effects were found in the numerical models by Noguchi (1996), who showed that an effective gas infall could create clumps in the disk that cause the scattering of the stellar component, making the disk stable against bar formation. Using the GADGET-2 code and including the gas component and its physics, inducing star formation and feedback, Athanassoula et al. (2013) showed that disks in gas-rich simulations take longer to develop non-axisymmetries than their gas-poor counterparts. This is consistent with the results in cosmological simulations (Kraljic et al. 2012) and the above referred studies of the bar fraction at high z (e.g. Sheth et al. 2008), indicating that bars form earlier ($\sim 7-8$ Gyr ago) in red massive disk galaxies (typically gas-poor) than in bluer late-type spirals (gas-rich on average). A direct proof of a drop in the bar fraction among gas-rich nearby systems using H I measurements from the ALFALFA survey (Giovanelli et al. 2005) was provided by Masters et al. (2012). Athanassoula et al. (2013) also showed that triaxial halos can make bars growing earlier than simulation models with spherical halos. Gas-poor models in Villa-Vargas et al. (2010) presented rapidly decelerating bars. The authors also found that gas-rich models typically produce smaller bars.

On the other hand, N -body simulations of disk galaxy encounters by Noguchi (1987), using self-gravitating disks and a rigid halos (preventing bar formation in isolation), showed that bars can also be tidally triggered. This was confirmed in subsequent, more sophisticated simulations (e.g. Gerin et al. 1990; Salo 1991; Barnes & Hernquist 1991; Mihos et al. 1997; Berentzen et al. 2004; Lang et al. 2014; Goz et al. 2015). The existence of tidally-induced bars was supported by observations of larger bar fractions in galaxy clusters, compared to field galaxies, and also of an increasing bar fraction with decreasing cluster-centric distances (e.g. Thompson 1981). This was consistent with the enhanced bar formation in binary systems (among early-type systems) reported by Elmegreen et al. (1990), or the larger fraction of barred galaxies in high density regions in the local Universe shown by Giuricin et al. (1993). Recent models by Łokas et al. (2016) showed that tidal forces can form bars in the cores of galaxy clusters, but not in the outskirts. Nevertheless, more contemporary observations with better statistics showed contradictory results: Andersen (1996) and Barazza et al. (2009) found the bar fraction to diminish with increasing cluster-centric distance, whereas Méndez-Abreu et al. (2010a) did not find any dependence of the Coma cluster bar fraction with

the cluster-centric radius. The latter result is most likely related to the fact that galaxy encounters also heat the disk, what tends to inhibit the formation of bars. Studies in the Virgo cluster by Marinova et al. (2012) reinforced this interpretation. Using the catalog by Yang et al. (2007) to discriminate between central and satellite galaxies, and the visually identified bars by Lee et al. (2012a), Cervantes Sodi et al. (2015) showed that the bar fraction was somewhat larger for satellite galaxies compared to central galaxies, for a given stellar mass. However, this relation turned to be very weak at a fixed color. Based on visual morphologies from the Galaxy Zoo, Skibba et al. (2012) found that barred galaxies are more frequent in denser environments than their non-barred counterparts. Whether a galaxy belongs to a triplet or not does not determine the formation of bars, according to the study by Hernández-Toledo et al. (2011). In fact, the authors argued that bars seem to be more actively thickened or destroyed in higher-density environments. Considering only systems in isolated environments in the SDSS, Hernández-Toledo et al. (2008, 2010) reported bar fractions of 60-70 %, implying that galaxy interactions are not decisive for the formation of bars, but rather internal processes in the disk (as discussed in Hernández-Toledo et al. 2007).

Irrespective of the presence of bars, inside galaxy clusters the frequency of S0s (and ellipticals) is known to increase in high density environments, whereas the population of spirals decreases (e.g. Oemler 1974; Dressler 1980). This is known as the *morphology-density relation* (Dressler 1980).

Double-barred systems were discovered by de Vaucouleurs (1975). 3-D self-consistent N-body models by Friedli & Martinet (1993), with a considerable gas component ($\sim 10\%$ of the total mass), modeled the formation of nuclear (or inner/nested) bars, with different rotation speeds compared to the main bar, emphasizing the importance of dissipation in their formation. They appeared aligned at random with respect to the main bar, what was supported by the observations of double-bar systems by Buta & Crocker (1993). Erwin & Sparke (2002) found secondary bars in more than $\sim 25\%$ of barred galaxies and reported a mean length of $\sim 12\%$ of that of the main bar. Retrograde orbits were also found responsible for nuclear bars in the models by Friedli (1996). Also, orbital analysis by Maciejewski & Sparke (2000) showed that long-lived secondary bars appear only when the main bar ILR is present. Simulations by Debattista & Shen (2007) showed that long-lasting secondary bars, which rotate faster than the main ones, can form spontaneously without requiring gas. The latter was also shown in the numerical simulations by Rautiainen & Salo (2000)

1.4.2 Evolution of bars

N-body models have emphasized the decisive role that bars play in the secular evolution of spiral galaxies, and the contribution of bars to the redistribution of angular momentum within the galaxy. As shown in the early numerical models by Sellwood (1981), once formed the bar grows through the emission of angular

momentum to the stars in the outer parts of the disk, as long as these absorbers are sufficiently cool, with the bar ending near corotation. In the simulations by Sellwood (1981) the bar rotated fast enough to avoid ILR initially, and the bar pattern speed declined after ILR formed.

One of the first fully self-consistent models (i.e. particles responding gravitationally to each other) with a halo and a bar-unstable disk was developed by Little & Carlberg (1991). Using a considerable amount of particles ($\sim 10^5$), they showed that the bar slows down by a factor of two within a Hubble-Lemaître time. In terms of the corotation resonance, that was translated into a bar that evolved from $1.0 \leq r_{\text{cor}}/r_{\text{bar}} \leq 1.1$ when it formed to $r_{\text{cor}}/r_{\text{bar}} \geq 1.3$ at the end of the simulation. The bar slowdown due to the dynamical friction with the halo has been witnessed in several other simulations (e.g. Hernquist & Weinberg 1992; Debattista & Sellwood 1998, 2000). The rapid slow-down of the bar rotation in the presence of a spherical halo was also demonstrated analytically by Weinberg (1985). Besides, Contopoulos (1980) demonstrated that the orbits making bars do not extend beyond the corotation resonance radius.

Using 3-D simulations with a large number of particles and a live halo, Athanassoula (2003) provided an up-to-date view of how the angular momentum transfer takes place in disk galaxies, which is in agreement with analytic calculations. Namely, angular momentum is emitted from material near the bar inner Lindblad resonance, and absorbed mainly by material in the surroundings of the resonances of the spheroidal components (dark matter halo and bulge, when present) and also in the outer disk resonances. Athanassoula (2003) also showed that the angular momentum transfer could be hampered if the absorbers were dynamically hot, in conformity with the analytical results in Lynden-Bell & Kalnajs (1972) and Tremaine & Weinberg (1984b).

As a consequence of the exchange of angular momentum, simulation models also predict that bars become longer, thinner and stronger within a Hubble-Lemaître time (e.g. Athanassoula & Misiriotis 2002). Here, by stronger bars we mean more elliptical and massive (larger density amplitudes). To illustrate this, in Fig. 1.11 we show the time evolution of different bar parameters (pattern speed, strength and size) in the high-resolution self-consistent simulation by Martinez-Valpuesta et al. (2006), which includes an exponential stellar disk embedded in a live dark matter halo, during a period $\tau \sim 14$ Gyr (a Hubble-Lemaître time). The bar strength is measured from the $m = 2$ amplitude (A_2 , see further details in Sect. 3.3) for the bar as a whole and for the outer part only. When the bar forms, its amplitude grows until it reaches $\tau \sim 1.8$ Gyr and the so-called vertical *buckling instability* (Raha et al. 1991) occurs. This is an instability that causes the inner parts of the bar to thicken out of the mid-plane, giving birth to a boxy/peanut bulge (see Sect. 1.5.4 for further details). After this buckling episode, the outer part of the bar gets practically dissolved and the inner part weakens (Martinez-Valpuesta & Shlosman 2004). The bar strengthens again in the ensuing gigayears and experiences other buckling events (e.g. at $\tau \sim 6$ Gyr) that lead to a transient

Figure 1.11: *Left column:* Time evolution of the bar pattern speed (lower panel) and the $m = 2$ amplitude of the bar as a whole ($0 \leq r \leq 11$, black thick line) and only for the outer part ($7 \leq r \leq 11$, green thin line) (upper panel) in the simulation by Martinez-Valpuesta et al. (2006). *Right column:* Time evolution of the bar length (upper panel), the corotation radius relative to the bar size (central panel), and the bar ellipticity (lower panel) for the same simulation. For the first two plots, bar sizes are estimated from ellipse fitting to the isodensities (solid lines) and from the semi-major axis of the last stable orbit of the main orbital family supporting the bar (filled green circles). Credit: Fig. 2 and Fig. 4 from Martinez-Valpuesta et al. (2006).

weakening of the bar and cause the appearance of X-shapes. These secondary bar buckling episodes were for the first time reported by Martinez-Valpuesta et al. (2006). The first buckling of the bar has an clear imprint (rapid growth and sharp drop) in the evolution of the bar length (r_{bar}) and ellipticity ($\epsilon = 1 - b/a$, where a and b refer to the bar major and minor axes length), whose overall trend over a Hubble-Lemaître period is monotonically rising, and also in the pattern speed (Ω_b), which tends to decay in time. Regarding the corotation radius, $r_{\text{cor}}/r_{\text{bar}}$ peaks during the first buckling and from this point forward it spans in the range 1 – 1.4. Athanassoula (1992b) showed that the relative extent of the bar with respect to its corotation radius defines the shape of the offset dust lanes in bars, which are the loci of shocks in the gas flow (Prendergast 1962). In particular, the observed

shapes of dust lanes limit $r_{\text{cor}}/r_{\text{bar}}$ to a narrow range 1.2 ± 0.2 , consistent with the values obtained later by Martínez-Valpuesta et al. (2006). Besides, it was shown that the curvature of the dust lanes is inversely proportional to the strength of the bars. This was confirmed observationally by Knapen et al. (2002), with a sample formed by a dozen galaxies. A more thorough analysis was done in Comerón et al. (2009), who confirmed the theoretical prediction, but reported a large spread in the relationship between the bar strength and the dust lane curvature. Using an improved method to calculate dust lanes shapes and based on numerical simulations, Sánchez-Menguiano et al. (2015) gave further evidence for this relation, but only among fast bars (i.e. $1 \leq r_{\text{cor}}/r_{\text{bar}} \leq 1.4$). They concluded that among slow bars the dust lane curvature distribution is constant as a function of bar strength.

Calculations of the bar pattern speed of real galaxies do not always match the bar slow-down prediction in numerical simulations. Traditionally, estimates from observations (e.g. Aguerra et al. 2003) have been done using the *Tremaine-Weinberg* method (Tremaine & Weinberg 1984a). Ω_b is obtained from measurements of the radial velocity and the surface brightness of a galactic disk, which is supposed to be flat, to have a single pattern speed, and to have a surface brightness which obeys the continuity equation. Using this method, Aguerra et al. (2015) reported fast bars for all Hubble types, in agreement with the previous studies in the literature (e.g. Corsini 2011). The bar pattern speed can be constrained with the aid of simulations by fitting the observed gas distribution and/or gas velocity field (e.g. Sanders & Tubbs 1980; Lindblad et al. 1996; Pérez et al. 2004). Also, using the 2-D sticky particle simulation method of Salo et al. (1999), Rautiainen et al. (2005, 2008) showed that bars in early-type galaxies have typical ratios $r_{\text{cr}}/r_{\text{bar}} \leq 1.4$ (fast bars), whereas later-types have bars which can be both fast and slow.

Most recent models argue in favor of bars being long-lived structures (e.g. Shen & Sellwood 2004; Villa-Vargas et al. 2010; Athanassoula et al. 2013), that is, once the stellar bars form in N-body simulations, they do not easily dissolve. Nevertheless, bars followed a very different track in the simulations by Bournaud & Combes (2002), experiencing a recurrent destruction and reformation, when a high gas accretion rate was considered. This gas compensated the disk heating caused by the episodic bar formation and dissolution. When the galaxy evolution was studied in isolation, the bar weakened to form a lens. Further support for the transient nature of bars (1-2 Gyr in typical Sb-Sc galaxies) was given by Bournaud et al. (2005). They found that the bar can be substantially weakened by a large central mass concentration (e.g. Norman et al. 1996) or due to the angular momentum that bars exchange with the infalling gas. The two effects together can dissolve the bar. However, the latter was not found to be very important in the simulations by Berentzen et al. (2007). It is worth reminding that, unlike in more recent simulations, Bournaud & Combes (2002) and Bournaud et al. (2005) used a rigid halo model. Besides, as discussed in Sellwood (2014), earlier phases of bar formation should enhance the central mass concentration, stabilizing the disk against forthcoming reformation episodes (e.g. Sellwood & Moore 1999), and as

the disk grows, gas would be preferentially accreted in the galaxy outskirts, barely influencing the bar instability in the central regions.

Simulation models of disk galaxies in MOND by Tiret & Combes (2008) produce strong bars very early (it takes ~ 1 Gyr to form a bar of amplitude $A_2 = 0.25$). Unlike when dark matter halos are present, there is a substantial weakening of bars in the late stages of the run. Besides, gas is more efficiently redistributed by MONDian bars. On top of that, under these circumstances, the pattern speed of bars is not found to decline, in agreement with some of the observational estimates in the literature.

1.4.3 Age of bars

Analysis of stellar populations in disk galaxies have not given conclusive results of the age of bars, given the small sizes of the studied samples. Based on observations of bar colors and ages for 12 bars, Gadotti & de Souza (2006) estimated an age difference between young and evolved bars of 10 Gyr, in agreement with bars being robust stellar structures. Observations of two galaxies by Sánchez-Blázquez et al. (2011) indicated that the stellar populations of their bars were similar to those of the bulge rather than to those of the disk, giving also support for the old age and survival of bars within a Hubble-Lemaître time. Previous work by Pérez et al. (2009) had found that galaxies with high central stellar velocity dispersions host bars mainly composed of old stars, while galaxies with lower central velocity dispersion have bars made of stars with a large dispersion in their ages. Recent stellar population analysis of NGC 4371 by Gadotti et al. (2015) revealed that the stars constituting the bar formed at $z \approx 1.8_{-0.4}^{+0.5}$, indicating a fairly early formation of its long-lived bar.

1.4.4 The role of bars in the secular evolution of disk galaxies

Simulation models predict that the torques exerted by the bar provoke the flow of gaseous and stellar material within the disk, driving the secular evolution of the inner parts of the galaxy and inducing the radial spread of the disk.

Secular evolution of the outer disk

Since the pioneering numerical experiments on the formation and evolution of bars by Hohl (1971), many independent studies based on N -body simulations showed the effect of bars pushing outwards the material which is located beyond the bar corotation, enhancing the stellar mass density of the outer disk (e.g. Schwarz 1984; Athanassoula & Misiriotis 2002; O'Neill & Dubinski 2003).

A $\sim 25\%$ increase in the disk scalelength induced by a bar was witnessed in simulations by Valenzuela & Klypin (2003). Likewise, Debattista et al. (2006) reported an enhancement of the disk scalelength due to the bar redistribution of

angular momentum, even when a rigid halo was used. The authors also found that the amount of disk spreading caused by the bar was strongly dependent on the initial kinematics of the disk before the bar instability, measured from the Toomre parameter. When the disk was hotter, the density change was weaker. Altogether, the authors concluded that the specific angular momenta of the halos do not determine alone the distribution of disk scalelengths.

Spiral arms (see Sect. 1.5.1 for a review) are also held responsible for the radial mixing of stars (e.g. Sellwood & Binney 2002), but this mechanism is not expected to induce very pronounced changes in the surface density profile of the disk. In the self-consistent high-resolution N-body + smooth particle hydrodynamics (SPH) simulations by Roškar et al. (2008), resonant scattering by transient spiral structure caused the radial migration of stars across the disk.

Another interesting mechanism for the radial motions of stars is the overlapping of the resonances of the spirals and the bar (e.g. Minchev & Famaey 2010; Shevchenko 2011). This can lead to an intense redistribution of angular momentum and material in the disk. Non-linear couplings between the spirals and the bar with different patterns have been witnessed in simulation models of galactic disks (e.g. Sellwood 1985; Tagger et al. 1987; Sellwood & Sparke 1988; Sygnet et al. 1988; Masset & Tagger 1997; Rautiainen & Salo 1999). Besides, this coupling is expected to pervade most of the disks, given the observational support for bars being drivers of density waves found by Salo et al. (2010) (see Sect. 1.5.1). The strong radial migration driven by this coupling was demonstrated with self-consistent Tree-SPH simulations and high-resolution N-body simulations in Minchev et al. (2011), where the disk spread was induced even in low mass galaxies. Brunetti et al. (2011) found that kinematically cold disks favor the radial mixing, in which case the role of bars becomes fundamental.

Furthermore, it has been shown by Athanassoula (2012) that the migration of material through bar-induced flux-tube manifold spirals (see Sect. 1.5.2 for further details) can induce an extension of the disk of as much as 50 %.

Evidence for the disk growth caused by bars was found by Sánchez-Janssen & Gadotti (2013) based on decompositions of the light distribution using SDSS-DR2 photometry. For massive systems ($M_* > 10^{10} M_\odot$) at low redshift ($0.02 \leq z \leq 0.07$), they found that barred galaxies typically show fainter extrapolated central surface brightness and larger disk scalelengths compared to their non-barred counterparts.

Secular evolution of the inner disk

The bar-induced flow of the material located inside the bar corotation behaves in the opposite way as it does in the outer disk. Simulation models in the 90's established that bars drive the cold gas towards the center of the galaxy (e.g. Athanassoula 1992a; Wada & Habe 1992; Friedli & Benz 1993). However, this has never been quantitatively probed using near-IR imaging and a large unbiased sample of

galaxies.

The funneled gas might eventually be spent in nuclear starbursts, and contribute to the buildup and evolution of disk-like bulges (Kormendy & Kennicutt 2004) (see Sect. 1.5.4 for further discussion on this stellar structure). Partial observational evidence for this process comes from the several detections of inner stellar and gaseous disks in the center of barred galaxies (e.g. Kormendy 2013, and references therein). Besides, an enhanced star formation in the central parts of barred galaxies has been detected (e.g. Ellison et al. 2011; Oh et al. 2012).

More light on the bar-driven secular evolution of the central parts of the galaxy has been shed analyzing kinematic data. For instance, from the study of the line of sight velocity distribution along the bar, Pérez et al. (2009) found that the barred galaxies in their sample presented a rotating disk-like component in the inner parts. Besides, unlike in non-barred galaxies, the distribution of stellar ages in the bulges of barred galaxies peaked for low stellar ages in the studies by Coelho & Gadotti (2011) and Pérez & Sánchez-Blázquez (2011). Recent work by Florido et al. (2015) showed an enhanced nitrogen-to-oxygen abundance ratio in the central parts of barred galaxies, which indicates a different star formation history caused by the bar-funneled gas.

Observational evidence for the trapping of disk particles by evolving bars has been recently presented by Kim et al. (2016). These authors showed that disks hosting longer, more massive, and more elongated bars (evolved bars, see previous Sect. 1.4.2) typically present a light deficit in the disk within the bar radius.

Star formation within bars of disk galaxies

As shown in Martin & Friedli (1997) and Verley et al. (2007), the ionized gas at the bar region, traced from the H_α emission, typically appears (1) distributed along the bar, (2) in the nuclear or circumnuclear regions, with little or no emission from the bar, and (3) in both the bar and the nuclear region.

To date, there is not a clear understanding about the influence of local dynamical conditions on the star formation activity in bars. It has been suggested that star formation does not take place in strongly barred galaxies (e.g. Jogee et al. 2002). In some cases, the distribution of molecular gas (traced from the carbon monoxide; e.g. Dickman et al. 1986) indicates that the star formation along the bar appears to be inhibited in some locations of the dust lanes due to the high strength of shocks and shear stress (e.g. Reynaud & Downes 1998). This is confirmed in the fluid dynamics simulations by Athanassoula (1992b). Nevertheless, H II regions have been found under these conditions in other galaxies (e.g. Martin & Friedli 1997; Sheth et al. 2002; Zurita & Pérez 2008). Furthermore, observations of H_α velocity gradients showed that shear makes star formation drop, whereas shocks enhance it in general (Zurita et al. 2004).

Using $H\alpha$ imaging for galaxies in the Coma supercluster (Gavazzi et al. 2015b) and in the Local supercluster (Gavazzi et al. 2012), recent work by Gavazzi et al.

(2015a) proposed that strong bars played an important role in the quenching of the star formation of massive galaxies since $z = 3$. Specifically, bars caused the inflow of gas and triggered the burst of star formation in the nuclear regions. This process eventually depleted the gas and thus induced the quenching of star formation in the inner regions. This was supported by their observations at different z of a declining bar fraction for non-quenched galaxies. This was also consistent with the study by Cheung et al. (2013), who found a larger bar fraction among galaxies which are quiescent (low total specific star formation rate).

Fueling of AGN by bars?

There is observational evidence for the presence of supermassive black holes in the centers of massive galaxies (e.g. Kormendy & Richstone 1995), with masses spanning several orders of magnitude ($\sim 10^6 - 10^{10} M_{\odot}$). Black holes are so compact that their gravitational pull prevents electromagnetic radiation from escaping the so-called *event horizon*. Studies of the stellar orbits in the location of Sagittarius A* (bright radius source from the center of the Milky Way) have revealed that our own galaxy has a super massive black hole of mass $\sim 4 \cdot 10^6 M_{\odot}$ (e.g. Schödel et al. 2002; Gillessen et al. 2009), confirming the prediction of its existence made by Lynden-Bell & Rees (1971). Around 10 Gyr ago, when the bulk of the SBH was assembled, these were extremely energetic objects known as *quasars*. Nowadays, their activity is rather quiescent. However, in some present-day *active* galaxies, there is an ongoing shallowing of gaseous material from an accretion disk by the SBH. The radiation resulting from this accretion can be observed in all wavelengths, from radio to gamma ray bands. These are systems with an active galactic nucleus (AGN).

Bars are expected to trigger the inflow of cold gas towards the central region of galaxies, leading to starbursts. Despite the several proposed mechanisms based on numerical simulations, how galaxies drive this gas to the central ~ 100 pc to feed the SBH is still unclear (e.g. Wada 2004; Hao et al. 2009). Pioneering work by Shlosman et al. (1989) proposed a system of nested bars (bars within bars) to sweep the interstellar medium into a central gaseous disk. Other possible mechanisms for the feeding of the central black hole is the existence of nuclear mini-spirals (e.g. Emsellem et al. 2015). The role of bars maintaining AGNs was supported by studies of the bar fraction in the local Universe. Using near-infrared photometry, Knapen et al. (2000) found that Seyfert hosts (i.e. active systems) are barred more often ($\sim 79 \pm 7.5\%$) than non-Seyfert galaxies ($\sim 59 \pm 9\%$). Likewise, based on H -band photometry from the HST, Laine et al. (2002) observed a $\sim 73 \pm 6\%$ bar fraction among Seyfert galaxies against a $\sim 50 \pm 7\%$ frequency among the non-active. Using near-IR imaging from the Ohio State University Bright Galaxy Survey (OSUBGS; Eskridge et al. 2002) and the Two Micron All Sky Survey (2MASS; Skrutskie et al. 1997), Laurikainen et al. (2004a) also found a larger frequency of bars in active galaxies, compared to the non-active counter-

parts. Nevertheless, work by Lee et al. (2012b) found no causality between the presence of bars and AGNs. The authors claimed that the apparent higher bar fraction among the Seyfert galaxies is explained by the fact that AGN-host galaxies are on average redder and more massive, which are conditions that favor the bar instability (e.g. Sheth et al. 2012). In fact, Lee et al. (2012b) found no correlation between the bar fraction and the nuclear activity when either the total stellar mass or the colour were fixed. Moreover, Cisternas et al. (2013) quantified the nuclear activity of S⁴G galaxies from *Chandra* X-ray data, finding no connection between the bar strength and the AGN X-ray luminosity. Recently, Cisternas et al. (2015) used the *Chandra* COSMOS survey (Elvis et al. 2009) to distinguish AGNs and HST imaging to identify bars at different z , finding that the bar fraction is similar for active and non-active systems, declining with redshift from 71% at $z \sim 0.3$ to 35% at $z \sim 0.8$.

1.4.5 Photometric properties of bars and the signatures of secular evolution

Light distribution of bars

As it was shown in the pioneering work by Kormendy (1982a) and Elmegreen & Elmegreen (1985), bars in early- and late-type disk galaxies are characterized by distinct azimuthally averaged surface brightness radial profiles. Early-type bars are flat, that is, they show a scarcely decreasing luminosity profile at the bar region, which decays in the outer disk. On the contrary, the luminosity profiles of late-type bars present an exponential decay with a similar slope as the rest of the disk. This has been recently reassessed by Kim et al. (2015), who found that bars in more massive and bulged systems are characterized by a flat profile, whereas bars in fainter disk-dominated systems show exponential profiles.

Among the early-type systems, many barred galaxies present blobs (or handles) at the end of the bar, known as ansae morphology (e.g. Danby 1965; Laurikainen et al. 2007). Martinez-Valpuesta et al. (2007) found that $\sim 40\%$ of the lenticulars hosting a bar show an ansae shape, whereas galaxies of types Sb or later do not present this feature.

Strength and shape of bars

The optimal methodology for estimating the bar-induced perturbation strength from photometry is a highly significant area for exploratory study, even though this topic has been widely treated in the last decades (e.g. Knapen 1999). The strength of a bar can be defined as the efficacy of its potential to control the orbital motions of the stars.

A very natural measurement of the strength of the bar is the ratio of the tangential force to the mean axisymmetric radial force field, proposed by Combes

& Sanders (1981). This method was applied later to relatively large samples of galaxies, whose gravitational potentials were inferred from optical and infrared images (e.g. Buta & Block 2001; Laurikainen & Salo 2002; Laurikainen et al. 2002, 2004a,b). Also, the bar prominence has been estimated from the $m = 2$ normalized Fourier intensity amplitude (e.g. Laurikainen et al. 2004b, 2005). Bars in early-type systems are characterized by larger $m = 2$ normalized Fourier amplitudes (e.g. Laurikainen et al. 2004a). However, the amplitude of the tangential-to-radial forces at the bar region is typically smaller for early-type spirals and S0s (Laurikainen et al. 2004b; Buta et al. 2010).

An alternative way to obtain the strength of the bars photometrically is to derive their intrinsic axial ratios (e.g. Martin 1995; Laurikainen et al. 2002). On average, all the spiral galaxies seem to host bars with the same ellipticity, regardless of their Hubble stage (e.g. Marinova & Jogee 2007). Lenticulars are characterized by less elliptical bars (Laurikainen et al. 2007). Gadotti (2011) quantified the strength of bars from 2-D decompositions by fitting generalized ellipses to the bar component and measuring their ellipticity and boxyness. Athanassoula et al. (1990) showed that the bar isophotes among early-type strongly barred galaxies are rectangular. Based on the analysis of the deviations of the bar isophotes from perfect ellipses, Gadotti et al. (2007) also claimed that bars are characterized by boxy isophotes in general.

Length of bars

Many techniques have been applied in the literature to estimate the length of stellar bars. The bar extent has been measured visually (e.g. Kormendy 1979) or based on the fitting of ellipses to the bar isophotes and the detection of a peak in the ellipticity radial profiles (e.g. Wozniak et al. 1995). Both N-body simulations and observations indicated that the ellipticity profiles of barred galaxies tend to peak slightly before the end of the bar (e.g. Rautiainen & Salo 1999; Athanassoula & Misiriotis 2002; Wozniak & Pierce 1991; Laurikainen & Salo 2002). To avoid this problem, Erwin & Sparke (2003) and Erwin (2005) used the first minimum after the bar enhancement in the ellipticity profiles to estimate the bar sizes. However, the location of this minimum is strongly dependent on the bar type, the inclination of the galaxy and the intrinsic eccentricity of the disk beyond the bar (Michel-Dansac & Wozniak 2006). Furthermore, bar sizes have been estimated from the bar-interbar luminosity contrast or phase by doing a Fourier analysis of the images (e.g. Ohta et al. 1990; Quillen et al. 1994; Aguerri et al. 2000; Laurikainen & Salo 2002).

It has been shown that bars in early-type spiral galaxies are substantially longer than their later-type counterparts (e.g. Erwin 2005). However, studies of bars with a rich sampling of the latest-types ($T \geq 6$) lack in the literature. Lenticulars are characterized by shorter bars on average (e.g. Laurikainen et al. 2007).

Figure 1.12: *Left column:* Bar size (relative to the disk) vs. bar strength (measured from the product of the bar ellipticity and boxyness) for galaxies with disky pseudobulges and classical bulges (see Sect. 1.5.4). Credit: Fig. 3 from Gadotti (2008b). *Central and right columns:* Bar maximum $m = 2$ normalized Fourier amplitude vs. disk-relative bar size (and radius of maximum A_2). Credit: Fig. 2 from Elmegreen et al. (2007a).

Imprints of secular evolution

A fundamental question concerning galaxy evolution is the following: *What galaxies are candidates to evolve secularly in the current Universe?* A possible answer to this question was provided by Kormendy & Kennicutt (2004): secular evolution in the local Universe is stronger in intermediate-late-type systems (e.g. Sbc galaxies like IC 0769). Indeed, Sbc galaxies seem to host the most massive disky-bulges (but see Sect. 1.5.4). As these galaxies deplete their gas, they are candidates to move in the Hubble sequence towards earlier-types. The patchy nature of the latest-type systems disfavors the outward convey of angular momentum, while early-type spirals and lenticulars lack cold gas to be transported by secular processes. Nonetheless, secular evolution of the stellar component among early-type systems also occurs (Kormendy 2013).

As reviewed in Kormendy & Fisher (2005) and in previous sections of this thesis, secular evolution takes place when bars/ovals or spiral arms are present in the disk. In addition to the presence of non-asymmetric structures as driving mechanisms, the disk spreading must be energetically favorable. That is, the shape of their rotation curves in the outer parts must be either flat or decaying (e.g. NGC 3198 and NGC 4736 in de Blok et al. 2008, respectively), meaning that the angular velocity decreases outwards ($\Omega \propto 1/r$ when the rotation curve is flat)

and thus the disk spreading minimizes the total energy at a fixed total angular momentum.

As discussed in Sect. 1.4.2, dynamical models predict that stellar bars become longer, thinner and stronger and slow down their rotation speed within a Hubble-Lemaître time as a result of the angular momentum exchange. The bar evolution was studied observationally by Laurikainen et al. (2007), who found that early-type systems (more evolved systems) typically present larger density amplitudes and bar lengths (relative to the disk size). Evidence for the bar growth in a cosmic time was also given by Elmegreen et al. (2007a) and Gadotti (2011), who found a correlation between the size of bars and various proxies of their strength, respectively the maximum $m = 2$ normalized Fourier amplitude and the ellipticity and boxyness of the bar (see Fig. 1.12).

1.5 Stellar structures in disk galaxies

The main features of the most fundamental galactic stellar structures are discussed in this section. A review of their possible formation mechanisms is also presented.

1.5.1 Spiral arms

The most conspicuous stellar structures of spiral galaxies are the two (or even more) spiral arms that sweep out from the center of the disk (if the galaxy is unbarred) or from both ends of the stellar bar, if any. Spiral arms are sites rich in gas with an intense star formation, having H II regions and dust (e.g. Schweizer 1976; Elmegreen et al. 2011). This makes them more prominent in blue bands of the spectrum, but their backbone is composed of old stars (e.g. Elmegreen 1981; Elmegreen & Elmegreen 1989).

There are three main types of spiral arms in the notation of Elmegreen & Elmegreen (1989): the grand-design, the flocculent and the multi-arm. The fraction of each of these classes in disk galaxies is $\sim 18\%$, $\sim 50\%$ and $\sim 32\%$, respectively (Buta et al. 2015). Grand-design galaxies (Lin & Shu 1966) are characterized by two long, narrow, and well defined arms. Flocculent spirals (Elmegreen 1981) present short and fragmented spiral arm sections. They are more common in faint systems (Elmegreen & Elmegreen 1985). The fairly symmetric multi-arm galaxies are a category between grand-design and flocculent, closer to the former, characterized by a central two-armed pattern that develops long ramifications in the outer parts of the optical disk.

How tightly wound the spiral arms are is typically quantified by measuring the pitch angle. It is defined as the angle subtended by the tangent to the spiral arm, relative to the tangent to a circle in a point at a given galactocentric radius. The pitch angle is not necessarily constant, regardless of the class of the spiral arms (e.g. Davis et al. 2015). It has been shown that pitch angles depend on the central

mass concentration and atomic gas density (Davis et al. 2015) as well as on the steepness of the rotation curves (e.g. Seigar et al. 2006).

The most accepted explanation of the formation of spirals is the density wave theory by Lin & Shu (1964). The arms are considered as density waves that rotate through the stars and gas in a shearing, differentially rotating galactic disk. Basically, this implies that the stars in the inner parts of the disk rotate faster than the spiral and can overtake it, whereas in the outer parts they lag with respect to the spiral pattern. Spirals can also be tidally triggered in interactions with companion galaxies (Kormendy & Norman 1979), as it is the case of the Whirlpool Galaxy (or M 51) (e.g. Salo & Laurikainen 2000).

Spiral arms play an important role in the secular evolution of disk galaxies. They are known to contribute to the rearrangement of gas that leads to the formation of disk pseudobulges, independently of the presence of a bar (e.g. Kormendy & Kennicutt 2004). Kormendy & Norman (1979) suggested that stellar bars are the main drivers of spiral density waves. The hypothetical coupling between bars and spirals has been a largely debated topic in the past decade (e.g. Seigar et al. 2003; Block et al. 2004; Buta et al. 2005, 2009; Durbala et al. 2009). It is supported in the recent work by Salo et al. (2010), who found a correlation between the local spiral density amplitude and the local bar-only forcing (the bar-induced tangential-to-radial forces after the effect of the spirals is suppressed).

1.5.2 Rings

Rings are stellar and gaseous closed structures in disk galaxies. Some of them are called pseudorings when they do not completely close but still a ring-like structure is seen, typically made by tightly wound spiral arms. Many rings present recent star formation and host young stars (e.g. Buta & Crocker 1993; Knapen et al. 1995). However, rings lacking star formation activity have also been found (e.g. Buta 1991; Comerón 2013).

Three main types of rings (nuclear, inner and outer rings) are found in galaxies, based on their position in the disk (e.g. Buta et al. 2015). The identification of the first nuclear and inner rings was done by Curtis (1918). Outer rings were first reported by Perrine (1922). The frequency of inner and outer rings in disk galaxies is approximately $\sim 45\%$ and $\sim 10\%$, respectively (e.g. Buta & Combes 1996). Only $\sim 20\%$ of the nearby disk galaxies sampled by Comerón et al. (2010), with Hubble stages $-3 \leq T \leq 7$, host nuclear rings.

The majority of the rings in disk galaxies are believed to form via secular evolution. They formed from the gas redistributed by non-axisymmetries and gathered mainly at the bar resonances (e.g. Marochnik et al. 1972; Schommer & Sullivan 1976) (see Sect. 1.3.5), namely the outer Lindblad resonance (e.g. Lynden-Bell & Kalnajs 1972; Duus & Freeman 1975; Athanassoula et al. 1982) (outer), the $1/4$ ultraharmonic resonance (e.g. Schwarz 1981)(inner) and in the inner Lindblad resonance (e.g. Rautiainen & Salo 2000) (nuclear). Nuclear rings

have been proposed to account for observed central drops in the velocity dispersion of disk galaxies (e.g. Comerón et al. 2008).

Because of their resonant origin, many inner rings in barred galaxies appear aligned with bars (e.g. de Vaucouleurs et al. 1964; Schommer & Sullivan 1976). However, Comerón et al. (2014b) pointed out that nearly 50 % of inner rings have random orientations with respect to the bar, suggesting that other physical mechanisms might be responsible for their creation. Also, alternative formation mechanisms have been proposed for nuclear rings, like an inner centrifugal barrier for the gas migration (e.g. Kim et al. 2012). A new theory for the formation of spirals, inner and outer rings, has been recently proposed and named the *manifold theory* (e.g. Romero-Gómez et al. 2006; Patsis 2006; Voglis et al. 2006; Romero-Gómez et al. 2007; Athanassoula et al. 2009). Their numerical simulations showed that material gets confined in tubes (invariant manifolds) that extend from the two unstable Lagrangian points at the end of the bar (L_1 and L_2).

Rings have also been found in non-barred galaxies (e.g. Buta 1995), where the bars could have dissolved (e.g. Raha et al. 1991; Bournaud et al. 2005) or got destroyed while interacting with a companion galaxy (e.g. Berentzen et al. 2003). Alternatively, they could also arise from strong spiral modes (e.g. Rautiainen & Salo 2000) or as a consequence of minor mergers (e.g. Knapen et al. 2004; Eliche-Moral et al. 2011). Another distinct and less frequent type of non-resonant rings, the collisional and polar rings, can form from accretion or collision with satellite galaxies (e.g. Lynds & Toomre 1976; Schweizer et al. 1983).

1.5.3 Lenses

Lenses are stellar structures with an almost flat surface brightness profile and a sharp outer cutoff that appear in many early-type disk galaxies (Kormendy 1979). They were part of the classification by Sandage (1961) and Sandage & Bedke (1994). Just like rings, they can be divided into outer, inner, or nuclear structures, based on their location with respect to the bar. They appear systematically coded in the *Near-infrared atlas of S0-Sa galaxies* (NIRS0S; Laurikainen et al. 2011), who showed that most of the early-type disks host a lens (consistent with Laurikainen et al. 2009; Buta et al. 2015), and that $\sim 25\%$ of the 206 galaxies in their sample had multiple lenses. As it happens with rings, lenses have been found in both barred and non-barred systems (e.g. Laurikainen et al. 2013).

Several mechanisms have been suggested for the formation of lenses, and their true nature remains a matter of debate. For instance, Athanassoula (1983) proposed that lenses arise from instabilities in the disk. They would form just like bars do, but their less eccentric shape would be a consequence of the differences in the initial velocity dispersion of the disk. This conclusion was based on the results in the simulations by Athanassoula & Sellwood (1983), where it was shown that cool systems tend to make thin bars, whereas hot systems tend to make fatter ones. Bosma (1983) proposed that lenses formed as a primary component in the

Figure 1.13: For left to right, an example of a galaxy hosting a classical bulge (M 81), a disky pseudobulge (NGC 6782) and a Boxy/Peanut bulge (ESO 597-G036). Credit: Figs. 5, 6 and 7 from Gadotti (2012). Courtesy NASA, ESA, and The Hubble Heritage Team (STScI/AURA).

early formation of the galaxy. The outer edge would correspond to the threshold beyond which the gas density is so low that the star formation was abruptly truncated. According to Kormendy (1979, 1981), lenses are the product of bars evolving into a more axisymmetric state. It has been proposed by Laurikainen et al. (2013) that some lenses are former barlenses (for details, see Sect. 1.5.4). Lenses have also been proposed to have an external origin, like a minor merger (e.g. Eliche-Moral et al. 2012).

A peculiar type of structures are the ringlenses, which are lens-like rings, firstly identified by Kormendy (1979). Their outer edges are like those in rings, but their inner edge is smoother. Ringlenses can also be classified as nuclear, inner or outer structures (e.g. NIRS0S).

1.5.4 Galactic bulges

Most of the present-day lenticulars, early-type and intermediate-type spirals ($T < 5$, i.e. earlier than Sc) present a substantial central mass concentration (e.g. Salo et al. 2015), that is, an excess of flux above the disk in the central regions historically referred as a bulge. The nature of this central mass concentrations is diverse, and it is not straightforward to disentangle the different stellar structures that emit this light. Studies of the photometric and kinematic features of bulges based on observations and simulation models have left us with three main categories: (i) classical bulges, (ii) disky pseudobulges, and (iii) boxy/peanut (B/P) bulges; in the notation of Athanassoula (2005). The physical mechanisms explaining the formation of each of these bulges is reviewed in this section. An example of each of them is displayed in Fig. 1.13.

All type of bulges can coexist in a galaxy. In fact, based on both photometric and spectroscopic observables, composite bulges have been detected in individual galaxies (e.g. Peletier et al. 2007; Erwin et al. 2015). In the rare event that a bar in a highly-inclined galaxy is seen in end-on perspective (i.e. the bar major axis is roughly parallel to the line of sight), it appears as a bulge-like central

concentration (e.g. Athanassoula 2013). A correlation between the size of bars and bulges was found in the early observational work by Athanassoula & Martinet (1980), suggesting a link between these two stellar structures. Most of the stars in bulges are known to be fairly old (~ 10 Gyr) (Sánchez-Blázquez et al. 2011). Recent work by Seidel et al. (2015a) showed that at least 50% of the stars in the bulges formed ~ 12 Gyr ago, while a younger component ($\sim 1 - 8$ Gyr) was also detected. This seems consistent with bulges forming through an early starburst-collapse, followed by a second phase dominated by secular evolution, as found in the simulations in a cosmological framework by Obreja et al. (2013).

Classical bulges

Classical bulges are featureless, somewhat spheroidal, mainly composed of old stars (very little gas or dust) and supported by random motions (e.g. Kormendy 1993; Moorthy & Holtzman 2006).

Attending to their photometric properties, classical bulges look indistinguishable from elliptical galaxies (Sandage & Bedke 1994; Renzini 1999). More specifically, they look like coreless-disky-rotating ellipticals (e.g. Kormendy 2016). This is manifested by the accurate fit of their surface brightness profiles, $I(r)$, that can be performed with a Sérsic function (Sérsic 1963) with a large (≥ 2) Sérsic index (n) (Kormendy & Kennicutt 2004; Fisher & Drory 2008):

$$I(r) = I_0 \exp \left[- \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^{1/n} \right], \quad (1.5)$$

where I_0 is the central intensity and r_0 the scale parameter. However, as shown by Fisher & Drory (2016), the Sérsic index alone is not a sufficient criterion to classify bulges as classical (~ 10 - 20% failure probability). A bulge-to-total mass ratio larger than 0.5 implies a classical bulge always (e.g. Kormendy 2016).

Kinematically, classical bulges also resemble ellipticals to a certain degree (e.g. Kormendy & Bender 2012). They seem to follow the Faber-Jackson relation and the size-luminosity relation from Kormendy (1977), known as the *Kormendy relation*, in a similar manner as ellipticals do. They also appear in a similar place of the fundamental plane (Djorgovski & Davis 1987; Dressler et al. 1987), that relates the size, velocity, and luminosity of the system. However, Gadotti (2009) and Laurikainen et al. (2010) noticed that classical bulges occupied somewhat distinct regions in the bulge mass-size relations, compared to ellipticals.

Since the early work by Toomre & Toomre (1972) and Toomre (1977a), it has been believed that classical bulges are the result of major mergers (mergers between two galaxies of similar sizes) followed by a rapid relaxation (rapid return to a equilibrium of the stellar system). This is thought to be the way elliptical galaxies formed (Lynden-Bell 1967), and is supported by the large galaxy collision cross sections predicted by Λ CDM that we commented in Sect. 1.2. Like in elliptical galaxies, the mass of a classical bulge has been found to correlate with

that of the SBH in its center (e.g. Gültekin et al. 2009), suggesting that the bulk of their growth is connected.

Another mechanism for the formation of classical bulges at high redshift is based on the clumpy structure that many galaxies present at $z \sim 1 - 2.5$ (e.g. Elmegreen et al. 2005). Unlike studies at low redshift, detailed decomposition and spectroscopic analysis of galactic bulges is not always feasible because of resolution. Noguchi (1999), Bournaud et al. (2007) and Elmegreen et al. (2008) proposed that clumps of masses of the order of $10^8 - 10^9 M_\odot$ and kpc-sized could have migrated to the center of galaxies via dynamical friction (mostly with the dark matter halo) and coalesced to form a classical bulge. In these models, a clump would take roughly 1 Gyr to reach the center of the galaxy, which is fast enough to prevent shear forces and supernova feedback from disrupting it. Interestingly enough, if the clump migration is modeled in a disk without DM halo (i.e. a MONDian galaxy, implying less dynamical friction), clumps would take ~ 3 Gyr to reach the center, which is enough time to destroy them (Tiret & Combes 2008). This makes MOND reducing substantially the formation of classical bulges at high redshift, what indeed would solve one of the flaws of the Λ CDM cosmological models.

Disky pseudobulges

The American astronomer John Kormendy was the first reporting the existence of very disky bulges (Kormendy 1979). He coined them pseudobulges in Kormendy (1982b, 1983). They are almost as flat as the underlying disks, making their detection complicated in largely inclined galaxies. Their luminosity distribution is fairly shallow (typically $n \leq 2$ in Eq. 1.5) (e.g. Fisher & Drory 2008). Disky pseudobulges are typically supported by rotation, that is, they are dynamically cold (e.g. Kormendy & Kennicutt 2004). Their structure in 3-D is well described by an oblate ellipsoid which is flattened by rotation (e.g. Davies & Illingworth 1983; Méndez-Abreu 2016).

Disky pseudobulges are mainly built from the gas gradually funneled by the non-axisymmetries (e.g. bars and spiral arms) to the central parts of the galaxy (e.g. Athanassoula 2003) (see Sect. 1.4.4 in this thesis for details). This basically means that disky pseudobulges are a product of secular evolution (e.g. Kormendy & Kennicutt 2004; Athanassoula 2005). Many disky pseudobulges present ongoing star formation (e.g. Fisher 2006), and they can host other substructures such as nuclear rings, spirals, bars, star-forming clumps and dust lanes (Kormendy 1993; Carollo et al. 1998; Kormendy & Kennicutt 2004).

There seem to be other non-secular mechanisms that trigger the formation of disky pseudobulges. Pseudobulges in a MW-type spiral galaxy were formed in the hydrodynamical+SPH cosmological simulations by Guedes et al. (2013) via dynamical processes rather than secular. The pseudobulges formed at high z from non-axisymmetric disk instabilities combined with minor mergers. They were

found to be the main building block of the galaxy, that assembled the periphery around it later (inside-out growth). This would explain why many pseudobulges are composed of old stars among late-type spirals (e.g. Carollo et al. 2007). Similar results were obtained in the simulations by Inoue & Saitoh (2012) and Okamoto (2013).

Boxy/peanut bulges

Many disk galaxies seen in edge-on perspective display a vertically thick inner component, which is boxy or peanut shaped, known as a boxy/peanut bulge. The first studies of B/P bulges in relatively large samples of edge-on galaxies were done by Jarvis (1986), Shaw (1987) and Shaw et al. (1990). Earlier notions of B/P bulges appeared in Sandage (1961), which refers to the boxy bulge identification for NGC 128 by E. Margaret Burbidge and G. R. Burbidge in 1959.

The formation of B/P bulges has been witnessed in numerical simulations of barred galaxies. A central thickening of the bar was first detected in the N -body models by Combes & Sanders (1981). Numerical simulations by Raha et al. (1991) linked the appearance of this puffed-up stellar structure to the *firehose* or *buckling* instability. An alternative explanation for the nature of this swollen component is the gradual inner thickening due to a vertical resonance heating proposed by Combes et al. (1990). Pfenniger & Friedli (1991) found that the formation of these structures was not inhibited even after forcing vertical symmetry of the potential in the mid-plane.

Using optical and near-IR imaging for ~ 1350 edge-on galaxies, Lütticke et al. (2000a) found that the frequency of B/P bulges is $> 40\%$ for Hubble types S0 to Sd, what supposed a robust link between B/P bulges and bars. Indeed, B/P bulges are known to share many photometric and kinematic properties with bars (e.g. Méndez-Abreu et al. 2008; Erwin & Debattista 2013). It has been suggested that the Galaxy hosts a B/P bulge (e.g. Cabrera-Lavers et al. 2007), that corresponds to the so-called COBE/DIRBE bar, the thick inner component detected in the image in the near-IR taken by the *COsmic Background Explorer* (COBE) satellite.

Observational and simulation-based studies of the line-of-sight velocity distributions (LOSVD) of strongly barred galaxies revealed a bar-signature in the form of a *figure-of-eight* (e.g. Kuijken & Merrifield 1995; Athanassoula & Bureau 1999). This traced stars in the bar potential orbiting faster and slower than the local circular velocity. Attending to simulation models, bars and B/P bulges are expected to have an imprint in the disk velocity fields, in the form of double-humped rotation curves (e.g. Bureau & Athanassoula 2005) and centrally flattened or peaking (σ -drops) velocity dispersion profiles (e.g. Wozniak et al. 2003).

Besides in the LOSVD (V , σ), B/P bulges are expected to stand out in the Gauss-Hermite moments. These moments describe the non-Gaussian terms of the LOSVD with the parametrization developed by van der Marel & Franx (1993) and Gerhard (1993). Specifically, they measure the skewness (h_3) and kurtosis

(h_4) of the LOSVD. h_3 is predicted to correlate with V (Bureau & Athanassoula 2005). Kinematic features of B/P bulges were detected in a sample of edge-on galaxies by Chung & Bureau (2004). In Bureau et al. (2004), both correlations and anticorrelations between V and h_3 were found. Also, a kinematic diagnostic for B/P bulges in face-on galaxies is the presence of a minimum in h_4 along the bar major axis (Debattista et al. 2005; Iannuzzi & Athanassoula 2015). This B/P bulge feature was identified in the kinematic observations by Méndez-Abreu et al. (2008, 2014). Despite the almost certain existence of a B/P bulge in NGC 4371, Erwin & Debattista (2013) did not find the aforementioned h_4 minimum, and it is unclear in the recent work by Gadotti et al. (2015).

Subtle galactic structures that appear against a bright and diffuse background are easier to identify when *unsharp* mask images are used. These images are created by subtracting artificially blurred or smoothed copies of the original image. Unsharp mask images of edge-on galaxies by Bureau et al. (2006) revealed that many B/P bulges are accompanied by peculiar X-shaped structures (see the $i = 90^\circ$ simulation snapshot in Fig. 1.14). This technique was recently applied in Laurikainen et al. (2014), leading to the discovery of 18 new X-shapes in addition to the 89 ones identified by direct inspection of raw $3.6 \mu\text{m}$ images in Buta et al. (2015). X-shapes were formed in the simulation models of disk galaxies (evolving in isolation) by Athanassoula (2005) and Martínez-Valpuesta et al. (2006). X-shapes have also been associated to galaxy interactions (e.g. Binney & Petrou 1985).

Barlenses: boxy/peanut bulges seen face-on

Barlenses, lens-like stellar structures embedded in bars that cover roughly one half of their size, were cataloged for the first time in NIRS0S (Laurikainen et al. 2011). An example of the barlens hosted by NGC 4314 is shown in the upper panels of Fig. 1.14, taken from Laurikainen & Salo (2016).

Strong evidence for a connection between barlenses and boxy/peanut bulges was found in Laurikainen et al. (2014). The authors showed that barlenses are actually B/P bulges in face-on view. Laurikainen et al. (2007) had already speculated that these inner lens-like structures were the face-on counterparts of B/P bulges.

Laurikainen et al. (2013) also conjectured that a fraction of the inner lenses that we observe in early-type unbarred galaxies might as well be the face-on counterparts of B/P bulges, in which the outer thin part of the bar dissolved, or they simply formed without any elongated thin component (e.g. Patsis et al. 2002).

Barlenses are mainly observed in galaxies of low inclinations. Laurikainen et al. (2014) showed that roughly one half of the barred S0s and early-type spirals host a barlens or an X-shape, which is similar to the frequency of B/P bulges in these systems. Prior to coining barlenses, Laurikainen et al. (2005) had modeled them in their multicomponent decompositions of lenticular galaxies. Barlenses

Figure 1.14: *Upper row:* K_S -band image of NGC 4314 (left) from Laurikainen et al. (2011) and its unsharp image (right). *Lower row:* Simulation model (gtr115) from Athanassoula et al. (2013) and Athanassoula (2014) in face-on and edge-on views (left) and surface brightness profile of NGC 4314 (right) across the major and minor bar axes (black and red points, respectively). Credit: Fig. 1 from Laurikainen et al. (2014).

can be mistaken for classical bulges by appearance. In fact, Laurikainen et al. (2014) also showed that, in the 2-D decomposition of the light distribution of an early-type disk galaxy with a barlens, the central flux of the galaxy would be erroneously associated to a classical bulge if the barlens is not modeled as a separate component. By doing so, the bulge-to-total mass ratio of the remaining central components is substantially reduced.

Recent work by Athanassoula et al. (2015) analyzed barlenses in an N-body + SPH simulation, finding a good agreement with observations. By studying these simulation snapshots at different orientations, they provided further evidence that barlenses and B/P bulges were indeed the same stellar structure. In addition, they showed that the sizes of barlenses (NIRS0S) and B/P bulges (Lütticke et al. 2000b; Erwin & Debattista 2013) have fairly similar distributions.

Chapter 2

Sample and data

The research in this thesis was done using the Spitzer Survey of Stellar Structure in Galaxies (S⁴G, Sheth et al. 2010). The S⁴G sample comprises 2352 galaxies observed in the 3.6 μm and 4.5 μm filters of the InfraRed Array Camera (IRAC; Fazio et al. 2004), installed on-board the *Spitzer* Space Telescope (Werner et al. 2004), that was launched in August 2003.

The S⁴G sample was defined based data taken from HyperLEDA¹ (Paturel et al. 2003), so that only bright and large galaxies (extinction-corrected total blue magnitude $m_{B_{\text{corr}}} < 15.5$ mag and blue light isophotal angular diameter $D_{25} > 1'$) in the local Universe (radial velocity $v_{\text{radio}} < 3000$ km s⁻¹, that is, $d \leq 40$ Mpc) were imaged. To avoid any unresolved light contribution from the Milky Way disk, only galaxies with a Galactic latitude $|b| > 30^\circ$ were chosen. The galaxies were mapped out to $1.5 \cdot D_{25}$ or more, but for $\sim 5\%$ of the galaxies the mosaics did not cover this extent.

S⁴G images reach depths at 3.6 μm of $\mu_{3.6\mu\text{m}}(\text{AB})(1\sigma) \sim 27$ mag arcsec⁻² ($\sim 1 M_\odot/\text{pc}^2$). The dust absorption or contamination by star formation is fairly reduced in these mid-infrared images. However, non-stellar emission from hot gas or polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) may pollute the emission in the 3.6 μm band (e.g. Zibetti & Groves 2011; Meidt et al. 2012).

The S⁴G sample spans for more than 5 orders of magnitude in stellar masses (M_*) and includes galaxies of all Hubble types (T), comprising both late-type dwarfs and bright galaxies. Nevertheless, it is dominated by late-type galaxies due to the distance restriction based on H I recessional velocities. More massive gas-poor systems will be added to the S⁴G sample (Sheth et al. 2013) to compensate this bias (these new galaxies have not been used in this thesis). Despite not being strictly complete in any quantitative sense, the S⁴G constitutes a representative and large survey of all masses and types in the nearby field and in diverse environments, covering galaxies from the red sequence through the green valley to the blue cloud.

The S⁴G sky subtracted science-ready images were processed from the raw

¹We acknowledge the usage of the database (<http://leda.univ-lyon1.fr>).

data through several pipelines, summarized in Sheth et al. (2010). After the image reduction, the final pixel scale of the $3.6 \mu\text{m}$ images is $0.75 \text{ arcsec pixel}^{-1}$, and the full width at half maximum (FWHM) is $\sim 2.1 \text{ arcsec}$. Masks of foreground objects or image defects were created automatically using SExtractor (Bertin & Arnouts 1996), and they were also edited by hand afterwards.

Muñoz-Mateos et al. (2015) (S⁴G Pipelines 1-3) obtained the $25.5 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$ isophotal radius of the $3.6 \mu\text{m}$ galaxy images ($R_{25.5}$) and the total magnitudes in the two S⁴G filters. Using the calibrations by Eskew et al. (2012) that were based on resolved maps of stellar mass and IR flux of the Large Magellanic Cloud (e.g. mass-to-light ratio at $3.6 \mu\text{m}$ $M/L = Y_{3.6\mu\text{m}} = 0.53$), the authors also derived the total stellar masses (M_*) that are used in this work:

$$M_*/M_\odot = 10^{5.65} F_{3.6\mu\text{m}}^{2.85} F_{4.5\mu\text{m}}^{-1.85} (D/0.05)^2, \quad (2.1)$$

where F is the total galaxy flux (in MJy) and D refers to the distance to the galaxy (in Mpc). The scatter in the relation between the IR flux and the stellar mass of the mapped regions in Eskew et al. (2012) was $\sim 30\%$.

Using GALFIT (Peng et al. 2010) and IDL-based visualization tools (GAL-FIDL), Salo et al. (2015) (S⁴G Pipeline 4) performed the 2-D decomposition of the $3.6 \mu\text{m}$ light distribution of the whole S⁴G sample into different structure components such as nuclear sources, bulges, bars and disks. Salo et al. (2015) also performed ellipse fitting to the $3.6 \mu\text{m}$ images (see Sect. 3.5 for a summary of the method) and calculated the disk outer orientation angle and axial ratio - $(b/a)_{\text{outer}}$ - from the outermost isophotes. Then, the inclination of each galaxy was derived by assuming the disks to be infinitesimally thin and intrinsically circular: $i = \cos^{-1}(b/a)_{\text{outer}}$. Bulge-to-total ratios (B/T), disk scalelengths (h_R), disk orientation parameters, and the ellipse fitting output from this pipeline have been extensively used in this thesis.

Querejeta et al. (2015) (S⁴G Pipeline 5) used the $3.6 \mu\text{m}$ and $4.5 \mu\text{m}$ bands and applied the independent component analysis (ICA) method (Meidt et al. 2012) to obtain mass maps in which non-stellar contaminants are filtered from the old stellar populations. They found that as much as $\sim 10\% - 30\%$ of the total light at $3.6 \mu\text{m}$ can originate from dust.

By visual inspection of the $3.6 \mu\text{m}$ images, Buta et al. (2015) classified the morphology of all the systems in the S⁴G, which is rich in disk galaxies (only $\sim 5\%$ are ellipticals), following a revised version of de Vaucouleurs Hubble-Sandage system (de Vaucouleurs 1959). Their taxonomy included stellar bars as well as other substructures like rings, lenses and barlenses. Buta et al. (2015) also determined the family (SB, SAB, SAB, and SAB) and the revised Hubble stage (T) of the galaxies. The galaxy family indicates the presence or absence of a stellar bar. SB and SA families refer to barred and non-barred galaxies, respectively, while the SAB is an intermediate family of weakly-barred systems. Intermediate sub-classes SAB (e.g. bars which are oval or have low bar-interbar luminosity contrasts) and SAB (fairly strong bars) are also cataloged.

The maximum circular velocities of the galaxies ($V_{\text{HI}}^{\text{max}}$) were estimated from the H I line widths ($W_{\text{mx}}^{\text{av}}$), available in the Cosmic Flows project (Courtois et al. 2009, 2011) and HyperLEDA ², correcting for inclination (from S⁴G Pipeline 4):

$$V_{\text{HI}}^{\text{max}} = W_{\text{mx}}^{\text{av}} / (2 \sin i). \quad (2.2)$$

In this thesis we mainly used 3.6 μm photometry for more than ~ 1300 disk galaxies with inclinations lower than 65° in Salo et al. (2015). Roughly two thirds of those galaxies are barred according to Buta et al. (2015). Contaminants-free mass maps are also used.

Some of the galaxies in the S⁴G sample belong to the Virgo and Fornax clusters (e.g. Binggeli et al. 1985; Sheth et al. 2010), whose centers are at distances of ~ 15.5 Mpc (e.g. Mei et al. 2007) and ~ 19.3 Mpc (e.g. Jordán et al. 2007), respectively. According to the catalog on interacting and merging systems in the S⁴G made by Knapen et al. (2014), only $\sim 1.5\%$ of the galaxies in our sample of low inclination galaxies are currently merging, $\sim 2.4\%$ appear highly distorted due to the presence of a companion, and $\sim 4.2\%$ present minor ongoing interaction.

²For $\sim 40\%$ of the galaxies in our sample we used HyperLEDA's apparent maximum rotation velocity of the gas (*vmaxg* parameter). This was obtained from 21-cm line widths and/or rotation curves (typically in H_α). The reader is referred to HyperLEDA's documentation for further details.

Chapter 3

Methods

The different methods applied in this thesis using the S⁴G sample are summarized in this chapter. It mainly describes the way in which we estimated the length and strength of stellar bars, the quantification of the stellar contribution of the circular velocity (leading to an estimate of the dark mass within the optical disk of the galaxy), and the calculation of 1-D average stellar disks and 2-D bar stacks.

3.1 Fourier decomposition of the galaxy images

Using the outer disk orientation parameters, the 3.6 μm images of the galaxies were converted to face-on under the assumption that the disks are intrinsically circular and infinitesimally thin. Using the NIR-QB code (Salo et al. 1999; Laurikainen & Salo 2002), the light distribution (I) of the de-projected image was Fourier decomposed (modes $m = 0 - 40$) in a polar grid with 128 bins in the azimuthal direction:

$$I(r, \phi) = I_0(r) \left[1 + \sum_{m=1}^{m=40} A_m(r) \cos[m(\phi - \phi_m(r))] \right], \quad (3.1)$$

where $A_m = I_m/I_0$ correspond to the normalized Fourier amplitudes and I_0 indicates the $m = 0$ surface density component. In particular, Fourier modes were calculated interpolating the flux within elliptical annulae concentric to the disk outermost isophotes, which were converted to face-on after multiplying by a projection factor equals $\cos(i)$.

3.2 Calculation of gravitational potential and forces

From the tabulated even Fourier amplitudes, we calculated the gravitational potential at the equatorial plane using the polar method (NIR-QB code):

$$\Phi_m(r, \phi, z = 0) = -G \int_0^\infty r' dr' \int_0^{2\pi} I_m(r', \phi') g(\Delta r) d\phi', \quad (3.2)$$

where $\Delta r^2 = r'^2 + r^2 - 2rr'\cos(\phi' - \phi)$, G is the gravitational constant, and $g(\Delta r)$ is a convolution function including the pre-tabulated integration over the vertical direction. For each mode m , the integration over the azimuthal direction was done with a fast Fourier transform (FFT), while in the radial direction a direct summation was used (for further details, see Laurikainen & Salo 2002). In each of the bins, we obtained the radial and tangential forces: $F_T = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \phi}$ and $F_R = \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial r}$. From these, we calculated maps of tangential forces normalized to the mean radial force field ($F_T(r, \phi) / \langle |F_R(r)| \rangle$). An example of the resulting maps for NGC 4314 and NGC 4123 is shown in panel C of Fig. 3.1 and Fig. 3.2. It is characterized by a four-quadrant butterfly pattern (e.g. Buta & Block 2001).

3.3 Bar density amplitude and gravitational torque parameter

The $m = 2$ Fourier amplitude comprises a large fraction of the bar flux (Laurikainen et al. 2002). Higher order even modes ($m = 4, 6$ and 8) also cover a substantial fraction of its light in early-type galaxies (e.g. Ohta 1996). We calculated the maximum of A_2 at the bar region, named A_2^{\max} , and used it as a measurement of the bar strength (e.g. Laurikainen et al. 2004a). The radius of this maximum was denoted as r_{A_2} .

We derived the radial profile of the normalized tangential force amplitude (Combes & Sanders 1981) from the torque maps (see panel D in Fig. 3.1 and Fig. 3.2):

$$Q_T(r) = \frac{\max(|F_T(r, \phi)|)}{\langle |F_R(r, \phi)| \rangle}. \quad (3.3)$$

The maximum of Q_T at the bar region, named Q_b , was used as an estimate of the strength of the bar (e.g. Buta & Block 2001; Laurikainen et al. 2002).

3.4 Assumptions and uncertainties in the calculation of bar torques

The assumptions made in the force calculations were the following:

1. The mass-to-light ratio is constant throughout the disk.
2. The vertical profile follows an exponential law: $\rho_z(z) = \frac{1}{2h_z} \exp(-|z|/h_z)$.
3. The scale height (h_z) is radially constant.
4. The scale height is proportional to the disk scale length (h_R). h_z was derived directly from h_R using the empirical scaling relation found by de Grijs (1998) from a study of edge-on galaxies. The multiplicative factors (and dispersions

Figure 3.1: See next page for caption.

Figure 3.1: The summary of force measurements for the barred early-type galaxy NGC 4314, classified as (R₁')SB(rl,bl,nr)a by Buta et al. (2015). *Panel A*: The de-projected image of NGC 4314 in magnitude scale with a range of 17-25 $\mu_{3.6\mu\text{m}}(AB)$. The light green line traces the ellipse fitted to the bar (maximum ellipticity). The blue dotted line corresponds to the size and position angle of the bar estimated visually. The purple and light blue circles show the radius of maximum normalized $m = 2$ Fourier amplitude and tangential-to-radial forces, respectively. The outer circle has a radius of twice the size of the bar. *Panel B*: The galaxy image with the axisymmetric $m=0$ component subtracted. The contours correspond to the force ratio $F_T/\langle F_R \rangle$ (separated by 0.1 intervals), and the dashed lines delimit the regions where the tangential forces change sign. *Panel C*: The map of tangential-to-radial forces ($F_T/\langle F_R \rangle$). The dashed line and the ellipse trace the shape and the length of the bar as in Panel A. The dotted circle indicates the bulge effective radius (from Salo et al. 2015). *Panel D*: The radial profiles of tangential-to-radial forces (Q_T). The solid black line corresponds to the nominal scale height used to calculate the gravitational potentials. The dashed lines correspond to Q_T (Eq. 3.3) computed with the upper (red) and lower (blue) bounds in the estimate of h_z in the relation by de Grijs (1998). The solid green line shows the Q_T profiles after eliminating the effect of the spiral arms (see text). *Panel E*: The normalized $m = 2$ Fourier density amplitude as a function of radius. The dashed lines correspond to the normalized amplitudes of the even Fourier components of higher order. The vertical lines show the maximum of the amplitudes at the bar region. *Panel F*: The $m=2$ Fourier intensity phase vs. radius. *Panel G*: The stellar component of the circular velocity inferred from the gravitational potential. The colors and style of the lines have the same meaning as in Panel D. The solid orange line indicates the inner slope of the curve (see text). The dotted vertical orange line corresponds to one fourth of $R_{25.5}$. The vertical dashed line traces the bar length.

Figure 3.2: As in Fig. 3.1 but for the barred spiral galaxy NGC 4123, classified as SBx(rs)ab by Buta et al. (2015).

in the relation) were the following (e.g. Laurikainen et al. 2004b): $h_R/h_z = 4(1-5)$ if $T \leq 1$, $5(3-7)$ if $T \in [2, 4]$, and $9(5-12)$ if $T \geq 5$. For each of these T -bins, the forces were calculated also for the highest and lowest h_z (ranges in parenthesis). This allowed to estimate the largest uncertainties on the forces. In addition, we calculated forces by estimating the disk scale height as $h_z = 0.1^{+0.1}_{-0.05} r_{k20}$, where r_{k20} is the K -band isophote radius at 20 mag arcsec⁻² from 2MASS, using the empirical relation from Speltinckx et al. (2008). The K -band is also sensitive to old stellar populations and has reduced dust extinction and contamination from star formation. The relation in Speltinckx et al. (2008) was derived to approximate the one by de Grijs (1998) when h_R or T were not easy to obtain (for instance, in galaxies at high z).

In Paper I we studied various sources of uncertainty in our estimates of Q_b , complementing the analysis in Laurikainen et al. (2004b). We showed that the uncertainty due to the vertical thickness determination was $\sim 10-15\%$. Laurikainen & Salo (2002) found that the value of Q_b was not strongly dependent on the functional form for the vertical profile as long as the same dispersion was assumed (for the exponential law $\sqrt{\langle z^2 \rangle} = 2h_z$).

We also tested the effect of the non-axisymmetries in the disk (e.g. spiral arms) on the Q_b measurement by setting to zero the $m > 0$ Fourier density amplitudes beyond the bar length (Salo et al. 2010). On average, the reduction of the gravitational torque after suppressing the contribution of the spiral arms was of the same order as the uncertainty related to the thickness of the disk, even though this correction was somewhat stronger for Sb and Sc galaxies (which are known to host more prominent spirals).

Similar differences ($\sim 10-15\%$) were found when the effect of non-stellar contaminants was tested by calculating the gravitational potential from P5 mass maps (Querejeta et al. 2015), and Q_b was measured (and likewise A_2) and compared to the bar torque parameter in $3.6 \mu\text{m}$.

We also reassessed how strong the assumption of a constant scale-height was. For an individual galaxy (NGC 4548) we calculated the gravitational potential after increasing the vertical thickness in the inner parts of the disk following the profile of a B/P bulge (e.g. Fragkoudi et al. 2015). Even for unrealistic very prominent B/P bulges, the deviation of the bar torque parameter with respect to the raw Q_b was similar to the uncertainty due to the disk thickness determination itself.

We also corrected for stretching effects of 3D bulges when deprojecting galaxies to face-on. The bulge stretching caused an enhancement of the tangential forces in the central parts of a few galaxies. In those cases, the bulge was subtracted from the image before de-projection, and the disk-only forces were calculated. The force of the bulge was added afterwards by assuming a spherically symmetric intrinsic light distribution. The flux of the bulge was taken from the 2-D decompositions by Salo et al. (2015). The bulge stretching correction was not very relevant in the statistical sense.

3.5 Ellipse fitting

Figure 3.3: Results of ellipse fitting for NGC 4314. *Left panel:* Image of the galaxy, with the bar elliptical isophote (ellipse) and the visually measured bar length (dotted line) highlighted. *Right panel:* Radial profiles of the ellipticity, position angle and b_4 parameter. The vertical solid and dashed lines correspond to radius of maximum ellipticity and the visual measurement of the bar length, respectively.

Ellipses were adjusted to the two-dimensional light intensity distribution of the galaxy images using the IRAF task *ellipse* (Jedrzejewski 1987). The ellipticity (ϵ) and position angle (PA) of the isophotes (intensity isolines) were allowed to vary freely, giving as an input the galactic center and the guess of the parameters of the first isophote. The position angle of an isophote is the angle subtended by its major axis referenced to North, moving counter-clockwise towards East, and the ellipticity is calculated as $1 - b/a$, where a and b refer to major and minor axes length, respectively.

The main output of ellipse fitting are the radial profiles of the PA and ϵ of the isophotes. The b_4 Fourier coefficient was also obtained, which measures the 4th harmonic deviation from a perfect ellipse of the isophotal fit. b_4 is positive or negative depending on whether disk or boxy isophotes are fitted, respectively (e.g. Beaton et al. 2007).

The result of applying ellipse fitting to the barred galaxy NGC 4314 is shown in Fig. 3.3. The ϵ profiles in galaxies with a well-defined bar grow monotonically until a maximum/plateau is reached, and start to drop at the bar end, as the outer disk is fitted (e.g. Martin 1995). In that region, the position angle is almost constant. The b_4 radial profiles typically present a rise due to the bar and a declining section in its outer parts, eventually turning negative.

Ellipse fitting was run for the whole S⁴G by Salo et al. (2015) to obtain the outer disk orientation parameters. For a sub-sample of S⁴G galaxies, we performed ellipse fitting again to obtain a better sampling of the isophotes in the bar region (Paper II). We also applied ellipse fitting to the bar stacks in Paper V (see Sect. 3.10).

3.6 Identification of bars

The bars in the S⁴G were identified with three different criteria:

1. Visually in the 3.6 μm images (Buta et al. 2015), navigating them with *SAOImage DS9*.
2. Detecting a maximum in the ellipticity profiles, accompanied by a constant position angle (e.g. Aguerri et al. 2009).
3. Detecting a maximum in the A_2 radial profiles, together with a constancy of the $m = 2$ phase (e.g. Aguerri et al. 2000), and simultaneously identifying a four quadrant butterfly pattern in the maps of gravitational torques.

3.7 Estimates of the bar length

The sizes of bars were also estimated with different methods:

1. Visually, after optimizing the brightness scale of the images to make the bars stand out.
2. From the radius of the peak in the ellipticity profiles (r_ϵ).
3. From the radius of maximum A_2 (r_{A2}).
4. From the radius of maximum gravitational torque (r_{Qb}).

We also derived the bar PA with methods (1) and (2). r_{Qb} and r_{A2} tended to underestimate the visual measurements (less strongly r_ϵ), specially among the faintest systems. All the statistical trends for the bar sizes reported in this thesis are maintained regardless of the bar length proxy that we used in the analysis. The different bar parameters (length, PA, ϵ) were de-projected to the plane of the disk by using the 2D analytical de-projection code in Salo et al. (1999) (see formulae in Gadotti et al. 2007). Here, the deprojected ellipticity of the bar is also used as a measurement of its strength (e.g. Abraham & Merrifield 2000).

3.8 Stellar contribution to the circular velocity

From the gravitational potential of the galaxies and their mean radial force field, we calculated the stellar contribution to the circular velocity as follows:

$$V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}(r) = \sqrt{\Upsilon_{3.6\mu\text{m}} \langle F_{\text{R}}(r) \rangle r}, \quad (3.4)$$

where r is the galactocentric radius, F_{R} corresponds to the radial force obtained for $M/L = 1$, and $\Upsilon_{3.6\mu\text{m}} = 0.53$ is the mass-to-light ratio at $3.6 \mu\text{m}$ obtained by Eskew et al. (2012), which is assumed to be constant throughout the disk. For every galaxy, we calculated the maximum of $V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}$ ($V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}^{\text{max}}$) and the radius of the velocity peak ($r_{3.6\mu\text{m}}^{\text{max}}$).

Examples of the resulting disk component of the rotation curves of NGC 4314 and NGC 4123 are displayed in the panel G of Fig. 3.1 and Fig. 3.2. Shown in the left panel of Fig. 3.4 is the rotation curve of an exponential disk (Freeman 1970) obtained analytically, which peaks at a radius of ~ 2.2 times the disk scalelength.

In Paper I we also studied how much the uncertainty on the scaleheight and its radial variations could affect the calculation of $V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}$. The most important source of uncertainty was associated to the mass-to-light ratio determination (e.g. $\sim 30\%$ according to Eskew et al. 2012). We found that the impact of non-stellar emission could account for a marginal $\sim 10\%$ mean overestimation of $V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}$.

3.8.1 Inner slopes of the rotation curve

We calculated the inner gradient of stellar component of the rotation curve, called as $d_{\text{R}}v_*(0)$. Following Lelli et al. (2013), we performed a polynomial fit (order $n=3$) to the inner part of $V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}$:

$$V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}(r) = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \cdot r^i. \quad (3.5)$$

We took the linear term as an estimate of the inner slope: $a_1 = \lim_{R \rightarrow 0} dv/dr = d_{\text{R}}v_*(0)$. The fit was made in the radial range between the galactic center and the radius of maximum velocity within $1/4R_{25.5}$. On average, $d_{\text{R}}v_*(0)$ is reduced by $\sim 15\%$ when non-stellar contaminants are removed (P5) prior to the calculation of the circular velocity.

3.8.2 Dark matter halo-to-stellar mass ratio

Using $V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}$ and the inclination-corrected H I velocity widths ($V_{\text{HI}}^{\text{max}}$), we obtained a first-order estimate of the halo-to-stellar mass ratio (M_{h}/M_*) within the optical radius (R_{opt}). R_{opt} is defined as the radius enclosing 83% of the light in the blue band, what corresponds to $\sim 3.2h_{\text{R}}$ for an exponential disk (e.g. Persic et al. 1996;

Figure 3.4: *Left panel:* Circular velocity of an exponential disk (Freeman 1970) as a function of galactocentric radius, normalized to the disk scalelength (h_R): $v^2 = 4\pi G \Sigma_o h_R y^2 [I_0(y)K_0(y) - I_1(y)K_1(y)]$, where $y = r/2h_R$, I_n and K_n are the modified Bessel functions, and Σ_o and G correspond to the central surface brightness of the disk and the universal gravitational constant (both parameters set to one). We also show the circular speed of a point with the same total mass as the exponential disk, $v = \sqrt{GM_{\text{total}}/r}$, and that of a spherical body that has as much mass inside a radius r as the exponential disk: $v = \sqrt{GM_{\text{expo}}/r}$ with $M_{\text{expo}}(<r) = 2\pi G \Sigma_o h_R^2 [1 - e^{-r/h_R} (1 + r/h_R)]$ (Binney & Tremaine 1987). *Right panel:* Ratio of the mass contained by a spherical mass distribution and that enclosed by an exponential disk as a function of the radius, relative to h_R .

Swaters et al. 2002). We assumed that (i) the gas contribution to the rotation curve is modest at the optical radius (e.g. Rhee 1996; Verheijen 1997; Borriello & Salucci 2001), (ii) the circular velocity at R_{opt} is approximately the observed maximum velocity:

$$(V_{\text{HI}}^{\text{max}})^2 \approx V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}^2(R_{\text{opt}}) + V_{\text{halo}}^2(R_{\text{opt}}), \quad (3.6)$$

and (iii) the disks are exponential. Based on these assumptions we derived:

$$M_{\text{h}}/M_{\text{s}}(< R_{\text{opt}}) \approx F \cdot \left(\frac{(V_{\text{HI}}^{\text{max}})^2}{V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}^2(R_{\text{opt}})} - 1 \right), \quad (3.7)$$

where F corresponds to the ratio between the mass contained by a spherical mass distribution and that enclosed by an exponential disk yielding a similar radial force at R_{opt} (Binney & Tremaine 1987). In the right panel of Fig. 3.4 we show this ratio as a function of the galactocentric radius. $F = 1.34$, and the ratio is roughly constant in the range $2 \leq r/h_R \leq 4$.

3.8.3 Decomposition model of the rotation curve

We calculated first-order decomposition models of the rotation curves. Our main goal was to quantify the contribution of the dark matter halo to the mean axisymmetric force field, so that we could assess its effect on the bar torque parameter

Figure 3.5: First-order rotation curve decomposition model of NGC 4314 (left) and the dilution of the tangential-to-radial force profiles by the dark matter halo (right). The x-axis ranges between the galactic center and the optical radius ($R_{\text{opt}} \approx 3.2h_R$). In both panels, the vertical dashed line indicates the visual estimate of the bar radius. Because this is a face-on galaxy ($i \approx 20^\circ$ in Salo et al. 2015), larger uncertainties in the inclination correction of the H I line width (Eq. 2.2), and thus in the decomposition model, are found.

(as done in Buta et al. 2004). Given the lack of rotation curves for the entire S⁴G sample, our only observables were the H I line widths and $V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}$.

We modeled the halo with an isothermal sphere:

$$V_{\text{halo}}^2(x) = V_\infty^2 \cdot \frac{x^2}{(x^2 + a^2)}, \quad (3.8)$$

where $x = r/R_{\text{opt}}$. The halo core radius (a) was estimated from the total I -band luminosity, (M_I , taken from HyperLEDA, where this value has been homogenized to the system by Mathewson et al. 1992) based on the universal rotation curve model (Persic et al. 1996), using the recipe from Hendry et al. (1997):

$$a/R_{\text{opt}} = \sqrt{2.25 \cdot 10^{-0.16(M_I+22)}}, \quad (3.9)$$

The halo velocity amplitude (V_∞) was obtained by matching the H I velocity at the optical radius, using Eq. 3.6. Finally, we calculated the radial forces exerted by the halo, $F_{\text{halo}}(r) = V_{\text{halo}}(r)^2/r$, and implemented the halo correction on the tangential-to-radial force profiles ($Q_T^{\text{halo-corr}}$) as follows:

$$Q_T^{\text{halo-corr}}(r) = Q_T(r) \cdot \frac{F_R(r)}{F_R(r) + F_{\text{halo}}(r)}. \quad (3.10)$$

Figure 3.6: The same as in Fig. 3.5 but for NGC 4321 ($i \approx 35^\circ$ in Salo et al. 2015), which has a much smaller halo-correction on the tangential-to-radial force profiles compared to NGC 4314. The black points in the left panel correspond to the observed $H\alpha$ rotation curve from Daigle et al. (2006). The rotation curves have been corrected for inclination using the orientations from Salo et al. (2015).

In Paper I we checked the robustness of the halo correction against variations (of the order of $\sim 20\%$) in the mass-to-light ratio, the galactic distance, the total luminosity or the measured H I width. For a subsample of galaxies, we also checked that the resulting rotation curve decomposition models more or less matched observed rotation curves in the literature (from Daigle et al. 2006; Dicaire et al. 2008; de Blok et al. 2008). In Fig. 3.5 and Fig. 3.6 we show an example of a rotation curve decomposition model for NGC 4314 and NGC 4321, together with the halo-correction on their force profile.

3.9 1-D stacked disk profiles

In order to stack the stellar disks in the S⁴G sample as a function of fundamental galaxy parameters, we rescaled the $m = 0$ radial amplitudes (I_0 , Eq. 3.1) to a common frame defined by the extent of the disks in physical units, and by the disk scalelength. We coadded the resized I_0 profiles to obtain 1-D average stellar density profiles (Σ_*) in bins of M_* and T . An example of the disk stack of galaxies with total stellar masses similar to the Milky Way ($M_{\text{MW}} \approx 5 \cdot 10^{10} M_\odot$) is shown in the left panel of Fig. 3.7.

Whether we averaged the profiles in units of flux or magnitudes, taking the mean or the median, the results were very similar as long as a large enough number of galaxies per bin (≥ 50) were considered. Beyond the $\sim 5 - 10 M_\odot \text{pc}^{-2}$ level,

the average Σ_* presented up-bending profiles. For a given stellar mass bin, less centrally concentrated galaxies extend further, introducing a bias in the galaxy outskirts. To minimize uncertainties, the mean Σ_* were only studied within the radial range with a large ($\geq 75\%$) sample completeness level.

In order to calculate the mean normalized $m = 2$ Fourier amplitude and the mean disk(+bulge) component of the rotation curve, A_2 and $V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}$ radial profiles of individual galaxies were rescaled to a common frame and coadded using the same methodology that was applied to I_0 .

3.10 2-D stacked stellar bars

In order to obtain average bars, the deprojected images of barred galaxies were reconstructed from Eq. 3.1 and rescaled following the next steps:

1. Rotation of the image with respect to the bar major axis, imposing a bar position angle equal to zero.
2. Geometric reflection across the bar major axis to make the spiral arms wind clockwise (in case they wind counter-clockwise).
3. Scaling of the reoriented image to a grid of radius $3 \cdot r_{\text{bar}}$.

In this 2-D common frame, the bar stacks were obtained by coadding the light within each of the bins in the polar grid. In the right panel of Fig. 3.7, we display the bar stack obtained by averaging the rescaled bars hosted by disk galaxies with total stellar masses similar to the Milky Way.

Figure 3.7: *Top panel*: mean stellar density profiles obtained by stacking galaxies with total stellar masses similar (± 0.1 dex) to that of the Milky Way ($M_* \approx 5 \cdot 10^{10} M_\odot$). The dispersion (σ) of the luminosity profiles at each radius are also indicated. The green circles indicate the median profile for MW-type galaxies at $z \approx 0$ from van Dokkum et al. (2013) using g -band SDSS photometry, showing good agreement with our measurements. *Central panel*: the number of galaxies whose radial profile extends to a given radius. The 75%, 50% and 25% sample completeness levels are highlighted with different lines. *Lower panel*: bar stack (in magnitude scale with range 17-25 $\mu_{3.6\mu\text{m}}(AB)$) obtained by co-adding bars whose host galaxies have M_* similar to the MW (same binning as in the left). Several isolines at the bar region (solid) and beyond the bar (dotted) are plotted (with the bar outer contour defined at 21 mag arcsec $^{-2}$).

Chapter 4

Results

In this section we summarize the content and the most important results in each of the papers compiled in this thesis. For their interpretation in the framework of galaxy formation and evolution, the reader is referred to Sect 5.

4.1 Paper I

In Díaz-García et al. (2016b) (Paper I) we characterized the lengths and strengths of bars in a sample of ~ 860 S⁴G disk galaxies with inclinations lower than 65° . We also studied the bar fraction (f_{bar}) in the S⁴G. Moreover, for more than 1100 galaxies, we calculated the stellar contribution to the circular velocity and we estimated the halo-to-stellar mass ratio within the optical radii, $M_{\text{halo}}/M_*(< R_{\text{opt}})$. Based on the universal rotation curve models, we also derived first-order models of their rotation curve decompositions. All the methods applied in this work were reviewed in Sect. 3.

4.1.1 Dark matter halos

We found that $M_{\text{h}}/M_*(< R_{\text{opt}})$ scales with M_* following the slope from the best-fit model at $z \approx 0$ in Λ CDM cosmological simulations (e.g. Moster et al. 2010)(see Fig. 4.1). Despite the substantial scatter, the predicted turnover at the high-mass end in Λ CDM models seemed to be followed by our cloud of points too, but a better sampling of lenticulars is needed. On average, we showed that the dark matter contained within the optical disk is roughly 4% of the total mass of the host halo. This percentage was estimated from the numerical factor needed to scale down the *total* halo-to-stellar mass ratio to match our M_{h}/M_* observations within the optical radius. Fainter systems ($T \geq 5$ or $M_* < 10^{10} M_\odot$) were more dark matter dominated within the optical radius than the more massive early-type systems, whose mean $M_{\text{h}}/M_*(< R_{\text{opt}})$ was ~ 2 (lower left panel of Fig. 4.1).

4.1.2 Bar fraction

Based on the various criteria for the detection of bars in this work (see Sect. 3.6), we studied the bar fraction as a function of fundamental galaxy parameters. A double-humped distribution of f_{bar} versus T was found ($\sim 75\%$ for Sab galaxies), with a minimum for Sb/c systems ($\sim 40 - 45\%$) (Buta et al. 2015). Unlike in early-type systems, for $T > 5$ the bar fraction was considerably reduced (by $\sim 30 - 50\%$) when the bars were identified via ellipse fitting or Fourier analysis instead of visually. Also, the amplitudes of higher order even components peaked at the bar region preferentially for $T < 5$ (consistent with Ohta et al. 1990). Furthermore, the bar fraction was found to drop for the systems with lowest stellar masses ($M_* < 10^{9.5-10} M_\odot$). This implied that f_{bar} dropped for systems with largest M_{h}/M_* ($< R_{\text{opt}}$), given the coupling between the luminous and dark matter commented in Sect. 4.1.1. In fact, f_{bar} was roughly constant ($\sim 50\%$) in the range $10^{10} - 10^{11} M_\odot$, with a solitary peak ($\sim 60\%$) at $\sim 3 \cdot 10^{10} M_\odot$, which is the mass of the turnover in the $M_{\text{halo}}/M_* - M_*$ relation discussed above (i.e. minimum dark matter content relative to the stars).

4.1.3 Bar length

We investigated the distribution of bar lengths, in physical units and normalized to the disk size (h_{R} and $R_{25.5}$), as a function of T and M_* . All bar length measurements presented in Sect. 3.7 gave very similar results. Completely different trends were found for early- ($T < 5$) and late-type galaxies ($T \geq 5$), or when splitting the sample with a mass cut-off at $10^{10} M_\odot$. For the former T-type bin bar sizes showed a positive correlation with M_* , whereas for the latter r_{bar} scaled inversely with M_* . Sc galaxies had the smallest bars on average ($\sim 0.15R_{25.5}$ and $\sim 0.7h_{\text{R}}$). Bar sizes were found to increase from intermediate-type spirals towards early-type spirals and lenticulars (see the upper panel in Fig. 4.2), reaching a maximum mean length of $0.25 - 0.30R_{25.5}$ and $\sim 1.25h_{\text{R}}$ for S0/a-Sa galaxies. Early-type S0s seemed to have somewhat smaller bars, but a larger sampling is needed to strengthen the statistics. Between $T = 5$ and $T = 10$, bars presented very similar lengths in physical units, but unexpectedly their sizes relative to the disk increased with increasing T .

4.1.4 Bar strength

We showed that the mean $m = 2$ Fourier bar amplitude (A_2^{max}) positively scaled with M_* . When studied versus T , the latest types showed the lowest A_2^{max} values on average ($\sim 0.35 - 0.4$), while A_2^{max} monotonically increased from $T = 4$ towards Sa and S0/a systems (e.g. Laurikainen et al. 2004a), dropping again in the range of early-type lenticulars (~ 0.5) (e.g. Laurikainen et al. 2007). Likewise, the mean deprojected bar ellipticity (ϵ) was roughly constant (~ 0.5) for all T and M_* .

among the spirals and irregulars (e.g. Marinova & Jogee 2007), dropping for the lenticulars (also consistent with Laurikainen et al. 2007). Finally, we showed that the mean Q_b increased monotonically from $T = -3$ (~ 0.15) towards $T = 7$ ($\sim 0.4 - 0.45$) (e.g. Laurikainen et al. 2004b). For early-type systems, the tangential-to-radial force profiles typically reached their maxima at $\sim 0.75r_{\text{bar}}$, whereas later-types showed centrally peaking profiles (at $\sim 0.4 - 0.5r_{\text{bar}}$). For all bar strength indexes, Magellanic and irregulars ($T = 9 - 10$) presented slightly weaker bars than Sd spirals.

Based on our rotation curve decomposition models, we estimated the dilution of the tangential forces by the dark matter halos. Among early-type systems ($T < 5$), we showed a moderate effect of the halo correction on Q_b ($\sim 10 - 15\%$) in the statistical sense, which is similar to the uncertainty in the determination of the vertical thickness. However, the effect of the dark matter halo was larger ($\geq 20\%$) for the late-type galaxies. Despite the analyzed sources of uncertainty in the calculation of the gravitational potential, Q_b was found to increase with increasing T . Nevertheless, when the tangential-to-radial forces at the end of the bar were studied, dark matter halos accounted for a reduction of 30 – 50% for the latest-type galaxies, flattening the statistical trends in the Hubble sequence (lower right panel in Fig. 4.1).

4.1.5 Dependence of bar parameters on the central mass concentration

We studied the dependence of bar parameters on the central mass concentration of their host galaxies, specifically their bulge-to-total mass ratio (B/T , from Salo et al. 2015) and the inner slope of the stellar component of the rotation curves, $d_{\text{R}}v_*(0)$. We found that bars with low values of Q_b appear together with galaxies with a large B/T , confirming the trends in Laurikainen et al. (2004a). This also manifested in anticorrelation between Q_b and $d_{\text{R}}v_*(0)$. The most natural interpretation of this trend is that the enhanced radial force field by the central mass concentration in early-type galaxies (e.g. classical bulges, disk pseudobulges and barlenses) dilute the bar-induced tangential forces, thus reducing Q_b (e.g. Laurikainen & Salo 2002). Likewise, more massive bulge (with larger Sérsic indexes) accompanied less eccentric bars, what is probably caused by bulges making the apparent bar isophotes rounder (e.g. Athanassoula et al. 1990; Gadotti 2008a).

Moreover, A_2^{max} , which is less affected by the bulge dilution, linearly correlated with $d_{\text{R}}v_*(0)$ and B/T . For the latter, a dependence was exclusively found with pseudobulges ($n \leq 2$) (obtaining a ~ 0.5 rank correlation coefficient). This is specially meaningful because it directly relates bars, which are expected to be important agents nourishing star formation, with the build-up of the central stellar components (see Sect. 5.4.1 for discussion). Also, bars hosted by early-type disk galaxies ($T < 5$) with large central inner slopes tended to have longer bars, relative to the disk size.

Figure 4.1: *Upper panel:* The halo-to-stellar mass ratio within the optical radius as a function of the total stellar mass. The orange filled circles correspond to the S⁴G galaxies with inclinations $30^\circ < i < 50^\circ$. More inclined ($50^\circ < i < 65^\circ$) and face-on systems ($i < 30^\circ$) are indicated with orange X symbols. As trends are the same regardless of the i -bin, we confirm that observation uncertainties due to inclination are not an issue in our analysis. The black dots correspond to the total running median and the error bars are obtained via bootstrapping. The different lines show the estimates in the literature for the total halo-to-stellar mass ratio vs. M_* , scaled down by the factor specified in the labels. *Lower panels:* The halo-to-stellar mass ratio inside the optical radius as a function of the Hubble stage (left), with the running median specified with a blue solid line. In the panel on the right we show the running mean of the bar maximum gravitational torque (Q_b) and $F_T/ < F_R >$ evaluated at the end of the bar - $Q_T(r_{bar})$ - with and without halo correction (i.e. the dilution of the bar tangential forces by the radial force exerted by the dark matter halo), as a function of T-type (right). Credit: Fig. 6 and Fig. 14 from Díaz-García et al. (2016b) (Paper I).

4.1.6 Relationship between the bar parameters

In spite of their different trends on the Hubble sequence, we showed a tight positive correlation between the different estimates of the bar strength. ε scaled with Q_b following a curved upwards trend (e.g. Block et al. 2001; Laurikainen et al. 2004a). This shows that the stellar orbits constituting the bar are effectively dominated by the underlying disk potential.

Besides, we found a two branched relation between Q_b and A_2^{\max} : a strong linear correlation between the two quantities was found when the sample was split at $T = 5$. This bimodality is partly explained by the effect of bulges diminishing Q_b , shown in the previous section. Despite the scatter, a similar segregation was found when both the normalized $m = 2$ Fourier amplitudes and the tangential-to-radial forces were evaluated at r_{bar} and compared. Because the effect of bulge dilution should be smaller at such radius, other galaxy properties might partially explain this trend.

The bar ellipticity was segregated in T when compared to the other two bar strength proxies. For a fixed ε , Q_b (A_2^{\max}) increased (decreased) with T-type. This is most likely explained by the fact that, unlike Q_b and A_2^{\max} , ε is insensitive to changes in the relative mass of a bar of fixed shape and length (e.g. Martin 1995).

We studied the different estimates of the bar parameters as a function of the galaxy families, as classified by Buta et al. (2015). SB and SAB galaxies typically had stronger and longer bars than SAB and SAB. Furthermore, all our bar strength indexes correlated with the bar length (scaled to disk size). This was specially clear for A_2 (see the lower panel in Fig. 4.2). This constitutes possible observational evidence for the concurrent increase of the strength and length of bars in time.

Figure 4.2: *Upper panel:* The bar length distribution, relative to the disk isophotal radius $R_{25.5}$, in terms of the galaxy Hubble stage. The blue line indicates the running mean. The standard error of the mean is indicated with an error bar. The green vertical line shows the region of S0s. *Lower panel:* The bar length (normalized to the 25 mag arcsec $^{-2}$ isophotal radius) vs. the $m = 2$ Fourier bar amplitude. The Spearman's rank correlation coefficient and significance are indicated. The color palette indicates the galaxy Hubble type. The straight line displays the linear fit of the cloud of points. Credit: Fig. 11 and Fig. 20 from Díaz-García et al. (2016b) (Paper I).

4.2 Paper II

Using S⁴G 3.6 μm photometry, in Herrera-Endoqui et al. (2015) (Paper II) we measured the lengths, position angles and ellipticities of different stellar structures in the S⁴G sample, like stellar bars, barlenses, and outer/inner/nuclear rings and (ring)lenses. Each of these features were introduced in Sect. 1. This was done combining different methods, namely visual measurements, isophotal analysis, ellipse fitting and also with the aid of unsharp mask images. In addition, pitch angles of spiral arm segments were also measured. Specially relevant in this study is the connection between bars and barlenses.

4.2.1 Link between bars, rings, lenses and barlenses

The different morphological structures were identified by Buta et al. (2015). Based on their morphological classification, we showed that inner and outer rings are most frequent among Sa galaxies ($T = 1$), while the distribution of lenses and ringlenses peaks for S0⁰ galaxies ($T = -2$). This agrees with previous work by Laurikainen et al. (2009, 2013), who found that among early-type lenticulars the ring fraction drops while the frequency of lenses rises. However, we observed a large spread of the sizes across the Hubble sequence. We also showed that inner rings and lenses are more common in weakly-barred and non-barred galaxies. Altogether, as bars are known to be responsible for the formation of the dynamical disk resonances (Sellwood & Wilkinson 1993), these results hint at an heuristic casual relation between the weakening/dissolution of bars and the formation inner rings and lenses (but see discussion in Sect. 5.2).

We found that barlenses are preferentially hosted by strong bars (i.e. bars in SB galaxies) in massive ($M_* > 10^{10}M_\odot$) early-type ($T < 5$) disks. Likewise, nuclear structures (nuclear rings, nuclear lenses and nuclear ringlenses) appeared only when $M_* > 10^{10}M_\odot$, most likely because faint systems lack inner Lindblad resonances due to their low central concentration (e.g. Salo et al. 2015).

The sizes of rings, (ring)lenses and barlenses were normalized to the bar lengths and studied as a function of fundamental galaxy parameters such as M_* (see upper-left panel in Fig. 4.3). Such normalization was aimed to study the link between stellar bars on one side, and rings (dynamical bar resonances) and barlenses (B/P face-on counterpart) on the other. Inner rings presented typical sizes similar to that of the bar (e.g. Laurikainen et al. 2011), confirming their resonant nature (Schwarz 1981), but a fraction of rings were larger. Inner lenses and ringlenses had sizes comparable to inner rings. Besides, the distributions of the lengths of outer rings, outer ringlenses, and outer lenses were quite similar; this suggests that similar physical mechanisms may be responsible for the assembly of these stellar structures. Also, outer features had typical sizes of ~ 2.4 times the bar length, in agreement with previous observational work (e.g. Kormendy & Norman 1979; Laurikainen et al. 2013; Comerón et al. 2014b), providing strong

evidence for their resonant origin (e.g. Buta & Combes 1996) (e.g. for a galaxy with a flat rotation curve and $r_{\text{cor}}/r_{\text{bar}} = 1.4$, the expected ratio of outer Lindblad resonance radius to bar length is 2.4). However, long tails in the distribution of these relative sizes were also found, probably linked to the variability of the ratio between bar length and corotation radius for the different mass size distributions of the galaxies.

Furthermore, we found that the lower the total stellar mass, the larger the sizes of inner features - inner rings and (ring)lenses - relative to the bar length. On average, we found a factor ~ 2 difference between the most massive and the faintest systems. This is in principle a counterintuitive trend, as enlarged central mass concentrations (common for largest M_*) are expected to push the 1/4 UHR further out (e.g. analytical work by Contopoulos 1980), where the gas piles up to form inner rings (e.g. Schwarz 1984). Likewise, as the bar corotation radius increases with increasing mass, bars tend to follow it and that should increase the outer resonance radii. This behavior of inner features as a function of M_* and r_{bar} could also imply that low-mass galaxies typically present slower bars (i.e. larger $r_{\text{cor}}/r_{\text{bar}}$) than the more massive counterparts, under the assumption of a similar rotation curve shape. However, the sizes of outer features, relative to the bar, do not show any clear trend versus M_* . Other fundamental parameters and physical mechanisms might also be responsible for the observed trends, as we discuss in Sect 5.2.

We also found that the length of barlenses tightly correlates with the length of the stellar bars (upper-right panel in Fig. 4.3). This implies a strong coupling between both structures. On the contrary, for the nuclear features, no connection with bars was found in relation to their sizes (but the low resolution of the S⁴G images might be an issue here).

Finally, we also analyzed the sizes of the various stellar features as a function of the disk scalelength (h_{R} , from Salo et al. 2015). This allowed us to extend the analysis to non-barred systems. The sizes of the outer, inner and nuclear structures (normalized to h_{R}), occupied distinct regions when studied as a function of the total stellar mass (lower panels in Fig. 4.3). Despite the considerable scatter, their average values were constant vs. M_* , for strongly-, weakly- and non-barred galaxies. An interesting trend was found when the sizes of barlenses (relative to h_{R}) were plotted versus M_* in the same family bins: while barlenses gradually disappeared for weakly- and non-barred galaxies, their locii in the plot was occupied by inner lenses. This might imply an evolutionary track between barlenses and some inner lenses.

Figure 4.3: *Upper-left panel:* The sizes of various stellar structures normalized to the length of the bars as a function of the total stellar mass of the host galaxy (left) and its morphological type (right). Black symbols represent barlenses. With blue, green and red symbols we plot outer, inner and nuclear features (rings, ringlenses and lenses), respectively. The green solid line shows the statistically significant linear fit for the inner structures. The black dashed line corresponds to the (non-significant) linear fit for barlenses. *Upper-right panel:* The size of barlenses vs. the size of the stellar bars (black filled circles), both given in physical units. The black line corresponds to the linear fit between these two parameters, forcing it to start at $(x, y) = (0, 0)$. The red circles correspond to the measured sizes of nuclear stellar structures: nuclear rings, nuclear lenses and nuclear ringlenses. *Lower panels:* The same as in the upper-left panel, but normalizing the sizes of the structures by the disk scalelength and binning the sample in terms of the galaxy family (as classified in Buta et al. 2015). Credit: Fig.10, Fig.12, and Fig. 11 from Herrera-Endoqui et al. (2015) (Paper II).

4.3 Paper III

In Seidel et al. (2015a)(Paper III) we obtained high-resolution (~ 100 pc) kinematic maps of the stellar and ionised gas components of a subsample of 16 early- and intermediate-type S⁴G barred galaxies (including S0s). These galaxies are very rich in stellar substructures (see Table 4.1) according to Buta et al. (2015). Observations were done with the SAURON integral field unit (IFU) (Bacon et al. 2001), sampling the bar region and extending somewhat further in the disk. Stellar and gas kinematics were extracted using the pPXF (Cappellari & Emsellem 2004) and GANDALF (Sarzi et al. 2006; Falc3n-Barroso et al. 2006) codes, respectively.

4.3.1 Bar-imprint in the galaxy kinematics

Radial (v_{rad}) and tangential (v_{tan}) velocities were inferred from the kinematic maps following the recipe by Maciejewski et al. (2012). From these, we defined a new measurement of the bar-induced perturbation strength (the kinematic bar torque):

$$Q_{\text{kin}} = \frac{\max(v_{\text{rad}}(R))}{\langle |v_{\text{tan},R}| \rangle}, \quad (4.1)$$

where first we identified the radius of maximum v_{rad} (numerator), and then we determined the mean v_{tan} in a ring around this radius (denominator). We found that Q_{kin} derived from the gas kinematics was ~ 2.5 larger than Q_{kin} derived from the stars. This is not unexpected, as the gas is more responsive to non-asymmetries. We also found a very tight correlation between the photometric torque (Q_{b}) and the kinematic torque (upper panel in Fig. 4.4). The latter finding was backed up by a set of N-body simulations (following Martinez-Valpuesta et al. 2006) with different disc-to-total mass ratios, which were treated in the same fashion as the observational data.

Kinematic position angles were determined following Barrera-Ballesteros et al. (2014). In general, in the disk region covered by the SAURON field-of-view, the kinematic major axes were constant versus galactocentric radius and no twists in the line-of-nodes were observed. Likewise, the kinematic major axes of the gas and stellar velocity fields were similar, independently of the bar strength, and both of them were close to the photometric PA. This means that bars do not have a strong influence in the global kinematics of their host galaxies in our sample, despite the local bar-imprint presented before and a few misalignments that we associated to galaxy interactions ¹.

¹Within the S⁴G subsample used in this paper, only NGC 4394 and NGC 5350 were cataloged as galaxies showing signs of interaction by Knapen et al. (2014). They were classified as systems with minor distortion of the disks or minor tidal features. Besides, Vollmer et al. (2005) tentatively proposed the lenticular galaxy NGC 4262 to had a rapid and close encounter with NGC 4254 ~ 280 Myr ago.

4.3.2 Rotation curves and velocity dispersions

About 60% of the galaxies in the sample showed the so-called double-humped rotation curves (inner local maximum and dip before the curve continues to rise), which are kinematic signatures of B/P shapes in edge-on galaxies shown in the N-body simulations of bar-unstable disks by Bureau & Athanassoula (2005). A similar fraction of galaxies presented σ -drops - inner humps in the velocity dispersion radial profiles - which is another kinematic feature observed in simulation models of barred galaxies (e.g. Wozniak et al. 2003). Despite our poor statistics, we found an apparent dependence between the strength of the bar (Q_b) and the relative depth/strength of the σ -drops and double humps, both in the stellar and gaseous component. The latter was measured from the difference between the inner maximum and subsequent dip, normalized by the maximum V or σ .

Furthermore, we quantified the bar-driven radial motions by analyzing the radial gradients of the stellar velocity dispersion. For $\sim 1/3$ of the sample, the σ profiles along the bar major axis showed somewhat higher values in the central parts, compared to σ along the minor axis. Also, this was the case when profiles were calculated using the photometric isophotes. However, this yield a lower σ along the bar major axis in the outer parts of the SAURON mosaics, compared to the minor-axis (where the dispersion of the bulge is dominant). Finally, we observed that the outer gradient of the σ profiles of the stars tended to be smaller for stronger bars. This implies that strongly barred galaxies seem to produce flatter stellar velocity dispersions in the disk (see further discussion in Sect. 5.4.2).

We derived and analyzed the Gauss-Hermite moments h_3 and h_4 . No bar pattern was clear in them at the first sight, and no kinematic feature of B/P bulges in h_4 was found, as predicted from numerical simulations (e.g. Debattista et al. 2005). For a large fraction of galaxies we observed a slight anticorrelation of h_3 with the stellar velocity. We studied the trends between h_3 and V/σ within apertures determined by the bar size: $r \in (0.13, 0.5, 1) \cdot r_{\text{bar}}$. We found that the smaller the aperture, the tighter the anticorrelation for about 50 % of the cases. Interestingly, most of those galaxies have been confirmed to host central stellar structures such as barlenses and nuclear (ring)lenses. In addition, larger σ were associated to larger h_4 in the spaxels within the central regions of the bar. Occasionally, high h_4 values accompanied central velocity σ -drops.

4.3.3 Stellar angular momentum

In order to quantify the rotation versus pressure supported motions across the disk, we calculated the stellar angular momentum (λ_R) following the method prescribed in Emsellem et al. (2007):

$$\lambda_R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_p} F_i R_i |V_i|}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_p} F_i R_i \sqrt{V_i^2 + \sigma_i^2}}, \quad (4.2)$$

Galaxy	Classification	Galaxy	Classification
NGC 1015	(R')SB(r,bl)0/a	NGC 2543	SAB(s,bl)b
NGC 2712	(R')SAB(rs,nl)ab	NGC 2859	(R)SABa(rl,bl,nl,nb)0 ⁺
NGC 2893	(R ₁ L)SAB(l)0/a	NGC 2962	(R)SABa(rl)0 ⁺
NGC 3485	SAB(rs)bc	NGC 3504	(R1')SAB(rs,nl)a
NGC 4245	(RL)SB(r,bl,nrl)0 ⁺	NGC 4262	(L)SBA(l,bl)0 ^{-/0}
NGC 4267	(L)SAB0 ⁻	NGC 4394	(RL)SB(rs,bl,nl)0/a
NGC 4643	(L)SB(rs,bl,nl)0 ^{0/+}	NGC 5350	SB(rs)ab
NGC 5375	(R')SBA(rs,bl)ab	NGC 5701	(R ₁ ')SAB(rl,bl)0/a

Table 4.1: The sample of galaxies in Paper III and its morphological classification from Buta et al. (2015).

where F_i refers to the flux, R_i is the circular radius, V_i corresponds to the velocity and σ_i is the velocity dispersion in each of the N_p spatial bins. We also studied the radial profiles of λ_R normalized to the bar size, finding a systematic dip at $0.2 \pm 0.1 r_{\text{bar}}$ (bottom panel in Fig. 4.4).

The scaling of the dip radius with the bar length might imply that the kinematic feature is linked to the bar resonances, most likely the ILR. Altogether, these kinematic features could indicate the presence of inner stellar components (inner disks or pseudobulges) made out gas funneled by bars (a more thorough discussion is done in Sect 5.4.2). Moreover, we integrated λ_R within one effective radius (R_e), named as λ_{R_e} . We found that λ_{R_e} increased with increasing bar strength. However, this is probably related to the strong dependence between Q_b and the Hubble-type (Paper I), because the late-type galaxies in our galaxy are faster rotators within R_e than the earlier-type galaxies (that encompass a smaller fraction of the disk, and hence less angular momentum, inside R_e).

Figure 4.4: *Upper panel:* The kinematic torque (Q_{kin}) vs. the photometric torque (Q_b) for a subsample of 10 S^4G galaxies. The dotted line shows a one-to-one correlation. Colors indicate T . The Pearson correlation coefficient (0.83) is indicated. *Lower panel:* λ_R profiles as a function of the galactocentric radius, normalized to the size of the bar, for the whole sample in Paper III. Credit: Fig. 10 and Fig. 12 from Seidel et al. (2015b) (Paper III).

4.4 Paper IV

In Erroz-Ferrer et al. (2016) (Paper IV) we used high-resolution H_α Fabry–Perot kinematics to study the inner parts of the rotation curves of a subsample of 29 S⁴G disk galaxies with a large spread in morphological types. The data was obtained with the GH α FaS instrument at the William Herschel Telescope, achieving high angular (~ 1 arcsec sampling, seeing limited) and spectral (~ 8 km/s sampling) resolutions. The reader is referred to Erroz-Ferrer et al. (2015) for details on the data reduction and how the velocity maps and rotation curves (RC) were inferred.

Rotation curves were corrected for asymmetric drift. However, this effect was negligible in the central parts for most of the galaxies in the sample. We also used contaminant-free stellar mass maps (from Querejeta et al. 2015) to calculate the stellar contribution to the circular velocity, and various bar parameters to study any possible connection between stellar bars and the inner shape of the galactic potential well. Here, the most relevant result was the confirmation of the coupling between the inner velocity gradient and the central stellar density.

4.4.1 Relation between the inner velocity gradient and the disk parameters

Following Lelli et al. (2013), we performed a polynomial fitting to the inner parts of the RC (up to the radius where it reaches 90% of the maximum velocity) and used the linear term to estimate the inner slope, $d_{\text{R}v_c}(0)$. We also calculated μ_0 from the ellipse fitting to the 3.6 μm images performed by Muñoz-Mateos et al. (2015). μ_0 was obtained extrapolating the luminosity profile in the inner few arcseconds to the galaxy center, correcting for inclination.

For the early-type galaxies with a substantial central mass component, μ_0 was obtained by summing the inclination-corrected extrapolated disk central surface brightness and the bulge central surface brightness. The disk μ_0 was obtained via an exponential fit to the outer parts of the luminosity profile, while the bulge μ_0 was extrapolated from a Sersic fit to the inner parts after subtracting the disc contribution.

We confirmed the scaling relation reported by Lelli et al. (2013): the inner slope of the rotation curve correlates with the central surface brightness of the galaxy (see left column of Fig. 4.5). However, a larger scatter in this relationship was found, perhaps due to the more patchy H_α emission compared to H I. A tighter correlation with μ_0 was shown when we used the inner slope of the stellar component of the circular velocity, $d_{\text{R}v_*}(0)$, and a very similar scaling relation was found.

Both $d_{\text{R}v_c}(0)$ and $d_{\text{R}v_*}(0)$ increased towards earlier Hubble types. More massive systems (larger maximum velocity amplitudes) had steeper inner slopes, while fainter systems showed shallower slopes. This is likely to be a consequence of the larger central mass concentration of disk galaxies across the Hubble sequence to-

wards the earliest-types. This manifests in larger bulge-to-total ratios, and hence bulge masses, for earlier-types and more massive galaxies. Indeed, the inner velocity gradient was found to correlate with the bulge-to-total mass ratio and with the bulge stellar mass.

$d_{Rv_*}(0)$ tightly correlates with M_* (and thus with the maximum circular velocity), T and the bulge-to-total. This is shown in Fig. 4.6 for the non-highly inclined galaxies ($i < 65^\circ$) in S⁴G sample, instead of the reduced sample shown in Paper IV.

In Paper I we showed a correlation between $d_{Rv_*}(0)$ and the bar strength and length. A mild dependence of the $d_{Rv_c}(0)$ on the various bar parameters was found. It seemed that longer bars, relative to the disk size, appear in galaxies with steeper central velocity gradients. Likewise, $d_{Rv_c}(0)$ showed a positive (negative) scaling with A_2 (Q_b). However, given the weak statistics and trends, it is hard to conclude that there is any casual connection between the central kinematic mass and the stellar bars, which are expected to be active agents controlling the central gas density (and hence, the star formation activity).

Unlike in the study by Lelli et al. (2014), who found a dependence of the inner velocity gradient on the SFR surface density (ΣSFR , normalized by the area in physical units) for a sample of gas-rich dwarfs, we did not find any dependence of the inner slope on either SFR or ΣSFR . This can imply that for our sample of galaxies there is no direct coupling between the central kinematic mass and the rate of supernova explosions, which is expected to affect the central baryonic density (e.g. Dekel & Silk 1986) and also the central dark matter content (e.g. Pontzen & Governato 2012). The lack of this correlation in our galaxies might also be explained by presence of various central stellar components, contributing to the steepness of the RC, that do not present ongoing star formation.

Figure 4.5: *Upper panels:* The inner slope of the circular velocity curve, $d_{Rv_c}(0)$, as a function of the central surface brightness (left) and the galaxy Hubble stage (right). The dashed line corresponds to the scaling relation from Lelli et al. (2013). Different symbols and colors correspond to different T-type bins, as indicated in the legend. The red upward-pointing arrows correspond to galaxies whose rotation curves were not fully sampled in the inner regions, implying that the measurements give only a lower limit to $d_{Rv_c}(0)$. For those outliers, the red crosses give the evaluated value using the scaling relation in Lelli et al. (2013). *Lower panels:* The same as above but using the stellar contribution to the circular velocity, derived from the gravitational potential at $3.6 \mu\text{m}$, instead of the Fabry-Perot H_α kinematics. Credit: Fig. 5 from Erroz-Ferrer et al. (2016) (Paper IV).

Figure 4.6: The inner slope of the stellar component of the rotation curve as a function of global galaxy parameters, for more than ~ 1100 disk galaxies with inclinations lower than 65° . From left to right and top to bottom, we plot $d_{R^*}v_*(0)$ versus the total stellar mass (from Muñoz-Mateos et al. 2015), the Hubble stage (from Buta et al. 2015), the maximum of the disk component of the circular velocity, and the bulge-to-total mass ratio (from Salo et al. 2015). For the first panel and those in the lower row, the color palette is defined based on T , and barred and unbarred galaxies are plotted with filled and empty circles, respectively. In the upper-right panel, the blue line indicates the running mean of $d_{R^*}v_*(0)$, while the red line corresponds to the linear fit done in Paper IV for a small subsample of S⁴G galaxies.

4.5 Paper V

In Díaz-García et al. (2016a) (Paper V) we calculated 1-D average stellar density radial profiles (Σ_*) and 2-D average bars, in bins of total stellar mass (M_* , from Muñoz-Mateos et al. 2015) and morphology (T and family, from Buta et al. 2015), using 3.6 μm photometry for the S⁴G and following the methodology described in Sect. 3.9 and Sect. 3.10. We also averaged the $m = 2$ amplitudes (A_2) and the stellar contribution to the circular velocity ($V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}$) in disk galaxies. These mean images and profiles, together with their dispersion, constitute a useful observational constraint for numerical models of galaxy formation and evolution. In this paper we provided observational evidence for the role of bars driving the secular evolution of galactic disks.

4.6 1-D average stellar density profiles

For all the M_* and T bins, the average stellar density profiles decayed exponentially down to at least $\sim 10M_\odot\text{pc}^{-2}$ (see upper left panel in Fig. 4.8), which is the luminosity threshold beyond which uncertainties associated to the depth of the images and the limited field-of-view reduced the reliability of our statistics. We showed that the extrapolated central stellar density and the scalelength of the disk stacks correlated with M_* .

We also showed that central mass concentrations in massive systems are larger than in fainter systems. This was done by rescaling images with respect to h_R , and analyzing the deviation from an exponential slope in the inner parts of disk stacks. Specifically, for $M_* \geq 10^{10}M_\odot$, the central stellar density was $\sim 6 - 10$ times that extrapolated from the disk. For galaxies of intermediate masses ($10^9M_\odot < M_* < 10^{10}M_\odot$) this difference dropped to a factor $\sim 2 - 3$, and for fainter systems the radial luminosity profile scarcely deviated from an exponential disk.

The stellar mass distribution of S⁴G galaxies was also characterized from the shape of the mean disk(+bulge) component of the rotation curve. The maximum velocity and inner gradient of the mean $V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}$ scaled with M_* and T (thus, with the bulge-to-total ratio). Galaxies with $T < 5$ had similar maximum velocities ($V_{3.6\mu\text{m}}^{\text{max}} \approx 120 - 130 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), and their inner slopes increased with decreasing Hubble stage (as B/T becomes larger).

4.6.1 Mean Σ_* for barred and non-barred galaxies

For a fixed stellar mass interval ($M_* \geq 10^9M_\odot$), we found a significant difference in the average stellar density profiles of barred and unbarred galaxies. Namely, barred galaxies had disks with larger scalelengths, fainter extrapolated central surface brightnesses and larger central mass concentrations than their non-barred counterparts (Fig. 4.8). This was observed among early- and late-type systems.

Figure 4.7: 2-D bar stacks as a function of T (upper row) and the galaxy family (lower row). Credit: Fig. 2 from Díaz-García et al. (2016, IAU321 proceedings).

For $T \leq 5$, barred galaxies were almost a factor of 2 more centrally concentrated than unbarred galaxies. Moreover, we found that the mean Σ_* of barred and unbarred systems (in a given M_* interval) intersected each other slightly after the mean bar length, most likely at corotation. As a matter of fact, r_{cor} is the radius beyond which bars are expected to push material outwards according to numerical simulations (e.g. Athanassoula 2013).

We studied the mean A_2 as a function of the galactocentric radius, normalized to the isophotal radius $R_{25.5}$, for both barred and non-barred galaxies. As expected (Paper I), the mean A_2 was largest at the bar region for SB and SAB systems, and non-barred galaxies had low amplitudes of A_2 without any clear peak within the typical bar region (relative to $R_{25.5}$). It is noteworthy that, for $0 \leq T < 5$, also outside the typical bar region A_2 tended to be larger among barred galaxies, compared to the non-barred systems; and strongly barred galaxies presented larger amplitudes beyond r_{bar} than weakly barred galaxies. In principle, this indicates that bars play a role in the development of other stellar non-axisymmetries (e.g. spirals) in the disk, or that stellar disks which are reactive tend to form bars in their inner parts.

4.7 2-D stacked stellar bars

Bars stacks comprising lenticular galaxies were oval-shaped. A qualitative analysis of the average bars showed that early- and intermediate-type spirals ($0 \leq T < 5$) have intrinsically narrower bars than later types (Fig. 4.7). Nevertheless, bulges and barlenses rounded off the bar shape in the inner parts for the earliest types.

We also studied the azimuthally averaged luminosity profiles of the bar stacks.

We showed that bars in early- and late-type systems tend to be flat and exponential, respectively, relative to the underlying disk. This agrees with the classical result by Elmegreen & Elmegreen (1985). When cuts along the bar major axis were considered, the bar hump was clear for all the bins.

We performed a Fourier decomposition of the bar stacks and calculated the gravitational potentials. We showed that stacks comprising early-type galaxies are characterized by larger $m = 2$ and $m = 4$ Fourier density amplitudes and weaker non-centrally peaking gravitational tangential-to-radial force radial profiles. This strengthens the conclusions in Paper I that were based on measurements on individual galaxies.

We performed ellipse fitting on the bar stacks and studied the resulting ϵ and b_4 radial profiles. ϵ presented a monotonic growth until a maximum was reached close to r_{bar} (e.g. Martin 1995). However, among the faintest systems ϵ tended to peak at inner radii. For $T < 5$, b_4 showed a hump in the inner parts of the bar, and dropped after the radius of maximum ellipticity. For spiral galaxies, b_4 became negative right after r_{bar} . Among early-type galaxies, we found that the stronger the bars that we co-added, the more disk-like (based on b_4) the isophotes of the inner stellar structures in the stack were.

We also binned the sample based on galaxy family (AB/AB/AB/B) and confirmed the good agreement between the different quantitative estimates of the bar strength ($m = 2$ Fourier amplitudes, ellipticity and tangential-to-radial forces) and the galaxy family.

Figure 4.8: *Upper panels:* Average surface brightness profiles as a function of the total stellar mass (left). The solid (dashed) lines trace Σ_* within the radial range with a 100% (75%) sample coverage. In the right panel we show the M_* -binned mean Σ_* for barred (solid lines) and non-barred (dashed lines) systems (90% coverage). The vertical dotted lines indicate the mean bar size (from PAPER II) of the barred galaxies in each of the M_* -bins. *Lower panels:* Mean Σ_* profiles of barred and non-barred galaxies, splitting the sample into early- and late-type systems (left). With the same binning, in the right panel we show the deviation from an exponential disk (Σ_*^{exp}) within the central regions of the average Σ_* (relative to h_R). Credit: Fig. 1 from Díaz-García et al. (2016, IAU321 proceedings).

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.1 Coupling of stellar and dark matter within the disk

In Paper I we obtained an estimate of the halo-to-stellar mass ratio within the optical disk for non-highly inclined S⁴G galaxies. The shape of the running median of the $M_h/M_* - M_*$ relation agreed with the best-fit model at $z \approx 0$ from abundance matching and halo occupation distribution methods (e.g. Moster et al. 2010; Behroozi et al. 2010; Guo et al. 2010; Leauthaud et al. 2012). This means that present-day galaxies tend to keep in memory the mass of their host (sub)halos, where the gas cooled down to form them, even inside the optical disk (i.e., $\sim 10\%$ of the halo virial radius). This reinforces the idea that dark matter and baryonic matter are intimately coupled in disk galaxies.

However, the $M_h/M_* - M_*$ relation showed a large scatter. Part of this scatter might be due to observation uncertainties of the H I line width, like the inclination correction or the presence of perturbed or truncated gas disks, specially among gas-poor early-type galaxies (e.g. Comerón et al. 2014a). It can also arise from the assumption that the gas component is negligible at the optical radius, that might not be true for the faintest systems. In individual galaxies, the scatter can be a consequence of a non accurately estimated M/L at $3.6 \mu\text{m}$, the impact of non-stellar contaminants (e.g. Querejeta et al. 2015), or a radially varying M/L (e.g. Portinari & Salucci 2010). Besides, our definition of $M_h/M_*(< R_{\text{opt}})$ (Eq. 3.7) can be oversimplified.

Nonetheless, part of the scatter in the $M_h/M_* - M_*$ relation may also have a physical origin, related to the evolution of a galaxy in a lifetime. Since their birth, galaxy undergo several changes that have an external origin (e.g. Kormendy & Kennicutt 2004). Their present-day mass distribution is affected by past violent processes like galaxy mergers, RAM-pressure or gas stripping. Environmental secular (slower) phases such as minor mergers, gas inflow, or galaxy harassment, also play a fundamental role in the evolution of galaxies. All these processes

together, combined with star formation and gas recycling, star formation and AGN feedback, are expected to make the halo-to-stellar mass ratio varying to a certain degree in a cosmic time.

Figure 5.1: *Left panel:* Mean stellar contribution to the circular velocity for the different M_* -bins (Paper V). *Right panel:* The central value of the M_* -bins vs. the mean $M_h/M_*(< R_{\text{opt}})$ (filled circles). Like in Fig. 4.1, the different lines correspond to estimates in the literature for the total halo-to-stellar mass ratio vs. M_* , scaled down by a factor 0.04, showing good agreement with our estimate.

In Fig. 5.1 we show the average disk(+bulge) component of the rotation curve in bins of M_* , from Paper V. Together with the mean stellar density profiles, these curves (and their dispersion) are an observational constraint for galaxy formation models to be checked against, and may constitute a useful tool to quantify the amount of dark matter within the optical disk that exists in present-day galaxies. From these mean rotation curves, following the methodology described in Sect. 3.8.2 and using the mean H I velocity amplitudes, we inferred the mean $M_h/M_*(< R_{\text{opt}})$. We reassessed the relation between the halo-to-stellar mass ratio and M_* , successfully reproducing the slope expected from Λ CDM cosmological simulations (right panel of Fig. 5.1).

Our first-order rotation curve decomposition models (Paper I) implied that only $\sim 10\%$ of the non-highly inclined galaxies in the S⁴G fulfilled

$$V_{\text{disk}}/V_{\text{total}}(2.2h_R) > 0.85, \quad (5.1)$$

which is the commonly used criterion that establishes if a disk is maximal (Sackett 1997). Nevertheless, despite the photometric and kinematic constraints considered in the decompositions, the use of universal rotation curve models and the applied methodology might have biased these results. In fact, counterexamples to the universal rotation curve have been shown in the literature (e.g. Verheijen 1997) (see also the discussion in Bosma 1998; Salucci et al. 2007). A more careful up-to-date assessment of the maximality of disks has been done in Martinsson et al. (2013), where the 30 spiral galaxies for which a more precise decomposition of the rotation curve was done turned out to be submaximal.

The most direct proof of the link between baryonic and dark matter in disk galaxies is the Tully-Fisher relation (Tully & Fisher 1977). Using H_α kinematics, in Paper IV we provided more insight into the interplay between stellar and dark matter by confirming the scaling relation between the inner slope of the rotation curve and the central surface brightness of the galaxy (Lelli et al. 2013). This scaling relation links the inner shape of the potential well to the central stellar density, which is to a major extent governed by gas accretion, star formation and feedback. Among the bright systems, Lelli (2014) and Lelli et al. (2016) found that this trend can be explained with a model for disk galaxies that lacks dark matter in the central regions. By computing the inner slope of the stellar component of the rotation curve, in Paper IV we confirmed that the baryonic mass seems to dominate the dynamics in the inner regions. This also manifests in the dependence of the inner velocity gradient on the bulge-to-total and bulge mass of the host galaxies.

5.2 Two distinct groups of disks and bars

Two clearly distinct types of disks, and thereby bars, are found across the Hubble sequence. Galaxies in early-type, $T \in [-3, 5)$, and late-type systems, $T \in [5, 10]$, present significantly different structural and kinematic properties, discussed in this section. The same differences are found when splitting the S⁴G sample with a M_* cut-off at $10^{10} M_\odot$.

In Paper V, we discussed that early-type systems ($T < 5$ or $M_* > 10^{10} M_\odot$) present bulges, whereas in later-types the central mass concentrations are substantially reduced or have no central concentrations at all. In fact, for morphological types later than Sc, most of the galaxies were bulge-less disks (e.g. Salo et al. 2015). Additionally, central stellar structures such as barlenses and nuclear bars, rings and (ring)lenses, were identified only in galaxies with total stellar masses larger than $10^{10} M_\odot$ (Paper II).

In Paper I we found that systems with morphological types later than \sim Sc are more dark matter dominated within the optical disk than the earlier types, what most likely affects the disk stability properties. In fact, in the study by Cervantes Sodi et al. (2015) the fraction of bars was lower for larger halo-to-stellar mass ratios, providing observational evidence for the role of halos inhibiting the bar formation (e.g. Hohl 1976). However, other properties like the gas fraction or the halo triaxiality are known to play an important role in the formation and evolution of bars (e.g. Athanassoula et al. 2013). When the bars were identified visually, we did not find any strong dependence of the bar fraction on either M_* or M_h/M_* . These trends were more evident when the detection of bars was based on Fourier decomposition and ellipse fitting methods, that reduced the bar fraction by a factor ~ 2 for $T \geq 5$, making clear the peculiar nature of late-type bars. Then, the bar fraction was found to drop for $M_* < 10^{9.5-10}$ and to decrease with increasing $M_h/M_*(< R_{\text{opt}})$.

Based on the study of tangential-to-radial forces at the bar region, we found that the later-types presented the largest Q_b values (e.g. Laurikainen et al. 2004b). Q_b decreased towards earlier-types due to the dilution of tangential forces by bulges and bars, which are prominent in the S0s and early-type spirals. For the sample of early-type galaxies considered in Paper III, we also showed that the bar-induced kinematic perturbation of the gas and stellar components monotonically increased with increasing T . Because of the more prominent dark matter halos of the late-type galaxies, the dilution of Q_b by halos, tested in Paper I, was $\sim 20 - 25\%$ for $T \geq 5$. Besides, we found that the halo-correction of the tangential-to-radial forces at the end of the bar was $30 - 50\%$ for the latest-type galaxies.

Other bar parameters studied in Paper I revealed the distinct nature of early- and late-type bars. For instance, in late-type systems, the mean bar size (relative to the disk) anticorrelated with M_* , whereas in early-type systems massive disks typically hosted longer bars. When $T < 5$, bars had larger amplitudes in the higher order even Fourier components (e.g. Ohta et al. 1990). Besides, based on the analysis of bar stacks in Paper V, we showed that bars in early-type spirals are intrinsically thinner than in the later types. Moreover, only among the early-types the radial profiles of ϵ and b_4 showed a well-defined trend (Papers I and V), with a bar enhancement and a declining trend in the outskirts. Bars in early-type galaxies were also characterized by flatter azimuthally averaged surface brightness profiles (e.g. Elmegreen & Elmegreen 1985). The bar stacks in Paper V constitute a non-parametric constraint for N-body models of barred galaxies to be compared with.

In Paper II we also found that the fainter the galaxies, the larger the sizes of the inner rings and (rings)lenses, relative to the bar length. We shed light on this by comparing our results with those reported by Salo et al. (1999), who used a 2-D sticky particle simulation (gas response to a rigidly rotating potential) to model the morphology and kinematics of the weakly-barred multiringed galaxy IC 4214, which has a similar stellar mass as the Milky Way. For a given bar pattern speed, the authors found that the shape of rings varied when the nominal bar amplitude was modified by a factor A . When A is decreased, the dark matter halo component is enlarged to account for the observed rotation curve of this galaxy. Salo et al. (1999) found that the inner rings increased ($\sim 10\%$) when the nominal bar amplitude was substantially reduced. This is consistent with our observations of inner rings (normalized to bar) getting larger with reduced M_* , because the halo contribution among fainter systems is known to be larger (e.g. Paper I; Courteau & Dutton 2015). However, other resonant structures in Paper II did not fulfill the expectations from these models, making clear that other fundamental parameters (e.g. gas fraction) need to be considered.

5.3 Secular evolution of stellar bars

Simulation models predict that stellar bars become longer, narrower and stronger (larger A_2^{\max}) in time as they trap particles from the disk and lose angular momentum (e.g. Athanassoula 2003). In Paper I we found possible observational evidence for the growth of bars in a cosmic time. The length of stellar bars correlated with their strength (for all bar strength indexes), more tightly among early- and intermediate-type spirals (S0/a-Sc). The correlation was very clear for A_2^{\max} (e.g. Elmegreen et al. 2007a), which is the most common proxy of the bar strength used in numerical simulations. Also, in Paper I and Paper IV we checked that bars with larger A_2^{\max} and sizes (relative to the disk) are typically hosted by galaxies with larger inner velocity gradients. These are indeed systems that evolve faster, given their bigger central densities (e.g. Elmegreen et al. 2007a).

Furthermore, in Paper I we showed that bars in S0/a-Sab galaxies had longer bars (in physical units and relative to the disk) than the Sb-Sc systems (e.g. Laurikainen et al. 2007). Likewise, bars in early-type spirals have larger $m = 2$ Fourier amplitudes than their intermediate-type counterparts. This is consistent with a plausible transition of galaxies across this sector of the Hubble sequence, as their bars grow. In fact, intermediate-type spiral galaxies are candidates to evolve secularly towards earlier types as they strip off their gas (Kormendy 2013).

N-body simulations have shown that the central parts of the bar thicken during its evolution (e.g. Combes & Sanders 1981) as a consequence of the buckling instability (e.g. Raha et al. 1991) or vertical resonance heating (e.g. Combes et al. 1990). These puffed-up material create B/P bulges, often seen in edge-on barred galaxies (Jarvis 1986). Strong evidence suggesting that barlenses are B/P bulges in face-on view has been provided (Laurikainen et al. 2007, 2014; Athanassoula et al. 2015). The last interpretation is reinforced by the tight correlation between the sizes of barlenses and bars that we found in Paper II. Moreover, barlenses were more frequently identified in strongly barred galaxies. This is most likely related to the connection between the prominence of B/P bulges and strength of bars in the simulations by Athanassoula (2005).

Unlike nuclear and outer stellar substructures, inner rings and lenses in Paper II appeared preferentially in weakly-barred and non-barred systems. This finding points towards an unknown mechanism that make some bars to dissolve into axisymmetric substructures (e.g. Kormendy 1979), although bars in simulation models are very difficult to destroy (e.g. Athanassoula 2003; Athanassoula et al. 2013), unless the disc is extremely gas-rich (e.g. Bournaud & Combes 2002). In addition, we found that the distribution of the sizes of inner lenses among weakly- or non-barred galaxies, studied as a function of the host disk mass and size simultaneously, was very similar to that of the barlenses among the strongly barred galaxies. This suggests that an important number of the inner lenses that we observe might have been previously barlenses (Laurikainen et al. 2013), that is, they might be naked B/P bulges in which the outer part of the bar has dissolved. However,

this would only account for a fraction of them because not all inner lenses show similar sizes as barlenses. This interpretation is not yet studied by simulations. Mechanisms explaining the creation of larger inner lenses could possibly be minor mergers (e.g. Eliche-Moral et al. 2012). Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that the temporary weakening of the outer thin component of bars had been witnessed in the high-resolution numerical models by Martinez-Valpuesta & Shlosman (2004) and Martinez-Valpuesta et al. (2006) as a consequence of the buckling(s) of the bar (see Fig. 1.11 in this thesis). Also, analytical work by Patsis et al. (2002) describes a formation mechanism for B/P bulges without the presence any elongated outer bar component.

5.4 Bar-driven secular evolution of disks

Simulation models predict that bars participate in the redistribution of stars and gas inside the galactic disks (e.g. Athanassoula 2013) by pushing them outwards or inwards, depending on whether they are beyond or within the corotation resonance radius. Bars are expected to cause the radial spread of the disk (e.g. Hohl 1971; Athanassoula & Misiriotis 2002; Debattista et al. 2006; Minchev et al. 2011; Athanassoula 2012) and to increase the central mass concentration after the bar-funneled cold gas is turned into stars (e.g. Athanassoula 1992a; Wada & Habe 1992). Here, we present observational evidence for the role of stellar bars causing the growth and secular evolution of disk galaxies, that is independent of any decomposition technique, based on the analysis of photometric and kinematic data.

5.4.1 Photometric signatures

In Paper V we showed that, for a given stellar mass bin, barred galaxies have disks with larger scalelengths and fainter extrapolated central surface brightnesses than the non-barred systems. Besides, the mean 1-D surface brightness profiles of barred and non-barred systems intersected each other slightly beyond the mean bar size, most likely at the bar corotation. This proves the effect of bars causing the disk growth.

Among early-type systems ($0 \leq T < 5$), we also found that the normalized $m = 2$ Fourier amplitudes of the spiral arms are on average larger for barred systems than for non-barred galaxies. Likewise, the amplitude of non-axisymmetries beyond the bar radius were more pronounced for the strongly barred galaxies than for the weakly barred ones. This is consistent with bar being drivers of spiral density waves (e.g. Salo et al. 2010).

The distribution of the sizes of the outer and inner rings and lenses as a function of the bar length, shown in Paper II, was consistent with their resonant origin, that is, they mainly formed through secular evolution via rearrangement of cold gas by non-axisymmetric structures (e.g. Buta & Combes 1996). More specif-

ically, they most likely formed from the gas piled up in the 1/4 ultraharmonic resonance (e.g. Schwarz 1981) and in the outer Lindblad resonance (e.g. Athanassoula et al. 1982). However, long tails in their distributions were shown, therefore other mechanisms might as well be responsible for the formation of some rings.

In Paper V we also showed that barred galaxies present larger central mass concentrations (almost a factor 2 for early-type systems) than their non-barred counterparts. In addition, somewhat larger mass concentrations were found for strongly barred galaxies. This shows the high efficiency of (strong) bars driving material towards the inner kpc (Sellwood & Wilkinson 1993). Part of this central mass concentration might be contributed by barlenses, which are more prominent in strongly barred galaxies. However, the differences between barred and non-barred galaxies in terms of central density remained even when barlens hosts (in Buta et al. 2015) were excluded from the sample.

Our results seem to agree with the recent studies of the stellar populations in bulges by Seidel et al. (2015a), who determined that at least 50% of their stars formed 12 Gyr ago, consistent with an early starburst-collapse phase in their formation (e.g. Obreja et al. 2013). Seidel et al. (2015a) also found a younger component ($\sim 1 - 8$ Gyr) which is likely to be associated to a secular phase driven by bars. Indeed, in Paper V we showed that even the mean Σ_* of unbarred galaxies were characterized by a substantial central mass concentration, suggesting that secular evolution and the presence of B/P/barlens bulges can not account for the formation of bulges alone. However, our results also indicate that hierarchical merging or clump migration at high redshift are not sufficient mechanisms to explain the observations either: otherwise, the mean central concentration of stellar mass at $z = 0$ should be independent of the presence of bars.

In Paper I we found that bars with large density amplitudes (as measured from A_2) appeared together with more prominent (larger B/T) pseudobulges (i.e. bulges with Sérsic indexes $n \leq 2$). On the other hand, for $n > 2$, no dependence was found. This result is consistent with a scenario in which there is a concurrent growth of bars and disk-like bulges (or B/P bulges). Or it can mean that stronger bars nourished the growth of disk-like bulge more effectively.

5.4.2 Kinematic signatures

The effect of stellar bars perturbing the stellar and gaseous material was demonstrated in Paper III, where we showed a tight correlation between Q_b and the kinematic bar torque, which was measured from the radial-to-tangential velocities at the bar region. Moreover, this correlation might show that in these early-type galaxies the potential is governed by the stellar component in detriment to the dark matter, in agreement with the distribution of M_b/M_* ($< R_{\text{opt}}$) shown in Paper I. The efficacy of the disk potential adjusting the stellar orbits making up the bars was also demonstrated in Paper I, by showing a tight dependence between the bar ellipticity and Q_b .

In Paper III we detected σ -drops or double-humped rotation curves, which are kinematic features related to bars (e.g. Wozniak et al. 2003; Bureau & Athanassoula 2005), in the center of $\sim 60\%$ of the 16 barred galaxies in the sample. In addition, 10 of the galaxies in the sample presented a stellar angular momentum dip at $0.2 \pm 0.1 r_{\text{bar}}$. These kinematic features were attributed to the presence of cold and dense (quasi-)axisymmetric central stellar disks, most likely formed via bar-induced secular evolution. In fact, we found that the relative strength of the σ -drops and double humps, both in the stellar and gaseous components, positively correlated with the bar strength, measured from Q_b .

Morphological features in the inner parts of the galaxies are natural candidates to account for the λ_R dip. In fact, 7/10 galaxies in Paper III host a barlens, 5 have a nuclear lens and another galaxy has a ringlens. 9 of them host outer lenses or rings, or present inner features in the form of (pseudo)ring(lenses). However, inner and outer features are very unlikely to be related to any of the reported kinematic features as they typically reside at the 1/4 UHR and OLR, respectively (Paper II), i.e. beyond the bar. Nuclear resonant rings and lenses, and barlenses, are the most feasible choices, as they lie within the bar region and some of them present sizes that scale with r_{bar} . In addition, the locii of the λ_R dip was found to decrease for increasing central mass concentration. This reinforced the interpretation that nuclear rings may account for the dip, as these structures are known to shrink as they evolve (e.g. Knapen et al. 1995; Fukuda et al. 2000). However, using measurements of nuclear ring sizes and bar torques from Comerón et al. (2010), we found no obvious relation. A posteriori, we checked that the sizes of all the nuclear lenses and ringlenses, measured in Paper II, systematically appear within the locii of the local maxima and the minima of the λ_R central dip, making them a plausible choice to explain this kinematic feature.

Furthermore, the analysis of Gauss-Hermite moments in Paper III suggested that the centers of barred galaxies (within at least $0.5 r_{\text{bar}}$, and even more obvious within $0.1 r_{\text{bar}}$) host dynamically distinct components, that could be attributed to disk-like bulges formed via SF from the gas driven by bar to the inner kpc. Specifically, an anticorrelation between h_3 and V/σ within these apertures was found in many of the galaxies. Interestingly enough, most of these systems host a barlens, therefore this anticorrelation could be taken as a kinematic signature of their presence. However, the face-on kinematic signatures of boxy/peanut bulges that are found in simulation models (e.g. Iannuzzi & Athanassoula 2015) were not detected.

Finally, we observed that the outer gradient of the stellar σ profiles tends to be smaller for larger values of Q_b , meaning that stronger bars seem to be more effective at causing σ flattening in our sample. This constitutes additional support for bars being effective agents triggering radial motions of stars and orbital mixing, and thus flattening the σ gradients. This seems consistent with the results in Martin & Roy (1994). They provided evidence for the large-scale bar-induced mixing of interstellar gas, finding that stronger and longer bars tend to induce radial flows

that make the O/H gradients flatter.

All the evidence for the bar-driven secular evolution of spiral galaxies presented in this section is consistent with bars being long-lived structures (e.g. Shen & Sellwood 2004; Villa-Vargas et al. 2010; Athanassoula et al. 2013).

Chapter 6

Conclusions

The main goal of this thesis was to study the properties of stellar bars, to address their growth, and to investigate the bar-driven secular evolution of disks. In particular, we aimed to unravel the nature of (pseudo)bulges, spiral arms, rings, lenses and barlenses, and to understand the role of stellar bars in their formation. We also intended to probe the interplay between stellar and non-baryonic matter in disk galaxies. The results in this work are mainly based on the $3.6\ \mu\text{m}$ photometry of the Spitzer Survey of Stellar Structure in Galaxies (S⁴G, Sheth et al. 2010), combined with high-resolution kinematic data from Seidel et al. (2015b) and Erroz-Ferrer et al. (2015). The most important conclusions of this thesis, based on the study of photometric and kinematic properties of S⁴G disk galaxies, are the following:

- Among disk galaxies, the strength and the length of the bars are strongly correlated. This observation agrees with the evolutionary track followed by bars in N-body simulation models (e.g. Athanassoula 2003).
- Stellar bars play a fundamental role in the radial spread of the disk, as shown by the comparison of average stellar density profiles of barred and non-barred galaxies, and the flattening of the outer stellar velocity dispersion profiles with increasing bar strength. This is in agreement with different simulation models (e.g. Athanassoula & Misiriotis 2002; Minchev et al. 2011; Athanassoula 2012).
- Based on the analysis of mean stellar density profiles, we show that barred galaxies present larger central mass concentrations than the non-barred galaxies. This demonstrates the role of bars funneling material towards the inner parts of the galaxy (e.g. Sellwood & Wilkinson 1993). We identify inner kinematic features related to bars, like double-hump velocity profiles and velocity dispersion drops (expected from the simulations by e.g. Bureau & Athanassoula 2005). We also find a dip in the stellar angular momentum, which is probably associated to the presence of inner stellar substructures.

- There is a connection in the properties of bars and inner substructures (rings and lenses) and barlenses in disk galaxies. Our results reinforce the interpretation that barlenses, that typically appear in massive galaxies with strong bars, are B/P bulges seen in face-on perspective (Laurikainen et al. 2007, 2014; Athanassoula et al. 2015). Our observations suggest that some inner lenses were previously barlenses (Laurikainen et al. 2013).
- We find that the amount of dark matter within the optical disk, estimated from the H I maximum amplitudes available in the literature, scales with the total stellar mass estimated from mid-infrared images, in a manner expected from the Λ CDM models (e.g. Moster et al. 2010). On average, the amount of dark matter within optical disk is about 4% that of the total host halo. We confirm the correlation between the observed inner slope of the rotation curve and the central surface brightness of the galaxy (Lelli et al. 2013). Our observations indicate that the central regions of galaxies are dominated by baryonic mass.
- Early-type ($T < 5 \equiv \text{Sc}$) and late-type ($T \geq 5$) disk galaxies are characterized by remarkably different disk properties. In terms of stellar mass the same division corresponds to galaxies with masses greater or smaller than $10^{10} M_{\odot}$. As quantified by the stacked density profiles of S⁴G galaxies, the massive systems have larger central mass concentrations than fainter ones, among which many galaxies are bulge-less. Our estimates indicate that faint late-type galaxies are more dark matter dominated within the optical disk than their early-type counterparts (in agreement with e.g. Courteau & Dutton 2015)
- Two distinct type of stellar bars are hosted by early-type ($T < 5$) and late-type ($T \geq 5$) disk galaxies, based on the frequency, length and strength of bars. Statistically, bars in early-type spirals are longer and have larger density amplitudes than in the intermediate-type ($T \approx 5$) spirals. The detection of bars in late-type galaxies is strongly dependent on the identification criteria: nevertheless, their sizes seem increase again compared to intermediate-types. In comparison to earlier types, the bars in late-type systems show larger tangential-to-radial force ratios. This result holds even when the estimated dark halo effect is included.

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